

Copernicus DEMs Quality Assessment Summary

Author(s): **Kevin Gross, Axel Corseaux**
Task 5 Team

Approval: **Serge Riazanoff**
Task 5 Lead

Accepted: **Clément Albinet**
EDAP Technical Officer

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Reference document

The following is a list of reference documents with a direct bearing on the content of this Technical Note. Where referenced in the text, these are identified as [RD-n], where 'n' is the number in the list below:

1.1.1 Quality assessment

- RD-1.** EDAP.REP.001 *EDAP Quality Assessment Guidelines*
issue 1.3, 16 October 2019
NPL
..\management\20191120_Piro_EDAP.REP.001_1.3 - Mission Quality Assessment Guidelines.pdf
- RD-2.** QA4ECV PUM *QA4ECV Documentation Guidance: Product User Manual*
Version 1.0, May 2017
QA4ECV
<http://www.qa4ecv.eu/sites/default/files/QA4ECV%20PUM%20Guidance.pdf>
- RD-3.** QA4ECV ATBD *QA4ECV Product Documentation Guidance: Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document*
Version 1.0, May 2017
QA4ECV
<http://www.qa4ecv.eu/sites/default/files/QA4ECV%20ATBD%20Guidance.pdf>
- RD-4.** JCGM 100:2008 *Evaluation of measurement data – Guide to the expression of uncertainty in measurement*
First edition, September 2008
Joint Committee for Guides in Metrology
https://www.bipm.org/documents/20126/2071204/JCGM_100_2008_E.pdf

1.1.2 TerraSAR-X and TanDEM-X

- RD-5.** Krieger, 2012 *TanDEM-X: A radar interferometer with two formation flying satellites*
63rd International Astronautical Congress, Naples, Italy, International Astronautical Federation.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actaastro.2013.03.008>
- RD-6.** Bachmann & al., 2009 *TerraSAR-X Antenna Calibration and Monitoring Based on a Precise Antenna Model*
IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing, vol. 48, no. 2, pp. 690-701, Feb. 2010
<https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/5356173>
- RD-7.** Post-launch calibration *TerraSAR-X Calibration results*
July 2018
German Aerospace Center
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/224232741_TerraSAR-X_calibration_results

RD-8. González & al, 2008 *TanDEM-X DEM Calibration Concept and Height References*
7th European Conference on Synthetic Aperture Radar, 2008, pp. 1-4.
https://elib.dlr.de/53636/1/DEM_Calibration_Concept-hueso.pdf

RD-9. González & al, 2012 *Bistatic system and baseline calibration in TanDEM-X to ensure the global digital elevation model quality*
ISPRS Journal of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing, ISSN: 0924-2716, Vol: 73, Page: 3-11
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isprsjprs.2012.05.008>

1.1.3 Copernicus DEMs

RD-10. Data access *Data Discovery and Download*
Copernicus Space Component Data Access
<https://spacedata.copernicus.eu/fr/web/cscda/data-access/discovery-and-download>

RD-11. Product Handbook *Copernicus Digital Elevation Model Product Handbook version 3.0, 9 November 2020*
Airbus
https://spacedata.copernicus.eu/documents/20126/0/GEO1988-CopernicusDEM-SPE-002_ProductHandbook_I3.0.pdf

RD-12. TD-GS-PS-0021 *TanDEM-X - Ground Segment - DEM Products Specification Document*
issue 3.1, 05.08.2016
DLR
https://elib.dlr.de/108014/1/TD-GS-PS-0021_DEM-Product-Specification_v3.1.pdf

RD-13. WorldDEM TPS *WorldDEM™ Technical Product Specification - Digital Surface Model, Digital Terrain Model*
version 2.5, April 2019 - Airbus
https://www.intelligence-airbusds.com/automne/api/docs/v1.0/document/download/ZG9jdXRoZXF1ZS1kb2N1bWVudC01NTcyOQ==/ZG9jdXRoZXF1ZS1maWxILTU1NzI4/WorldDEM_TechnicalSpecifications_Version2.6-202012.pdf

RD-14. P. Rizzoli & al., 2017 *Generation and performance assessment of the global TanDEM-X digital elevation model*
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.isprsjprs.2017.08.008>

RD-15. Validation report *Copernicus DEM Validation Report*
version 3.0, 9 November 2020
Airbus
https://spacedata.copernicus.eu/documents/20126/0/GEO1988-CopernicusDEM-RP-001_ValidationReport_I3.0.pdf

RD-16. K. Becek & al., 2016 *Evaluation of Vertical Accuracy of the WorldDEM™ Using the Runway Method*
Remote Sens. 2016, 8(11), 934;
<https://doi.org/10.3390/rs8110934>

RD-17. COPE-PMAN-EOPG-TN-15-0004

*Copernicus Space Component Data Access Portfolio:
Data Warehouse 2014 – 2020*
issue/revision 2.7, 16/12/2019 - ESRIN
<https://spacedata.copernicus.eu/documents/20126/0/DAP+Document+-+current+%2810%29.pdf>

1.1.4 ICESat-1

RD-18. User Guide

*User guide GLAS/ICESat L2 Global Land Surface
Altimetry Data*
23 October 2014
National Snow and Ice Data Center
https://nsidc.org/data/GLAH14/versions/34?qt-data_set_tabs=3#qt-data_set_tabs

RD-19. Data Management Plan

Science Data Management Plan
Version 4.0
July 1999
Peggy L. Jester and David W. Hancock III
<https://glas.wff.nasa.gov/wp-content/uploads/sdmp.pdf>

RD-20. Cal/Val Plan

*GLAS Altimeter Post-Launch Calibration/Validation
Plan*
Version 1.0, October 2001
Bob E. Schutz
http://www2.csr.utexas.edu/glas/pdf/plan/validation_plan_v1_oct2001.pdf

RD-21. Glas_laser_ops_attrib

*NSIDC Distributed ICESat GLAS Laser Operations
Periods*
December 2014
National Snow and Ice Data Center
https://nsidc.org/sites/nsidc.org/files/files/glas_laser_ops_attrib.pdf

1.1.5 ICESat-2

RD-22. ATL08 User Guide

*ATLAS/ICESat-2 L3A Land and Vegetation Height,
Version 3 - User Guide*
23 June 2020
National Snow and Ice Data Center
https://nsidc.org/data/atl08?qt-data_set_tabs=3

RD-23. ATL08 ATBD

*Ice, Cloud, and Land Elevation Satellite 2 (ICESat-2)
Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document (ATBD) for
Land - Vegetation Along-Track Products (ATL08)*
15 January 2020
Amy Neuenschwander and Katherine Pitts
https://nsidc.org/sites/nsidc.org/files/technical-references/ICESat2_ATL08_ATBD_r003.pdf

RD-24. Major Activities

ICESat-2 Major Activities (includes yaw flips)
13 January 2021
Kaitlin Harbeck
https://nsidc.org/sites/nsidc.org/files/technical-references/ICESat2_major_activities_01122021.xlsx

- RD-25.** ATL08 Data Dictionary *ATL08 Data Dictionary (V03)*
03 February 2020
NASA/GSFC
https://nsidc.org/sites/nsidc.org/files/technical-references/ICESat2_ATL08_data_dict_v003.pdf
- RD-26.** ATL08 Release 003 *ATL08 Land and Vegetation Data product – Release 003*
15 March 2020
Amy Neuenschwander and Ben Jelley
https://nsidc.org/sites/nsidc.org/files/technical-references/ICESat2_ATL08_Known_Issues_v003_Aug_2020.pdf
- RD-27.** C. Carabajal & al., 2020 *ICESat-2 Altimetry as Geodetic Control*
Int. Arch. Photogramm. Remote Sens. Spatial Inf. Sci., XLIII-B3-2020, 1299–1306
<https://doi.org/10.5194/isprs-archives-XLIII-B3-2020-1299-2020>

1.1.6 GEDI

- RD-28.** L2 User Guide *GLOBAL Ecosystem Dynamics Investigation (GEDI) Level 2 User Guide*
Version 2.1, April 2021
NASA, UMD

https://lpdaac.usgs.gov/documents/998/GEDI02_UserGuide_V21.pdf
- RD-29.** L2A Data Dictionary *GEDI L2A Product Data Dictionary*
NASA GSFC, UMD
https://lpdaac.usgs.gov/documents/982/gedi_l2a_dictionary_P003_v2.html
- RD-30.** Waveform ATBD *Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document (ATBD) for GEDI Transmit and Receive Waveform Processing of L1 and L2 Products*
Version 1.0, 4 December 2019
NASA GSFC, UMD
https://doi.org/10.5067/DOC/GEDI/GEDI_WF_ATBD.001
- RD-31.** Geolocation ATBD *Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document (ATBD) for GEDI Waveform Geolocation for L1 and L2 Products*
Version 1.0, 5 December 2019
NASA GSFC, UMD
https://doi.org/10.5067/DOC/GEDI/GEDI_WFGEO_ATBD.001
[..reference documents\20191205_Luthcke_Algorithm_Theoretical_Basis_Document_for_GEDI_Waveform_Geolocation_for_L1_and_L2_Products.pdf](https://reference.documents\20191205_Luthcke_Algorithm_Theoretical_Basis_Document_for_GEDI_Waveform_Geolocation_for_L1_and_L2_Products.pdf)
- RD-32.** R. Dubayah & al., 2020 *The Global Ecosystem Dynamics Investigation: High-resolution laser ranging of the Earth's forests and topography*
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.srs.2020.100002>

1.1.7 CCI-LC / C3S-LC

- RD-33.** CCI-LC-PUGV2 *Land Cover CCI Product User Guide*
Version 2.0, 10 April 2017
European Space Agency
http://maps.elie.ucl.ac.be/CCI/viewer/download/ESACC-I-LC-Ph2-PUGv2_2.0.pdf
- RD-34.** CCI-LC-ATBD *Land Cover CCI Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document*
issue 2.3, 28 November 2013
European Space Agency
https://www.esa-landcover-cci.org/?q=webfm_send/75
- RD-35.** CCI-LC-DPM *Land Cover CCI Detailed Processing Model*
Version 2.3, 27 November 2013
European Space Agency
https://www.esa-landcover-cci.org/?q=webfm_send/77

1.1.8 Vertical reference systems

- RD-36.** EGM2008 *Office of Geomatics, Earth Gravitational Model 2008 Data and Apps*
National Geospatial-Intelligence Agency
<https://earth-info.nga.mil/>

1.1.9 Other studies

- RD-37.** EDAP.REP.029 *Global DEM quality assessment summary*
Issue 1.2, 16/07/2020 – VisioTerra
https://visioterra.fr/telechargement/P317_ESA_EDAP/EDAP.REP.029_1.2_Global_DEM_Quality_Assessment_Summary.pdf
- RD-38.** HYP-087-VtWeb *Presentation of ICESat-2 ATLAS*

https://visioterra.fr/telechargement/A003_VISIOTERRA_COMMUNICATION/HYP-087-VtWeb-E_Presentation_of_ICESat-2_ATLAS.pdf
- RD-39.** HYP-089-VtWeb *Comparison of Digital Elevation Models (DEMs) in Chott Melghir (Algeria)*

https://visioterra.fr/telechargement/A003_VISIOTERRA_COMMUNICATION/HYP-089-VtWeb_Comparison_of_DEMs_in_Chott_Melghir_Algeria.pdf
- RD-40.** HYP-093-VtWeb *Le MNT Copernicus en RDC*

https://visioterra.fr/telechargement/A003_VISIOTERRA_COMMUNICATION/HYP-093-VtWeb-F_MNT_Copernicus_en_RDC.pdf
- RD-41.** HYP-094-VtWeb *Assessment of slopes in Alaska LiDAR DEM*

https://visioterra.fr/telechargement/A003_VISIOTERRA_COMMUNICATION/HYP-094-VtWeb-E_Assessment_of_slopes_in_Alaska_LiDAR_DEM.pdf
- RD-42.** HYP-095-VtWeb *Comparison of Copernicus DEM releases 2020 vs 2019*

https://visioterra.fr/telechargement/A003_VISIOTERRA_COMMUNICATION/HYP-095-VtWeb-E_Comparison_of_Copernicus_DEM_releases_2020_vs_2019.pdf

RD-43. HYP-096-VtWeb

Comparison of LiDAR GEDI vs ICESat-1/ICESat-2
https://visioterra.fr/telechargement/A003_VISIOTERRA_COMMUNICATION/HYP-096-VtWeb-E_Comparison_of_LiDAR_GEDI_vs_ICESat-1_ICESat-2.pdf

RD-44. HYP-097-VtWeb

NASADEM vs SRTMGL1 comparison
https://visioterra.fr/telechargement/A003_VISIOTERRA_COMMUNICATION/HYP-097-VtWeb-E_NASADEM_SRTMGL1_comparison.pdf

RD-45. HYP-098-VtWeb

COP-DEM and EU-DEM comparison
https://visioterra.fr/telechargement/A003_VISIOTERRA_COMMUNICATION/HYP-098-VtWeb-E_COP-DEM_EU-DEM_comparison.pdf

RD-46. HYP-099-VtWeb

COP-DEM GLO-90 vs. GLO-30 for Sentinel-2 orthorectification
https://visioterra.fr/telechargement/A003_VISIOTERRA_COMMUNICATION/HYP-099-VtWeb-E_COP-DEM_GLO-90_vs_GLO-30_for_Sentinel-2_orthorectification.pdf

1.2 Glossary

The following acronyms and abbreviations have been used in this Report.

ALOS	Advanced Land Observing Satellite
ASTER	Advanced Spaceborne Thermal Emission and Reflection Radiometer
ATBD	Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document
ATLAS	Advanced Topographic Laser Altimeter System
AVNIR-2	Advanced Visible and Near Infrared Radiometer type 2
AW3D	ALOS World 3D
AW3D30	ALOS World 3D – 30 m
C3S	Copernicus Climate Change Service
CCI	Climate Change Initiative
CEOS	Committee on Earth Observation Satellites
CRS	Coordinates Reference System
DEM	Digital Elevation Model
DGED	Defense Gridded Elevation Data
DLR	Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt
DSM	Digital Surface Model
DTED	Digital Terrain Elevation Data
DTM	Digital Terrain Model
EEA	European Economic Area
EEA 10	European Economic Area DEM 0.4"arcsecond (\approx 10 metres)
EGM96	Earth Gravitational Model 1996
EGM2008	Earth Gravitational Model 2008
EPSG	European Petroleum Survey Group
ESA	European Space Agency
GCP	Ground Control Point
GDEM	Global Digital Elevation Model
GEDI	Global Ecosystem Dynamics Investigation
GeoTIFF	Geocoded TIFF
GL1	Global 1" arc
GLAS	Geoscience Laser Altimeter System
GPS	Global Positioning System
GSD	Ground Sampling Distance
HDF5	Hierarchical Data Format version 5
ICESat-1	Ice, Cloud and land Elevation Satellite 1
ICESat-2	Ice, Cloud and land Elevation Satellite 2
INSPIRE	INfrastructure for SPatial InfoRmation in Europe
ISS	International Space Station
JAXA	Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency
LiDAR	Light Detection and Ranging
LP DAAC	Land Processes Distributed Active Archive Center
KML	Keyhole Markup Language
METI	Ministry of Economy, Trade, and Industry (Japan)
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration (USA)
NGA	National Geospatial-Intelligence Agency (USA, former NIMA)
NSIDC	National Snow and Ice Data Center
PALSAR	Phased Array L-band Synthetic Aperture Radar
PRISM	Panchromatic Remote-sensing Instrument for Stereo Mapping
RMSE	Root Mean Square Error
SAR	Synthetic Aperture Radar
SIR-C	Shuttle Imaging Radar-C
SRTM	Shuttle Radar Topography Mission
SRTM-GL1	Shuttle Radar Topography Mission Global 1 arc second
STS-99	Space Transportation System 99 (Endeavour)
TanDEM-X	TerraSAR-X add-on for Digital Elevation Measurements
TIFF	Tagged Image File Format

UMD University of Maryland
USGS United States Geological Survey
VRS Vertical Reference System
WGS84 World Geodetic System 1984

1.3 Definitions

The following definitions have been used in this Report.

**coordinates
reference
system (CRS)**

geographic

**DTM
or
DEM
or
DSM**

The “Digital Terrain Model” is also called “Digital Elevation Model” (DEM) or sometimes “Altimetry model”. A DEM is a raster data made of a georeferenced grid in which each cell gives an altitude with regard to a geoid (most frequent case) or a height above an ellipsoid.

In maritime parts, the altitudes or elevations may give the sea level (altitude equal to 0 metres above a geoid) or may give the ocean floor (negative values also called bathymetry).

The “Digital Surface Model” (DSM) gives altitudes or heights above overground: building roofs, top of canopy, sea level...

KML

The KML (Keyhole Markup Language) is a XML grammar describing the objects (points, lines, images, polygons) handled by Google Earth.

KML is based on the version 3.0 of the GML (Geographic Markup Language).

hyperlook Rich URL containing the server address / product identifier / processing parameters / geometry of view) that readers may activate to achieve the same views in their usual Web browser (Internet Explorer, Firefox, Chrome, Safari...).

Metrology
accuracy vs. precision
Accuracy measures the closeness of agreement between a measured quantity value and a true quantity value. Distance between the arithmetic mean and the reference value is called the bias.

The precision measures the closeness of agreement between indications or measured quantity values obtained by replicate measurements on the same or similar objects under specified conditions.

See https://www.bipm.org/utis/common/documents/jcgm/JCGM_200_2012.pdf

vertical reference system

There are three types of reference surface:

- topography - being the site of the interface between the solid phase and the gaseous and liquid phases of terrestrial matter;
- geoid - equipotential surface of the acceleration field of gravity (gravity + centrifugal force); the geoid is close to the mean surface of the sea;
- ellipsoid - regular surface resulting from the rotation of an ellipse around its minor axis and approximating at best the geoid in an area of interest.

The heights H with respect to the geoid (also called "altitude") are reference heights for the study of physical phenomena such as runoff. The altitude 0 metre corresponds to the mean sea level.

The heights h with respect to the ellipsoid (also called "elevation") are used for terrestrial modelling and in particular for orthorectification with respect to a reference ellipsoid (often WGS84).

2. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

2.1 Maturity Matrix

Product Information	Product Generation	Ancillary Information	Uncertainty Characterisation	Validation
Product Details	Sensor Calibration & Characterisation Pre-Flight	Product Flags	Uncertainty Characterisation Method	Reference Data Representativeness
Availability & Accessibility	Sensor Calibration & Characterisation Post-Launch	Ancillary Data	Uncertainty Sources Included	Reference Data Quality
Product Format	Retrieval Algorithm Method		Uncertainty Values Provided	Validation Method
User Documentation	Retrieval Algorithm Tuning		Geolocation Uncertainty	Validation Results
Metrological Traceability Documentation	Additional Processing			

Key
Not Assessed
Not Assessable
Basic
Intermediate
Good
Excellent

Information Not Public

Table 1 - Copernicus DEMs Product Quality Evaluation Matrix.

2.2 Summary of quality assessment

This document presents the quality assessment of the three Copernicus DEMs: Copernicus DEM EEA-10, Copernicus DEM GLO-30 and Copernicus DEM GLO-90. A first major section focuses on evaluating the maturity of the Copernicus DEMs (see section 3), with respect to the EDAP Quality Assessment Guidelines (see RD-1). The second major section of the document encompasses two quality assessment methods (see section 4):

- **Qualitative assessments** - the VisioTerra VtWeb tool is used to compute the difference between Copernicus DEM GLO-30 and ALOS World 3D. This tool allows to compute the difference between two DEMs at any scale, immediately highlighting their anomalies (see section 4.1).
- **Quantitative assessments** - Copernicus DEM EEA-10, GLO-30 and GLO-90 are compared to ICESat-1 / GLAS, ICESat-2 / ATLAS and GEDI LiDAR reference data. Five quantitative studies are followed per DEM, respectively using ICESat-1, ICESat-2 terrain, ICESat-2 terrain with canopy, GEDI lowest mode (ground) and GEDI highest return (top of canopy) heights as vertical references (see sections 4.2 and 4.3).

Illustrations and results of the qualitative assessment, consisting of comparing ALOS World 3D to Copernicus DEM GLO-30, are available in section 4.1. This section provides both global views of this comparison and a case study of the Lake Garda in Italy, highlighting an anomaly of ALOS World 3D.

Regarding the quantitative assessment, this technical note aims to answer to the following questions:

- Considering ICESat-1, ICESat-2 and GEDI products, which reference data is the most suitable for DEM quantitative assessments?
- Which instance (among EEA-10, GLO-30 and GLO-90) of the Copernicus DEM has the best overall height error statistics?
- Taking into account results of previous quantitative assessments of ALOS World 3D, ASTER GDEM and SRTMGL1 (RD-37), and the results of the quantitative assessment of Copernicus DEM GLO-30, which global DEM at 1" is the most accurate?

The quantitative studies show that the best results are achieved with **ICESat-1**, retrieving an arithmetical mean of 0.033 metres and a RMSE of 0.628 metres among all height differences for the assessment of Copernicus DEM GLO-30 (LE95 statistics). Similar results are achieved with **ICESat-2 terrain height only**, with an arithmetical mean of 0.195 metres and a RMSE of 0.999 metres. Worse results are obtained using **ICESat-2 terrain with canopy height** as a vertical reference, retrieving an arithmetical mean of -1.124 m and a RMSE of 2.907 m. Considering **GEDI lowest mode** reference data gives an arithmetical mean of 1.088 m, but a high RMSE of 3.639 m. The worst statistics are obtained considering **GEDI highest return**, retrieving an arithmetical mean of -5.840 m and a RMSE of 6.710 m. According to these studies, ICESat-1 seems to be the best vertical reference for DEM quantitative assessments. ICESat-2 terrain heights give similar results and is still recommended for DEM quantitative assessments. ICESat-2 terrain with canopy heights is not recommended, as the canopy height is only an estimation and not the actual canopy height retrieved at each geolocation indicated in the ICESat-2 products. GEDI lowest mode and highest return are not recommended as the statistics show very high error arithmetic mean and RMSE.

Among **Copernicus DEM EEA-10, GLO-30 and GLO-90**, the **Copernicus DEM GLO-30** obtains the best height error statistics. Considering ICESat-1 reference data, a mean of 0.033 metres, a standard deviation of 0.627 metres and a RMSE of 0.628 m are obtained for the height errors of Copernicus DEM GLO-30 (see section 4.2.5.3). Copernicus DEM GLO-90 height error statistics show similar results, with a mean of 0.066 metres, a standard deviation of 0.706 metres and a RMSE of 0.709 metres (see section 4.2.6.3). Copernicus DEM EEA-10 height error statistics are the worse, considering a mean of 0.276 metres, a standard deviation of 1.389 metres and a RMSE of 1.415 metres (see section 4.2.4.3).

The quality of **ALOS World 3D**, **ASTER GDEM**, **SRTMGL1** and **Copernicus DEM GLO-30** was assessed using **ICESat-1** reference data. These DEMs are available at global scale and share the same spatial resolution of 1". In previous quantitative studies, ALOS World 3D was assessed to be the best DEM, as opposed to SRTMGL1 and ASTER GDEM (see RD-37). According to the quantitative studies of this technical note, **Copernicus DEM GLO-30 is assessed to be the best DEM**, showing a significant improvement with regard to the three other global DEMs. The height error statistics of Copernicus DEM GLO-30 are even better than those of ALOS World 3D, retrieving a mean of 0.033 metres, a standard deviation of 0.627 metres and a RMSE of 0.628 metres, as opposed to ALOS World 3D, which obtained a mean of -0.151 m, a standard deviation of 1.660 metres and a RMSE of 1.653 metres (LE95 statistics, see section 5.3.4).

3. PRODUCT ASSESSMENT OVERVIEW

3.1 Overview of Copernicus DEMs generation and products

3.1.1 Short history of Copernicus DEMs

The German Space Agency (DLR) has developed great skills in the field of X-band Radar imaging. Its first successes were achieved in the 1990s by developing the "SRTM-XSAR" instrument within the framework of the famous [SRTM mission](#) in partnership with the United States Space Agency (NASA).

During the 2000s, the DLR developed an ambitious X-band acquisition program involving two identical satellites: TerraSAR-X and then TanDEM-X whose very close orbits make it possible to calculate centimetric vertical displacements of the ground by interferometry and a digital model of all the Earth with a sampling step (12m) and an unrivalled vertical accuracy.

3.1.2 The TanDEM-X constellation

A new era in radar remote sensing began 10 years ago, on 21 June 2010, when the radar satellite TanDEM-X was launched. Since then, it has been orbiting Earth in close formation flight with TerraSAR-X, its three-year-older 'twin'. The distance between the satellites varies between several kilometres and sometimes only 120 metres. This enables the radar sensors to obtain a 3D view of Earth. This is referred to as a bistatic interferometer in space, which allows the terrain structure to be recorded in three dimensions in just one pass. This space mission continues to be globally unique.

The primary mission objective – the creation of a highly accurate global elevation model of Earth's entire landmass – was achieved as early as mid-2016 with the completion of the TanDEM-X DEM (Digital Elevation Model). The digital elevation model provides precise topographic information and sets a new standard due to its high accuracy and global homogeneity. The DEM product is available in three different resolution variants. Depending on the quality requirements, elevation measurements were calculated for a grid of 12, 30 or 90 metres. The absolute height error, the inaccuracy of each measurement – only 1.3 metres – is extremely small and far exceeds the original requirement of 10 metres. (extracted from https://www.dlr.de/content/en/articles/news/2020/02/20200625_congratulations-tandem-x-ten-years-of-3d-mapping-from-space.html).

	TerraSAR-X (TSX)	TanDEM-X (TDX)
Launch date	15.06.2007	21.06.2010
Orbital altitude	514.8 km	514 km
Revisit time (orbit repeat cycle)	11 days	11 days
Radar frequency	9.65 GHz	9.65 GHz
Radar wavelength	3.1 cm (X band)	3.1 cm (X band)
Orbital plan inclination	97.4° (Sun synchronous)	97.4° (Sun synchronous)
Polarizations	HH, VH, HV, VV	HH, VH, HV, VV

Table 2 - Main features of TerraSAR-X and TanDEM-X.

One may find an accurate description of the two satellites formation in RD-5.

Figure 1 - View of the close satellite formation (left) and the helix satellite formation (right).

This precise configuration enables each one of the two satellites to receive the backscattered energy from the pulse sent by it-self (monostatic) or sent by the other satellite and received by both satellites (bistatic).

Figure 2- Data acquisition configurations: Pursuit monostatic (left), bistatic (middle), and alternating bistatic (right).

3.1.3 Produced by TanDEM-X constellation

Elevations expressed in the Copernicus DEMs were acquired by two satellites: TerraSAR-X and TanDEM-X. Some confusions are made between those terms, because the name TanDEM-X refers both as the satellite name and the constellation of both satellites.

The main goal of the TanDEM-X constellation was to create a global DEM using both the TerraSAR-X and TanDEM-X satellites. This DEM, TerraSAR-X DEM, was the source DEM used to create WorldDEM™ which is the basis of the three Copernicus DEMs.

3.1.4 Becoming an element of Copernicus programme

The global instances of the Copernicus DEM are available cost-free (Copernicus DEM GLO-30 and Copernicus DEM GLO-90). Only Copernicus DEM EEA-10 and some countries of Copernicus DEM GLO-30 have a restricted access to public. The current licensing can be found at the following link:

https://spacedata.copernicus.eu/documents/20126/0/CSCDA_ESA_Mission-specific+Annex.pdf/5308d1e7-17de-b55b-2be8-8a3a286aa88b?t=1581077110498

3.1.5 Formats of Copernicus DEMs

The Copernicus DEM instances are available in three different formats depending on the product resolution:

- **DGED** (Defence Gridded Elevation Data) – This is the main format of the Copernicus DEMs. It is available for the three products resolutions and provides elevation data as 32-bit floating data within GeoTIFF image format. The associated metadata are given as XML files and the quality data as GeoTIFF images.
- **DTED** (Digital Terrain Elevation Data) – This format is available for the GLO-30 and GLO-90 products. It provides elevation data as 16-bit integer data.
- **INSPIRE** – This format is available for the EEA-10 product only. It provides the elevation as a 32-bit floating data with a slightly better spatial resolution (0.3" arc second instead of 0.4" arc second).

The table here below sums up the available formats.

	INSPIRE	DGED	DTED
EEA-10	X	X	
GLO-30		X	X
GLO-90		X	X

Table 3 - Copernicus DEMs available formats.

The DGED format has been selected for this study as well as for the import of the Copernicus DEMs in the VtWeb platform for, at least, the following reasons: -the format is the same for the three products, -it provides elevation data with great accuracy and -the GeoTIFF format is widely supported.

3.1.6 Copernicus DEMs product generation

This section gathers technical information about the three Copernicus DEMs: **Copernicus DEM EEA-10**, **Copernicus DEM GLO-30** and **Copernicus DEM GLO-90**, as the three DEMs are described in the same technical documents and share many common features.

As the Copernicus DEMs are derived from the WorldDEM™ and the TanDEM-X DEM, some of the next references (such as the ATBD) are not directly referring to the Copernicus DEMs. The following figure (see 1.1.3) summarizes the generation process of the Copernicus DEMs:

Figure 3 – Copernicus DEMs Generation Process Chart (See 1.1.3).

3.2 EDAP standard tables

3.2.1 Product Information

All the required information has been found: the Copernicus DEMs have been given the Excellent grade for Product Details.

Product Details	
Product Names	<i>Copernicus DEM EEA-10 Copernicus DEM GLO-30 Copernicus DEM GLO-90</i>
Sensor Name	<i>SAR-X (both satellites)</i>
Sensor Type	<i>X-band SAR (both sensors)</i>
Mission Type	<i>TanDEM-X mission (TanDEM-X/TerraSAR-X satellites)</i>
Mission Orbit	<i>Sun synchronous, 97.44 degrees of inclination</i>
Product Version Number	<i>2019_1 (not explicitly given but deduced from the data directory name). The present study is based on this version. 2020_1 is a second version that has been notified in January 2021 and integrated recently in VtWeb (RD-42).</i>
Product IDs	<i>COP-DEM_EEA-10-DGED short-named EEA-10 COP-DEM_GLO-30-DGED short-named GLO-30 COP-DEM_GLO-90-DGED short named GLO-90</i>
Processing level of product	<i>Level 3</i>
Measured Quantity Name	<i>Elevation</i>
Measured Quantity Units	<i>metres</i>
Stated Measurement Quality	<i>Absolute vertical accuracy: < 4m (90% linear error) Relative vertical accuracy: < 2m for slopes below or equal 20%, < 4m for slopes above 20% (90% linear point-to-point error within an area of 1° x 1°)</i>
Spatial Resolution	<i>1 arc second in latitude, variable in longitude (0.4 to 4.0 arc seconds depending on the latitude)</i>
Spatial Coverages	<i>Copernicus DEM GLO-30, GLO-90: Global Copernicus DEM EEA-10: European Economic Area</i>
Temporal Resolution	<i>11 days (TanDEM-X orbit repeat cycle)</i>
Temporal Coverage	<i>2010 to 2015 (TanDEM-X acquisitions)</i>
Point of Contact	<i>Copernicus Services Coordinated Interface (SCI)</i> <i>ESA - European Space Agency EOSupport@Copernicus.esa.int</i>
Product locator (DOI/URL)	<i>https://spacedata.copernicus.eu/web/cscda/dataset-details?articleId=394198</i>
Conditions for access and use	<i>https://spacedata.copernicus.eu/documents/20126/0/CSCDA_ESA_Mission-specific+Annex.pdf/5308d1e7-17de-b55b-2be8-8a3a286aa88b?t=1581077110498</i>
Limitations on public access	<i>Restricted access for the EEA-10 instances, public release for the GLO-30 and GLO-90 instances (Armenia and Azerbaijan have limited access to GLO-30 as specified in https://spacedata.copernicus.eu/fr/web/cscda/explore-more/news-archive/-/asset_publisher/Ye8eqYeRPLEs/blog/id/434960 and the Excel table at https://spacedata.copernicus.eu/documents/20126/0/Non-released-</i>

	tiles_GLO-30_PUBLIC_Dec.xlsx/bcdd6cef-6379-4890-de8f-788daf41dce8?t=1608549440765
Product Abstract	The Copernicus DEM is a Digital Surface Model (DSM) which represents the surface of the Earth including buildings, infrastructure and vegetation. This DEM is derived from an edited DSM named WorldDEM™. The Copernicus DEM is provided in 3 different instances named EEA-10, GLO-30 and GLO-90. The Copernicus DEM instances have varying geographical extent (European and global) and varying format (INSPIRE, DGED, DTED).

To discriminate between the four FAIR principles and to assess a global notation more traceable, four notations have been given over 4 (Findable), 3 (Accessible), 3 (Interoperable) and 4 (Reusable) leading to a total notation over 14.

Copernicus DEM instances fully meet the FAIR principles and have an associated Data Management Plan, which gives an Excellent grade to Copernicus DEMs for the Availability & Accessibility section.

Availability & Accessibility	
Compliant with FAIR principles	Yes (14/14)
Data Management Plan	CSC data access (RD-17)
Availability Status	Available via HTTP/FTP (registered users only, see RD-10)

As the Copernicus DEM instances are available in the GeoTIFF format and follow a specific metadata convention, an Excellent grade has been given for Product Format.

Product Format	
Product File Format	GeoTIFF
Metadata Conventions	ISO 19115 Geographic Information – Metadata (First edition, 2003-05-01)
Analysis Ready Data?	Yes

As a product user guide is available (but not QA4EVC compliant, see RD-2 for product user guide assessment guidelines) and a physical description has been found, but no ATBD, the Intermediate grade has been given for User Documentation.

User Documentation		
Document	Reference	QA4ECV Compliant
Product User Guide	See 1.1.3	No case studies given
ATBD	See RD-14	No specific ATBD but a good physical description found in RD-14

As no proper metrological traceability has been found (except for a first elevation budget), but as a traceability chain is present in the user guide, identifying most of the important processing steps of the Copernicus DEM instances, the Intermediate grade has been given for Metrological Traceability Documentation.

Metrological Traceability Documentation	
Document Reference	A first elevation error budget of WorldDEM™ (Copernicus DEM is a successor of WorldDEM™ as shown in Figure 3) is given in RD-16.
Traceability Chain / Uncertainty Tree Diagram Available	Yes, but not strictly following the QA4ECV (see 1.1.3, figure 19)

3.2.2 Product Generation

The RD-6 document gives a complete overview of the TerraSAR-X calibration procedures, especially giving information about the pre-flight calibration. Based on a mathematical antenna model, methods and results of the pre-flight validation are given in section V. A Good grade has been given for Sensor Calibration & Characterisation – Pre-Flight, as the pre-flight calibration methods and results are rigorously described, and as no reference have been found concerning the impact of uncertainties on the final product.

Sensor Calibration & Characterisation – Pre-Flight	
Summary	<i>Sections III, IV and V of the reference document provide information about the antenna model used to calibrate the TerraSAR-X instrument before launch, as well as the methods and results of the pre-launch validation. The pre-launch validation results successfully fulfil the requirements of the TerraSAR-X instrument.</i>
References	<i>See RD-6 under sections III, IV and V.</i>

The 5 tasks described in the reference document cover the major aspects of the post-launch calibration. As a consequence, the Good grade has been given for Sensor Calibration & Characterisation – Post launch.

Sensor Calibration & Characterisation – Post-Launch	
Summary	<i>Post-Launch calibration has been divided into 5 tasks: Geometric Calibration, Antenna Pointing Determination, Antenna Model Verification, Relative Radiometric Calibration, Absolute Radiometric Calibration. These 5 tasks are described in the reference document below.</i>
References	<i>See RD-7</i>

The reference document gives an overview of the generation of the TanDEM-X DEM, which includes the height retrieval method for this DEM. As the height retrieval methods are richly described and as the accuracy of the generated DEM is evaluated (using ICESat-1 data), an Excellent grade has been given to the Retrieval Algorithm Method.

Retrieval Algorithm Method	
Summary	<i>Sections 2.3 and 2.6 of the reference document describes the algorithms used to retrieve heights from multiple TerraSAR-X and TanDEM-X acquisitions.</i>
References	<i>See RD-14 under section 2.3: Processing single-pass interferometric data and 2.6: Global DEM generation process: from single scenes to DEM mosaic.</i>

The retrieval algorithm involves global DEMs and ICESat-1 reference data. ICESat-1 data is accurate and available at global scale. However, the mentioned DEMs are not fully representative of the TanDEM-X DEM, both in terms of geographical extent (SRTM C-band DEM), and resolution (GLOBE DEM). As a consequence, the Intermediate grade has been given for Retrieval Algorithm Tuning.

Retrieval Algorithm Tuning	
Summary	<i>Section 2.6 of the reference document describes the parameters used in order to enhance the quality of TanDEM-X acquisitions, also covering external data sources used in the tuning process.</i>
References	<i>See RD-14 under section 2.6: Global DEM generation process: from single scenes to DEM mosaic.</i>

The Copernicus DEM instances are generated from the WorldDEM™ / WorldDEM Core, which are generated from the TanDEM-X DEM. As a consequence, the additional processing steps referenced in the following tables can be relative to the WorldDEM Core, the WorldDEM™ and the Copernicus DEMs. Hereafter, the additional processing steps are described respecting the

order of the processing chain when available (see Figure 3). As there are numerous additional processing steps which are fully documented, providing a rich set of quality layers, the Excellent grade has been given to Additional Processing.

Additional Processing	
<i>Additional Processing 1 – Geoid transformation</i>	
Description	<i>The TanDEM-X DEM ellipsoidal heights, relative to the WGS84-G1150 ellipsoid, are converted to geoid heights, relative to the EGM2008 geoid. This processing step generates the WorldDEM Core, which is the basis of the WorldDEM™ generation.</i>
Reference	<i>See RD-13, under section 3.1.</i>
<i>Additional Processing 2 – Terrain editing</i>	
Description	<i>Terrain editing is applied to the WorldDEM Core, and consists of editing the following features: spikes / wells, voids, noise and negative elevations nearby ocean shorelines. Further explanations concerning the conditions of edition are given in the reference document.</i>
Reference	<i>See RD-13 under section 4.2.1</i>
<i>Additional Processing 3 – Hydrology editing</i>	
Description	<i>Hydrology editing is applied to the WorldDEM Core, and consists of classifying water body pixels into oceans, lakes and rivers, and to edit the elevation of each water body pixel according to its classification. Further explanations concerning the conditions of edition are given in the reference document.</i>
Reference	<i>See RD-13, under section 4.2.2</i>
<i>Additional Processing 4 – Airport editing</i>	
Description	<i>Airport editing is applied to the WorldDEM Core, and consists of modifying bad height values acquired over airports. Further explanations concerning the conditions of edition are given in the reference document.</i>
Reference	<i>See RD-13, under section 4.2.3</i>
<i>Additional Processing 5 – Quality layers</i>	
Description	<i>The following quality layers are generated from the previous processing steps:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Filling Mask (FLM): indicating the sources of elevations used to fill data voids, - Editing Mask (EDM): indicating if a pixel has been edited, and which editing has been applied, - Water Body Mask (WBM): indicating the classification of a water body pixel <i>Further explanations concerning the generation of these quality layers are given in the reference document.</i>
Reference	<i>See RD-13, under section 4.2.3</i>
<i>Additional Processing 6 – Resampling and reformatting</i>	
Description	<i>The WorldDEM™ is resampled and reformatted to generate the three Copernicus DEM instances (EEA-10, GLO-30, GLO-90).</i>
Reference	<i>See RD-13, under section 4.2.3</i>

3.2.3 Ancillary Information

As product flags are available at pixel level and as their gradation is well documented, an Excellent grade has been given for Product Flags.

Product Flags	
Product Flag Documentation	<i>See 1.1.3 under section 1.2.5: Quality Layers</i>
Comprehensiveness of Flags	<i>Excellent</i>

As both an accuracy layer and a source data layer are available, an Excellent grade has been given for Ancillary Data.

Ancillary Data	
Ancillary Data Documentation	<i>See 1.1.3 under section 1.2.5: Quality Layers, subsections 1.2.5.5 and 1.2.5.6)</i>
Comprehensiveness of Data	<i>Excellent</i>
Uncertainty Quantified	<i>Yes (section 2 and 1.2.5.5)</i>

3.2.4 Uncertainty Characterisation

The Copernicus DEM instances are compared to ICESat-1 reference data. As this assessment seems to follow a limited part of the Type A uncertainty classification method (as described in the Guide to the Expression of Uncertainty in Measurement, see RD-4 under section 4.2), an Intermediate grade has been given for Uncertainty Characterisation Method.

Uncertainty Characterisation Method	
Summary	<i>The methods used to characterize the uncertainty of the Copernicus DEMs are details in section 2 of the reference document (Data and Methodology)</i>
Reference	<i>See RD-15 under section 2: Data and Methodology</i>

As a short summary of each error source is available, the Good grade has been given for Uncertainty Sources Included.

Uncertainty Sources Included	
Summary	<i>The section 2.4 of the reference document covers the different error sources affecting the quality of SAR acquisitions (in this case, SAR-X acquisitions).</i>
Reference	<i>see RD-14 under section 2.4: DEM Error Sources</i>

As a height error mask is available at pixel level, but no error-covariance is given, the Good grade has been given for Uncertainty Values Provided.

Uncertainty Values Provided	
Summary	<i>A height error mask is provided. Figure 5 and figure 8 of the reference document respectively show height error maps over the European Economic Area and worldwide.</i>
Reference	<i>See RD-15, figure 5 and figure 8</i>
Analysis Ready Data?	<i>Yes</i>

As a circular error is only given for the whole product, the Basic grade have been given for Geolocation Uncertainty.

Geolocation Uncertainty	
Summary	<i>The section 2.3 of the reference document gives the absolute horizontal accuracy of every Copernicus DEM instance, stated as a circular error of less than 6 metres (90% confidence level).</i>
Reference	<i>See 1.1.3 under section 2.3: Absolute Horizontal Accuracy</i>

3.2.5 Validation

This section presents the validation report of the Copernicus DEMs prepared by Airbus (Validation Activity #1), as well as the validation activities performed in this document (Validation Activities #2, #3 and #4). The grades given in this section only refer to the Validation Activity #1, as it is the validation report of reference for the Copernicus DEM instances.

The Copernicus DEM instances are assessed using ICESat-1 data, which is reliable and available at global scale. However, the assessment concerns tiles with at least 200 valid ICESat-1 elevations, which excludes a significant number of tiles (see *RD-15*, figures 5 and 8). As a consequence; an Intermediate grade has been given to the Reference Data Representativeness.

As the reference ICESat-1 data used only comes with a global estimation of the uncertainty, an Intermediate grade has been given for Reference Data Quality.

Vertical accuracies of the Copernicus DEM instances are given in the validation report, but this document does not include any validation activity performed on the reference ICESat-1 data. As a consequence, an Intermediate grade has been given for Validation Method.

As stated in the validation report, “The mission goal of TerraSAR-X and TanDEM-X was the generation of a global DEM with an accuracy better than 10m”. The validation results show that only a small number of Copernicus DEM tiles do not reach this accuracy. Even if the results are good, as the validation is not independently assessed, the Intermediate grade has been given for Validation Results.

Validation Activity #1 (Airbus)	
Independently Assessed?	<i>No</i>
<i>Reference Data Representativeness</i>	
Summary	<i>The ICESat-1 GLAS reference dataset used in this validation report is available at a global scale.</i>
Reference	<i>see RD-15 under section 2.2: ICESat-1 GLAS Reference Data</i>
<i>Reference Data Quality & Suitability</i>	
Summary	<i>Reference data has been filtered in order to remove outliers (see section 2.3); the vertical accuracy of the reference data is more than three times higher than the vertical accuracy of each Copernicus DEM instance (see section 2.5.1)</i>
Reference	<i>See RD-15 under sections 2.3 and 2.5.1</i>
<i>Validation Method</i>	
Summary	<i>The reference data elevations are converted from the Topex/Poseidon ellipsoid to the EGM2008 geoid. Reference data is filtered by taking into account the slope of the terrain and waveform of the returning signal. Erroneous data taken over water surfaces is filtered using the Copernicus</i>

	<i>DEM Water Body Mask. Acquisitions in mountainous terrain are also filtered (see section 2.3).</i>
Reference	<i>See RD-15 under sections 2.3 to 2.5.2</i>
Validation Results	
Summary	<i>Vertical accuracy is assessed relative to the WorldDEM™ product, which is the source DEM used to generate all Copernicus DEM instances. WorldDEM™ has been assessed both on the European Economic Area and globally. A vertical accuracy of 2.03 metres has been assessed for the European Economic Area (90% linear error). Globally, a vertical accuracy of 2.17m has been assessed.</i>
Reference	<i>see RD-15 under section 3: Results</i>

Validation Activity #2 (VisioTerra)	
Independently Assessed?	Yes
Reference Data Representativeness	
Summary	<i>The quality assessment of the three Copernicus DEM instances is assessed using all the terrain acquisitions of the GLAS instrument, which are available at global scale (GLAH14 product). The number of compared heights may vary from one DEM study to another, as bad quality data is filtered both on the DEM products and ICESat-1 products.</i>
Reference	<i>see section 4.2 of this document</i>
Reference Data Quality & Suitability	
Summary	<i>GLAS acquisitions are analysed on the same orbit on multiple periods to ensure the consistency of the retrieved heights. A particularly flat area has been chosen for this assessment: The Salt Lake Salar de Uyuni in Bolivia. The results of this study highlight the accuracy and constancy of GLAS acquisitions.</i>
Reference	<i>see section 4.2.3 of this document</i>
Validation Method	
Summary	<i>Copernicus DEMs heights are compared to ICESat-1 acquisitions to assess their accuracy. The ICESat-1 data is filtered using the provided quality flags. At each ICESat-1 footprint location, an interpolated height is processed from each Copernicus DEM. Both ICESat-1 and Copernicus DEMs heights are converted from their original vertical reference system to the WGS84 ellipsoid, from which every ICESat-1 height is subtracted to its corresponding Copernicus DEM instance interpolated height.</i>
Reference	<i>see section 4.2.4.2 of this document</i>
Validation Results	
Summary	<i>The results show an average difference between the height value in ICESat-1 and Copernicus DEM GLO-30 of 0.025 metres with a RMSE of 0.457 metres. Other results are available in the referenced sections below.</i>
Reference	<i>see sections 4.2.4.3, 4.2.5.3 and 4.2.6.3 of this document</i>

Validation Activity #3 (VisioTerra)	
Independently Assessed?	Yes
<i>Reference Data Representativeness</i>	
Summary	<i>The quality assessment of the three Copernicus DEM instances is assessed using all the terrain and canopy acquisitions of the ATLAS instrument (ATL08 product, 9 orbit cycles of acquisition). The number of compared heights may vary from one DEM study to another, as bad quality data is filtered both on the DEM products and ICESat-2 products. Results of this study are compared to results obtained taking ICESat-1 / GLAH14 data as a vertical reference (Validation Activity #2).</i>
Reference	<i>see section 4.3 of this document</i>
<i>Reference Data Quality & Suitability</i>	
Summary	<i>ATLAS acquisitions are analysed on the same orbit on multiple periods to ensure the consistency of the retrieved heights. A particularly flat area has been chosen for this assessment: The Salt Lake Salar de Uyuni in Bolivia. The results of this study highlight the accuracy and constancy of ATLAS acquisitions.</i>
Reference	<i>see section 4.3.3 of this document</i>
<i>Validation Method</i>	
Summary	<i>Copernicus DEMs heights are compared to ICESat-2 / ATL08 terrain and canopy height estimations to assess their accuracy. The ICESat-2 data is filtered using the provided quality flags. At each ICESat-2 estimated terrain and canopy height's location, an interpolated height is processed from each Copernicus DEM. Copernicus DEMs heights are converted from their original vertical reference system to the WGS84 ellipsoid, from which every ICESat-2 height (terrain only and terrain with canopy) is subtracted to its corresponding Copernicus DEM instance interpolated height.</i>
Reference	<i>see section 4.3.4.1 of this document</i>
<i>Validation Results</i>	
Summary	<i>The results show a mean difference between the height values of the Copernicus DEM EEA-10 and ICESat-2 of 0.822 metres with a standard deviation of 1.944 metres for terrain heights only, and a mean difference of -5.477 metres with a standard deviation of 4.838 metres considering canopy heights (LE95). These results show that the Copernicus DEM EEA-10 heights are closer to the terrain than to the canopy. Considering terrain heights only, the statistics show that the Copernicus DEM EEA-10 is really accurate. These statements are also true for the GLO-30 and GLO-90 instances. Other results are available in the referenced sections below.</i>
Reference	<i>see sections 4.3.4.3, 4.3.5.3 and 4.3.6.3 of this document</i>

Validation Activity #4 (VisioTerra)	
Independently Assessed?	Yes
<i>Reference Data Representativeness</i>	
Summary	<i>The quality assessment of the three Copernicus DEM instances is assessed using one month of GEDI acquisitions (GEDI02_A product). The number of compared heights may vary from one DEM study to another, as bad quality data is filtered both on the DEM products and GEDI products. Results of this</i>

	<i>study are compared to results obtained taking ICESat-1 / GLAH14 and ICESat-2 / ATLO8 data as vertical references (Validation Activity #2 and #3).</i>
Reference	<i>see section 4.4 of this document</i>
<i>Reference Data Quality & Suitability</i>	
Summary	<i>GEDI02_A heights are compared to ICESat-1 and ICESat-2 heights on a few samples over a particularly flat area: the Salar de Uyuni in Bolivia. This study is just an example of comparison between multiple LiDARs and is not representative of the overall GEDI02_A product quality.</i>
Reference	<i>see section 4.4.3.3 of this document</i>
<i>Validation Method</i>	
Summary	<i>Copernicus DEMs heights are compared to GEDI lowest mode (ground) and highest return (top of canopy) heights to assess their accuracy. The GEDI data is filtered using the provided quality flags. At each GEDI lowest mode and highest return location, an interpolated height is processed from each Copernicus DEM. Copernicus DEMs heights are converted from their original vertical reference system to the WGS84 ellipsoid, from which every GEDI height (lowest mode and highest return) is subtracted to its corresponding Copernicus DEM instance interpolated height.</i>
Reference	<i>see section 4.4.4.1 of this document</i>
<i>Validation Results</i>	
Summary	<i>The results show a mean difference between the height values of the Copernicus DEM EEA-10 and GEDI of 2.363 metres with a standard deviation of 5.277 metres for lowest mode, and a mean difference of -6.916 metres with a standard deviation of 3.968 metres considering highest return (LE95). These results show that the Copernicus DEM EEA-10 heights are closer to GEDI lowest mode (terrain) than to GEDI highest return (top of canopy). Other results are available in the referenced sections below.</i>
Reference	<i>see sections 4.4.4.3, 4.4.5.3 and 4.4.6.3 of this document</i>

4. DETAILED ASSESSMENT

VisioTerra promotes the on-the-fly processing of data required by the user. As illustrated here joined, this “ecological process” only processes part of the products and on the required scale.

This processing strategy makes it possible to interactively configure the functions and to tune the rendering parameters according to the range of values and/or the features of the landscape.

These processing parameters, the product(s) to which they apply as well as the viewing geometry can be kept in a hyperlook, a rich URL that the user can share and that other users will replay by “navigating” interactively in the data. This process makes it possible to design galleries of use cases that can be kept. See for example, the hyperlooks documents RD-39 and RD-40.

These new possibilities require the maintenance of a server called “Data Processing Relay (DPR)” capable here of -viewing DEMs with different restitution styles (for example different shading directions), -calculating on-the-fly derived measurements (for example slope, azimuth, curvatures), or even -orthorectifying on-the-fly products previously prepared, i.e. downloaded from ESA servers (or other data providers) and organized in quadtrees without modifying their geometry neither their radiometry.

4.1 DEMs intercomparison – Qualitative assessment

The previous study (RD-37) showed that the “ALOS World 3D” DEM is clearly superior to the other two DEMs SRTM and ASTER-GDEM.

These good results are certainly due to the tri-stereo (forward, nadir and backward) acquisition technique of the PRISM instrument on board the “DAICHI” satellite (ALOS), more stringent quality assurance procedures performed by the Japanese Space Agency (JAXA) and the experience gained through the production of ASTER GDEM.

For more information about ALOS World 3D, please refer to <https://www.aw3d.jp/en/technology/>.

In this section, we qualitatively assess the differences between ALOS World 3D and Copernicus DEM GLO-30 (considered to be the reference). These two DEMs are at the same 1" arc ground sampling distance, i.e. 30 meters at the equator. All the results of this section can be found in the layer stack pointed to by the hyperlook

<https://visioterra.org/VtWeb/hyperlook/1de9b1899f7f48cb8df59a45db05ea15>

4.1.1 Global views

Before performing the subtraction between the two DEMs, the elevations of "ALOS World 3D" initially above the gravity model EGM96 are transformed into elevations above the WGS-84 ellipsoid. In the same way we transform the elevations of "Copernicus DEM GLO-30" initially above the gravimetric model EGM2008 in elevations above the ellipsoid WGS-84.

Figure 4 - Global views of the difference between "ALOS World 3D" and "Copernicus DEM GLO-30".

In these 2D (geographic coordinate reference system) and 3D (vertical perspective) views, the colour chart indicates:

- **blue** that the elevations of Copernicus DEM GLO-30 are the highest,
- **white** that the elevations of ALOS World 3D and Copernicus GLO-30 are approximately equal,
- **red** that the elevations of ALOS World 3D are the highest.

More important differences will be noted at high latitudes. During the previous study (RD-37), we had already noted the weakest performances of "ALOS World 3D" outside the latitude interval $[-60^\circ; +60^\circ]$. We note in particular higher values of "ALOS World 3D" above the Antarctic, while segments of acquisitions of ALOS seem to render lower elevations in Siberia. Without being able to attribute paternity to one of the two DEMs, one observes a long segment showing differences by higher values interlaced with differences by lower values.

4.1.2 Lake Garda (Italy)

In this example, we observe an anomaly of "ALOS World 3D" on the water surface of Lake Garda. The animation <https://visioterra.org/VtWeb/hyperlook/cab3faa2c47742fba0faa271196e46e1> highlights this flaw.

ALOS World 3D

Copernicus DEM GLO-30

Copernicus DEM GLO-30 - ALOS

Figure 5 - Anomaly of ALOS World 3D above Lake Garda (Italy).

4.2 Elevation assessment from ICESat-1 / GLAS LiDAR – Quantitative assessment

This section 4.2 presents the quantitative evaluation of the vertical accuracy of Copernicus DEM EEA-10, Copernicus DEM GLO-30 and Copernicus DEM GLO-90 data using reference data from the ICESat-1 / GLAS LiDAR.

Unlike the previous section 4.1, the following evaluation is quantitative, consisting of the comparison between each valid elevation given in ICESat-1 products to its homologous point to be interpolated from the DEM to be verified.

4.2.1 History of ICESat-1

ICESat-1 was a mission led by the NASA Goddard Space Flight Center (GSFC). The purpose of this mission was to measure ice sheet mass balance, cloud and aerosol heights, as well as land topography and vegetation characteristics. The Geoscience Laser Altimeter System, which is a LiDAR, was developed to satisfy the needs of this mission. ICESat-1 was launched on the 13th of January 2003 and decommissioned on the 14th of August 2010, due to a laser failure that occurred on the 11th of October 2009. From February 2003 to October 2009, the GLAS instrument fired nearly 2 billion laser pulses all over the world.

Figure 6 - ICESat-1 3D representation.
(<https://www.csr.utexas.edu/glas/>)

4.2.2 Technical specifications

Onboard ICESat-1, the Geoscience Laser Altimeter System (**GLAS**) sends laser pulses at the frequency of **40 Hz**, which approximates to an acquisition every 170 metres along track. The GLAS instrument emits laser pulses at both 532 nm and 1064 nm of wavelength.

The following figure illustrates the functioning of the GLAS instrument:

Figure 7 - GLAS instrument characteristics.
(<https://earth.esa.int/workshops/spaceandthearctic09/Zwally.pdf>)

The following table summarizes the characteristics of the ICESat-1 mission and the GLAS instrument:

Technical specification	Value
Instrument name	Geoscience Laser Altimeter System (GLAS)
First acquisition date	02.20.2003
Last acquisition date	11.10.2009
Acquisition frequency	40 Hz
Ground sampling distance	~170 m
Central wavelength	532 nm (green) / 1064 nm (near infrared)
Number of beams	1
Repeat cycle	Phase 1 – 8 days – [20/02/2003; 04/10/2003] Phase 2 – 91 days – [04/10/2003; 11/10/2009]
Footprint diameter	~70 m

Table 4 – GLAS instrument technical specifications

4.2.3 Assessment of ICESat-1 / GLAS measurements reliability

4.2.3.1 GLAH14 Product

4.2.3.1.1 Product organisation

Land altimetry data is available in the GLAH14 product. Each product is delivered in the HDF5 format and contains variables concerning location, elevation and quality of the data (in both 1 Hz and 40 Hz frequencies). The HDF5 format is a hierarchical format, organised in groups of variables. The following figure illustrates the root group of a GLAH14 product.

Figure 8 - Root of a GLAH14 product.

4.2.3.1.2 Data filtering

Each GLAH14 product used is filtered using these quality flags:

- `elev_use_flg` indicating whether the elevations on the record should be used (0 = true, 1 = false)
- `sat_corr_flg` indicating if a saturation correction needs to be applied (between 0 and 4, values meaning is detailed below)
- `elv_cloud_flg` indicating probable cloud contamination (0 = false, 1 = true)

The following table summarizes the meaning of each `sat_corr_flg` value (<https://nsidc.org/icesat/saturation-correction>):

Value	Meaning
0	Not saturated or no signal (no correction needed)
1	Inconsequential
2	Applicable
3	Not computable
4	Not applicable

Table 5 - Values of the `sat_corr_flg` in the GLAH14 product.

Elevations having a `sat_corr_flg` value over 2 are excluded, as they can't be corrected. Saturation correction is added to the elevation values where `sat_corr_flg` equals 1 or 2. Potentially cloud contaminated elevations are removed from all the measures (where `elv_cloud_flg` equals 1).

The variable `d_satElevCorr` contains the saturation correction applied to elevations. Another correction, `d_ElevBiasCorr`, is applied to the data: this correction was determined by the GSFC on post flight analysis.

4.2.3.2 Sampling of ICESat-1 / GLAS data

This section defines the equations used in the sampling of ICESat-1 data. The following equation is used to process linear interpolation:

$$h_i = h_1 + (h_2 - h_1) * \frac{(l_1 - L_i)}{(l_2 - l_1)} \quad (\text{eq. 1})$$

Where:

- L_i is the latitude of the height to be interpolated
- h_i is the interpolated height at L_i
- l_1 is the highest latitude $<L_i$ from the reference acquisition points
- l_2 is the lowest latitude $>L_i$ from the reference acquisition points
- h_1 is the height of the point of latitude l_1
- h_2 is the height of the point of latitude l_2

4.2.3.3 Collocated measurements on the same orbit

4.2.3.3.1 Scope

Multiple measurements are analysed on the same orbit to assess ICESat-1's instrument reliability. A particularly flat area is chosen for this assessment: The Salt Lake Salar de Uyuni in Bolivia (see attached figure).

4.2.3.3.2 Method

Definitions

The following terminology is used in this study:

- **Measurement:** height measured by ICESat-1/GLAS at a given geolocation (longitude, latitude). The geolocation of a measurement corresponds to the geolocation of the GLAS instrument's laser footprint centre during acquisition,
- **Ground track:** segment of orbit identified by an id, which remains identical from one revolution to another,
- **Profile:** set of measurements acquired contiguously along-track.

Reliability assessment

The goal of this study is to ensure ICESat-1/GLAS heights acquired over multiple revolutions on a common ground track do not largely differ. This study aims to evaluate the **constancy** of ICESat-1/GLAS height acquisitions over multiple revolutions.

For this study, measurements are extracted among the 642 products of the ICESat-1 GLAH14 dataset. Only valid measurements acquired over the study area are considered (see 4.2.3.1

for GLAH14 measurement filtering method). The following illustration shows the measurements considered for this study:

Figure 9 - Ground tracks considered for the ICESat-1 reliability study.

The following table gives an exhaustive list of GLAH14 products used in this study:

Ground track	Product identifier
351	GLAH14_634_2107_002_0351_0_01_0001.H5
	GLAH14_634_2109_002_0351_0_01_0001.H5
	GLAH14_634_2115_002_0351_0_01_0001.H5
	GLAH14_634_2113_002_0351_0_01_0001.H5
	GLAH14_634_2121_002_0351_0_01_0001.H5
	GLAH14_634_2111_003_0351_0_01_0001.H5
85	GLAH14_634_2123_002_0085_0_01_0001.H5
	GLAH14_634_2125_002_0085_0_01_0001.H5
	GLAH14_634_2107_003_0085_0_01_0001.H5

Ground track	Product identifier
	GLAH14_634_2113_002_0085_0_01_0001.H5
	GLAH14_634_2119_002_0085_0_01_0001.H5
	GLAH14_634_2103_002_0085_0_01_0001.H5
	GLAH14_634_2111_003_0085_0_01_0001.H5
	GLAH14_634_2121_002_0085_0_01_0001.H5
	GLAH14_634_2107_002_0085_0_01_0001.H5
	GLAH14_634_2115_002_0085_0_01_0001.H5
	GLAH14_634_2109_002_0085_0_01_0001.H5
	GLAH14_634_2115_003_0085_0_01_0001.H5

Table 6 – ICESat-1 GLAH14 ground tracks and products studied.

As shown in Figure 9, from one revolution to another, horizontal shifts may occur between the acquired profiles. These shifts may lead to important differences in height between measurements acquired over multiple revolutions on the same ground track. The choice of a particularly flat area for this study minimizes these height differences, but the horizontal shift prevents from comparing heights of multiple profiles over a same ground track directly: heights need to be interpolated at a fixed step on each profile.

ICESat-1/GLAS acquires measurements at 40Hz, which approximates to a ground sampling distance of 170 metres along-track near equator. Starting from the top of the study area, heights are interpolated linearly every 170 metres (fixed step in latitude) for each profile (see 4.2.3.2 for the equation of the linear interpolation). An interpolated height is only valid if the following conditions are true:

- Considering measurements with latitudes lower than the interpolated height latitude, the measurement with the highest latitude should be located at less than 170 metres of the interpolated height in latitude,
- Considering measurements with latitudes higher than the interpolated height latitude, the measurement with the lowest latitude should be located at less than 170 metres of the interpolated height in latitude,
- Along-track measurements from which the height is interpolated should be contained in the study area.

Given interpolated heights at a fixed step in latitude, standard deviation of the computed heights is calculated at each step, considering every profile of a ground track. Statistics are calculated based on these standard deviation calculations.

4.2.3.3.3 Results

The following figures show, for the two studied ground tracks, the evolution of the interpolated heights of each profile according to the latitude:

Figure 10– ICESat-1 reliability study, interpolated heights over ground track 85.

Figure 11 – ICESat-1 reliability study, interpolated heights over ground track 351.

Ground track 85 interpolated heights approximately range from 3697,5 metres to 3698,25 metres, whereas ground track 315 interpolated heights approximately range from 3697,55 metres to 3698,25 metres among all profiles.

The following table gives the statistics calculated for this study. These statistics are calculated at every latitude step, regarding the standard deviation of the interpolated heights of every profile among a ground track:

Per latitude step statistics					
Ground track	Count	Min	Max	Arithmetic Mean	Standard Deviation
85	204	0.029 m	0.112 m	0.064 m	0.016 m
351	204	0.013 m	0.115 m	0.049 m	0.017 m

Table 7 – Statistics regarding standard deviation of interpolated heights at each latitude.

The statistics show that the constancy of ICESat-1/GLAS measurements is really good, considering a maximal arithmetic mean of 0,064 metres and standard deviation of 0,017 metres.

4.2.3.4 Geographical distribution of ICESat-1 products

The assessments performed in this document are based on the **642 products** of ICESat-1 mission. Most of the products contain one day acquisition over 14 revolutions. These products are distributed all over the world as shown in the following figures.

Figure 12 - Distribution of the 642 ICESat-1 products.

4.2.4 Assessment of Copernicus DEM EEA-10 from ICESat-1 / GLAS data

This section 4.2.4 presents the quantitative evaluation of the vertical accuracy of Copernicus DEM EEA-10 using reference data from the ICESat-1 / GLAS LiDAR. The method and the notations of the next subsection 4.2.4.2 are detailed here after. The same methods will apply for the evaluation of Copernicus DEM GLO-30 (section 4.2.5) and Copernicus DEM GLO-90 (section 4.2.6) and will not be repeated.

4.2.4.1 Spatial extent

As opposed to the global spatial extent of Copernicus DEM GLO-30 and Copernicus DEM GLO-90, Copernicus DEM EEA-10 is spatially restricted to the European Economic Area. The following figure ([hyperlook https://visioterra.org/VtWeb/hyperlook/be0edefce6cd410686fe647deeed2529](https://visioterra.org/VtWeb/hyperlook/be0edefce6cd410686fe647deeed2529)) shows the coverage map of Copernicus DEM EEA-10:

Figure 13 - Copernicus DEM EEA-10 coverage map.

4.2.4.2 Method and notations

Scope of the numerical analysis is to process height error statistics concerning Copernicus DEM EEA-10, given ICESat-1 GLAH14 products as a vertical reference.

4.2.4.2.1 Conversion from TOPEX / Poseidon to WGS84

ICESat-1 elevations are relative to the TOPEX/Poseidon ellipsoid and shall be converted to the WGS84 ellipsoid using the following formula (see <https://www.mdpi.com/2072-4292/10/2/297/htm>):

$$\Delta h = \frac{a'(1 - e'^2)}{\sqrt{1 - e'^2 \sin^2 \phi}} - \frac{a(1 - e^2)}{\sqrt{1 - e^2 \sin^2 \phi}} \quad (\text{eq. 2})$$

Where:

- a is the semi-major axis of the WGS84 ellipsoid,
- e is the eccentricity of the WGS84 ellipsoid,
- a' is the semi-major axis of the TOPEX/Poseidon ellipsoid,
- e' is the eccentricity of the TOPEX/Poseidon ellipsoid,
- ϕ is the latitude of the elevation (relative to the TOPEX/Poseidon ellipsoid),

Δh is the difference in elevation between the TOPEX/Poseidon and WGS84 ellipsoids.

This formula gives the difference in elevation between the WGS84 and TOPEX/Poseidon ellipsoids. This difference has to be subtracted from the TOPEX/Poseidon referenced elevations, as the TOPEX/Poseidon ellipsoid is smaller than WGS84. The following table (found at <https://nsidc.org/data/icesat/faq.html#alt7>) summarizes the differences between the WGS84 and TOPEX/Poseidon ellipsoids:

	TOPEX/Poseidon	WGS84
• Equatorial radius (a)	• 6 378 136.3 metres	• 6 378 137.0 metres
• Polar radius (b)	• 6 356 751.600 563 metres	• 6 356 752.314 245 metres
• Reciprocal flattening (1/f)	• 298.25700000	• 298.25722356
• Eccentricity (e)	• 0.081819221456	• 0.081819190843

Table 8 - Difference between TOPEX/Poseidon and WGS84 ellipsoids.

The differences in latitudes between these two ellipsoids are small (up to +/-1.5 cm), as illustrated by the following graph (see data in <ftp://sidacs.colorado.edu/pub/DATASETS/icesat/tools/idl/ellipsoid/>):

Figure 14 - Latitude difference between WGS84 and TOPEX/Poseidon ellipsoids (in centimetres).

Latitudes can be considered as equal from TOPEX/Poseidon to WGS84, as the maximum difference in latitude between the two ellipsoids is far below the horizontal accuracy of ICESat-1. On average, horizontal accuracy ranges from 0.0 to 4.63 metres, with a minimal standard deviation of 2.22 metres.

4.2.4.2.2 From ICESat-1 longitude and latitude to the Copernicus DEM EEA-10 tile

The longitude and latitude ranges of each product are the following:

- ICESat-1: longitude $\in [0^\circ, 360^\circ]$, latitude $\in [-90^\circ, +90^\circ]$
- Copernicus DEM EEA-10: longitude $\in [-180^\circ, 180^\circ]$, latitude $\in [-90^\circ, +90^\circ]$

To match Copernicus DEM EEA-10 with ICESat-1 longitudes, 360° are subtracted from all ICESat-1 longitudes values greater than 180° .

To compare ICESat-1 to Copernicus DEM EEA-10 elevations, a corresponding Copernicus DEM EEA-10 tile is found for each ICESat-1 footprint, and the exact cell of the DEM containing it. The Copernicus DEM EEA-10 tile name pattern is the following:

Copernicus_DSM_10_<c><l>_00_<C><L>_00_DEM.tif

Where:

- c corresponds to the latitude's cardinal (S for South or N for North)
- l is the latitude in degrees ranging from 00 to 90
- C corresponds to the longitude's cardinal (E for East or W for West)
- L is the longitude in degrees ranging from 000 to 180

Example: For ICESat-1_longitude = -96.051 and ICESat-1_latitude = 42.472, the corresponding Copernicus DEM EEA-10 tile is entitled:

"Copernicus_DSM_10_N42_00_W097_00_DEM.tif"

A Copernicus DEM EEA-10 tile is composed of 3601 rows and a varying number of columns (depending on the latitude). The bottom left value of the file corresponds to the smallest longitude and latitude. The following equation gives the position of the corresponding sample in the file:

$$p = |C - C \times y| \times L + |L \times x| \quad (\text{eq. 3})$$

Where:

- p is the position of the sample
- L is the line size in bytes
- C is the column size
- x corresponds to ICESat-1 longitude's digits
- y corresponds to ICESat-1 latitude's digits

Interpolating ICESat-1 footprints on the Copernicus DEM EEA-10 grid is necessary, as the location of ICESat-1 acquisitions are punctual, in opposite to regularly gridded elevation sources, such as DEMs. Bilinear interpolation is used on the Copernicus DEM EEA-10 grid to obtain elevations at each ICESat-1 footprint location.

4.2.4.2.3 From EGM2008 to WGS84

The EGM2008 geoid is the vertical reference system of Copernicus DEM EEA-10, longitudes and latitudes referring to the WGS84 ellipsoid. As a result, only elevations need to be converted from EGM2008 to the WGS84 ellipsoid, which is done considering EGM2008's geoid undulations. EGM2008 is distributed by the [NGA/NASA](#) as a grid, with respect to the WGS84 ellipsoid (see RD-36). At each Copernicus DEM EEA-10/ICESat-1 height comparison location, bilinear interpolation is used on the EGM96 undulation grid to retrieve heights relative to the WGS84 ellipsoid.

In this case, EGM2008 undulation values are added to the interpolated Copernicus DEM EEA-10 heights, retrieving Copernicus DEM EEA-10 heights relative to WGS84.

Figure here after shows the EGM2008 undulations over the WGS84 ellipsoid.

Figure 15 - EGM2008 map with reference to WGS84.

4.2.4.2.4 Copernicus DEMs pixel filtering

For this study, only Copernicus DEM pixels corresponding to the following filtering conditions have been considered.

Layer	Filtering condition
WBM	= 0 (land)
EDM	= 1 (not edited)
FLM	= 2 (not filled)

Table 9 – Filtering of the Copernicus DEMs

The WBM layer filtering allows for further filtering of outliers (clouds acquisitions over oceans misunderstood as terrain data). The EDM and FLM filtering is used to select heights computed from TanDEM-X data.

4.2.4.2.5 Computing the height difference

Height difference between Copernicus DEM EEA-10 and ICESat-1 is finally calculated:

$$\Delta h = h_{DEM} - h_{ICESat-1} \quad (\text{eq. 4})$$

Where:

- Δh is the height difference between Copernicus DEM EEA-10 and ICESat-1,
- $h_{ICESat-1}$ is the ICESat-1 height (with respect to the WGS84 ellipsoid),
- h_{DEM} is the Copernicus DEM EEA-10 height (with respect to the WGS84 ellipsoid).

4.2.4.2.6 Overall algorithm

The following diagram summarizes all the steps of the ICESat-1/Copernicus DEM EEA-10 height comparison:

Figure 16 - Summary of the Copernicus DEM EEA-10 assessment method.

4.2.4.3 Results

Here are the results of this study. All the statistics refer to the differences between Copernicus DEM EEA-10 and ICESat-1 heights (Copernicus DEM EEA-10 – ICESat-1):

	Raw	LE95	LE90
Number of ICESat-1 products	642		
Number of compared heights	1 898 474	1 803 551	1 708 627
Min	-2641.975 m	-5.924 m	-3.422 m
Max	119.259 m	5.924 m	3.422 m
Mean (metres)	0.539 m	0.270 m	0.111 m
RMSE (metres)	9.535 m	1.415 m	0.983 m
Standard deviation (metres)	9.520 m	1.389 m	0.976 m
Median (metres)	0.03 m	0.00 m	-0.01 m
Skewness	1.436	1.091	0.679
Kurtosis	146.872	3.797	1.894

Table 10 - Statistics of the (Copernicus DEM EEA-10 – ICESat-1) comparison.

Figure 17 - Error histogram of the (Copernicus DEM EEA-10 – ICESat-1) comparison.

Arithmetic mean (0.270 m, 95% linear error) gives the systematic bias between Copernicus DEM EEA-10 and ICESat-1 heights. Root Mean Square Error or RMSE (1.415 m, 95% linear error) is the quadratic mean of the errors including the bias. Standard deviation (1.389 m, 95% linear error) gives the distribution of the errors around the mean out of the bias. The median error m is the one for which 50% of the pixels have an error less than m and 50% have an error greater than m.

This histogram looks like the Normal distribution (Gaussian) with a small positive bias.

4.2.4.4 Typical sources of elevation errors

4.2.4.4.1 ICESat-1 elevation errors

ICESat-1 data is reliable and precise, however, after filtering, a small percentage of outliers remain in the reference data. The main cause of outliers is the presence of clouds during the data acquisition. Most of the clouds are filtered by using product quality flags (see 4.2.3.1) but a small percentage of acquisitions still don't correspond to the terrain height but to the top of clouds height.

Figure 18 - ICESat-1 cloud outliers over France.

In Figure 18, a 3D profile corresponds to multiple ICESat-1 height acquisitions over the same orbit taken over France. Copernicus DEM GLO-30 has been used as a background map to distinguish good and bad ICESat-1 acquisitions: green areas represent relatively low elevations whereas intermediate or high elevations are coloured in yellow/red. In this case, an example of good elevation acquisition is delimited by the blue rectangle: the ICESat-1 acquired heights increase and decrease progressively, following the height colour gradient of the Copernicus DEM GLO-30. An example of bad ICESat-1 acquisition is delimited by the red rectangle: an abrupt change of height is detected by ICESat-1 (multiple kilometres), which is not highlighted by the DEM background map. In this case, the most probable explanation is that these acquisitions correspond to the top of clouds that were not filtered by the cloud mask of the ICESat-1 product concerned.

4.2.4.4.2 Geomorphological and land use / land cover context causing elevation errors

This section aims to provide a better understanding of the sources of elevation errors by observing their repartition all over the geographical extent of Copernicus DEM EEA-10. In the figures of this section, negative height errors are depicted in blue (Copernicus DEM EEA-10 height is lower than the ICESat-1 reference height) whereas positive height errors are depicted in red (Copernicus DEM EEA-10 height is greater than the ICESat-1 reference height). The labelling associated with each elevation error geolocation corresponds to the value of the height error in metres (value of Δh). The following subsections present potential causes of these elevation errors.

Sparse canopy

Assessing a Digital Surface Model (DSM) from LiDAR data can cause high elevation errors in case of sparse canopy. A gridded elevation model such as a DSM cannot highlight drastic height changes, which can punctually be highlighted by LiDAR data.

This type of error is highlighted in the case study of Figure 19. In this case study of Życiński Las near Żytna in Poland, a high elevation error is retrieved (+14.939 m). This height error is certainly due to the sparse canopy of this area, for which the acquired height of ICESat-1 is relative to the ground, whereas the Copernicus DEM EEA-10 height is relative to the canopy.

Figure 19 - EEA-10 - ICESat-1 height differences - Case of Życiński Las near Żytna (Poland).

Deforestation

Deforestation occurring between the ICESat-1 and TanDEM-X missions may cause errors, as these missions had two distinct temporal acquisition intervals (2003 to 2009 for ICESat-1, 2010 to 2015 for TanDEM-X). This type of error is highlighted by the case study of Figure 19, subfigure c, which shows an example of height error linked to deforestation in Forêt de la Matte near Matemale in France.

Figure 20 - EEA-10 - ICESat-1 height differences – Case of Forêt de la Matte near Matemale (France).

The case study of Figure 20 shows a height error geolocated over an area which was deforested. This area was observed on two dates, for which the acquisitions are shown in Figure 21.

Figure 21 - EEA-10 - ICESat-1 height differences – Evolution of the studied deforestation over two acquisition dates.

The first acquisition of Figure 21 (subfigure a) was taken in December 2004 and shows no sign of deforestation. The second acquisition (subfigure b), acquired in April 2009, shows the same study area but deforested. As ICESat-1 height acquisitions range from 2003 to 2009, the deforestation occurring in this area is certainly the cause of this negative elevation error, ICESat-1 heights acquired before the deforestation of this area being relative to the canopy. As a consequence, Copernicus DEM EEA-10 heights relative to the ground may be compared to ICESat-1 heights relative to the canopy.

Deep valleys

Deep valleys related height errors are not the most widespread errors of this study, but they can reach tens of meters. A first case study is depicted in Figure 22, which shows a really high positive error (+48.522 m) in the Alps, near the Breithorn, in Switzerland.

Figure 22 - EEA-10 - ICESat-1 height differences - Case of the Alps near the Breithorn (Switzerland).

A second case study, depicted in Figure 23, shows a similar height error (+43.638 m) in the Alps, near Andalo Valtellino, in Italy.

Figure 23 - EEA-10 - ICESat-1 height differences - Case of the Alps near Andalo Valtellino (Italy).

In subfigure b of Figure 22 and Figure 23, isocurves are set to 50 metres showing steep slopes over the study area.

Excavations

Excavations can lead to important height changes from one acquisition to another. Figure 24 highlights the case of Carrière de Marche-les-Dames, an excavation located near Namèche in Belgium.

Figure 24 - EEA-10 - ICESat-1 height differences - Case of Carrière de Marche-les-Dames near Namèche (Belgium).

In this case study, an important negative error is calculated (-18.206 m), which occurs over Carrière de Marche-les-Dames. To ensure the depicted height error is linked to this excavation, two acquisitions of this area on different dates are compared in Figure 25.

Figure 25 - EEA-10 - ICESat-1 height differences – Evolution of the studied excavation over two acquisition dates.

Figure 25 shows that the excavation of this case study was active from April 2007, date of acquisition of subfigure a, to October 2015, date of acquisition of subfigure b. As the first picture (subfigure a) was acquired on the acquisition period of ICESat-1, and as the second picture (subfigure b) was acquired on the acquisition period of TanDEM-X, the depicted height error is certainly due to the excavation expanding over the years.

Buildings

The construction and the demolition of buildings can cause height errors, as ICESat-1 and TanDEM-X acquired heights over different acquisition periods. Figure 26 highlights a case of industrial building demolition in Grenzach-Wyhlen, in Germany.

Figure 26 - EEA-10 - ICESat-1 height differences - Case of an industrial building in Grenzach-Wyhlen (Germany).

Figure 26 shows a height error over the foundations of a demolished industrial building. To ensure the depicted height error is caused by the demolition of a building, two pictures of the study area acquired on different dates are compared in Figure 27.

Figure 27 - EEA-10 - ICESat-1 height differences – Demolition of an industrial building over two acquisition dates.

The subfigure a of Figure 27 shows the presence of an industrial building over the study area in October 2009, whereas the building is demolished in the second picture dated from October 2015. As a consequence, the height error of this study area is probably due to the demolition of this building, especially considering the acquisition period of ICESat-1 (2003 to 2009) and TanDEM-X (2010 to 2015).

4.2.5 Assessment of Copernicus DEM GLO-30 from ICESat-1 / GLAS data

4.2.5.1 Spatial extent

The following figure (hyperlink <https://visioterra.org/VtWeb/hyperlook/dbe8a529cd2d4844b70f1008fa77b07e>) shows the coverage map of Copernicus DEM GLO-30.

Figure 28 - Copernicus DEM GLO-30 coverage map.

However, Copernicus DEM GLO-30 is only assessed in the $[-60, 60]$ latitude interval in order to compare its results with SRTM-GL1, ASTER GDEM and ALOS World 3D. This limitation has been chosen considering the latitude limitation of SRTM-GL1 and the voids of ALOS World 3D.

4.2.5.2 Method and notations

The methodology used is the same as the one for the assessment of Copernicus DEM EEA-10 from ICESat-1 (see section 4.2.4).

4.2.5.3 Results

Here are the results of this study. All the statistics refer to the differences between ICESat-1 and Copernicus DEM GLO-30 heights (Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – ICESat-1):

	Raw	LE95	LE90
Number of ICESat-1 products	642		
Number of compared heights	62 441 346	59 319 279	56 197 212
Min	-4144.059 m	-2.725 m	-1.415 m
Max	3871.810 m	2.725 m	1.415 m
Mean (metres)	0.276 m	0.033 m	-0.027 m
RMSE (metres)	3.810 m	0.628 m	0.449 m
Standard deviation (metres)	3.800 m	0.627 m	0.449 m
Median (metres)	-0.01 m	-0.03 m	-0.04 m
Skewness	1.629	0.943	0.345
Kurtosis	190.349	3.594	1.033

Table 11 - Statistics of the (Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – ICESat-1) comparison.

Figure 29 - Error histogram of the (Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – ICESat-1) comparison.

Arithmetic mean (0.033 m, 95% linear error) gives the systematic bias between Copernicus DEM GLO-30 and ICESat-1 heights. Root Mean Square Error or RMSE (0.628 m, 95% linear error) is the quadratic mean of the errors including the bias. Standard deviation (0.627 m, 95% linear error) gives the distribution of the errors around the mean out of the bias. The median error m is the one for which 50% of the pixels have an error less than m and 50% have an error greater than m.

4.2.6 Assessment of Copernicus DEM GLO-90 from ICESat-1 / GLAS data

4.2.6.1 Spatial extent

The following figure (hyperlink <https://visioterra.org/VtWeb/hyperlook/2083868e1ab84b27891ed8c5b8f21617>) shows the coverage map of Copernicus DEM GLO-90.

Figure 30- Copernicus DEM GLO-90 coverage map.

However, Copernicus DEM GLO-90 is only assessed in the $[-60, 60]$ latitude interval in order to compare its results with SRTM-GL1, ASTER GDEM and ALOS World 3D. This limitation has been chosen considering the latitude limitation of SRTM-GL1 and the voids of ALOS World 3D.

4.2.6.2 Method and notations

The methodology used is the same as the one for the assessment of Copernicus DEM EEA-10 from ICESat-1 (see section 4.2.4).

4.2.6.3 Results

Here are the results of this study. All the statistics refer to the differences between Copernicus DEM GLO-90 and ICESat-1 heights (Copernicus DEM GLO-90 – ICESat-1):

	Raw	LE95	LE90
Number of ICESat-1 products	642		
Number of compared heights	62 522 183	59 396 074	56 269 965
Min	-4144.069 m	-3.015 m	-1.636 m
Max	3871.787 m	3.015 m	1.636 m
Mean (metres)	0.278 m	0.066 m	0.006 m
RMSE (metres)	3.818 m	0.709 m	0.505 m
Standard deviation (metres)	3.808 m	0.706 m	0.505 m
Median (metres)	0.001 m	-0.001 m	-0.001 m
Skewness	0.823	0.793	0.364
Kurtosis	180.141	3.600	1.257

Table 12 - Statistics of the (Copernicus DEM GLO-90 – ICESat-1) comparison.

Figure 31 - Error histogram of the (Copernicus DEM GLO-90 – ICESat-1) comparison.

Arithmetic mean (0.066 m, 95% linear error) gives the systematic bias between ICESat-1 and Copernicus DEM GLO-90 heights. Root Mean Square Error or RMSE (0.709 m, 95% linear error) is the quadratic mean of the errors including the bias. Standard deviation (0.706 m, 95% linear error) gives the distribution of the errors around the mean out of the bias. The median error m is the one for which 50% of the pixels have an error less than m and 50% have an error greater than m .

4.3 Elevation assessment from ICESat-2 / ATLAS LiDAR – Quantitative assessment

This section presents the quantitative evaluation of the vertical accuracy of Copernicus DEM EEA-10, Copernicus DEM GLO-30 and Copernicus DEM GLO-90 data using reference data from the ICESat-2 / ATLAS LiDAR.

As described in the previous section 4.2, this assessment is quantitative, consisting of comparing each valid elevation given in LiDAR products to its homologous point to be interpolated from each assessed DEM.

As this study follows the same principles as the previous quantitative study (see section 4.2), this section focuses on the processing of ICESat-2 products used as a vertical reference. Information about the processing of the three Copernicus DEMs will not be repeated.

4.3.1 History of ICESat-2

Ice, Cloud and Land Elevation Satellite (ICESat-2) is an ongoing mission launched on the 15th of September 2018. This mission succeeds the ICESat-1 mission, which acquired heights from the 13th of January 2003 to the 11th of October 2009. The main goal of this mission is to precisely measure the elevation of ice sheets, sea ice, canopy and terrain surface. The ATLAS instrument, carried by ICESat-2, is a photon counting LiDAR. This instrument, by means of its unprecedented accuracy and measurement frequency, has already acquired terabytes of data in less than ten cycles of acquisition.

Figure 32 – 3D representation of ICESat-2.
(<https://svs.gsfc.nasa.gov/cgi-bin/details.cgi?aid=11712>)

4.3.2 Technical specifications

Onboard ICESat-2, the Advanced Topographic Laser Altimeter System (**ATLAS**) sends laser pulses at the very high frequency of **10Khz**, which is 250 times greater than the 40Hz acquisition frequency of the Geoscience Laser Altimeter System (GLAS instrument, carried by ICESat-1). Moreover, the **ATLAS** instrument acquires elevations over **six ground tracks**: three strong beams and three weak beams.

The following figure illustrates the ground tracks of the ATLAS instrument:

Figure 33 – Ground tracks of ICESat-2.
(extracted from <https://doi.org/10.5194/tc-2020-330>)

The following table summarizes the characteristics of the ICESat-2 mission and the ATLAS instrument:

Technical specification	Value
Instrument name	Advanced Topographic Laser Altimeter System (ATLAS)
First acquisition date	13.10.2018
Last acquisition date	Ongoing
Acquisition frequency	10 KHz
Ground sampling distance	~0.7 m
Central wavelength	532 nm (green)
Number of beams	6
Repeat cycle	91 days
Footprint diameter	13 m

Table 13 – Technical specifications of ICESat-1 and ICESat-2.

4.3.3 Assessment of ICESat-2 / ATLAS measurements reliability

4.3.3.1 ATL08 product

4.3.3.1.1 Product organisation

The ATL08 product, distributed by the NSIDC, contains terrain and canopy height above the WGS84 ellipsoid. This product is available in the HDF5 format. This format consists of a hierarchical data structure, composed of groups and variables. For instance, the root group of the ATL08 products contain the following groups and variables:

Figure 34 – Root group of ATL08 products.

The groups **ancillary_data**, **METADATA**, **orbit_info**, **quality_assessment** and the variables **ds_geosegments**, **ds_metrics** and **ds_surf_type** give information and data at product level, whereas the groups **gt1l**, **gt1r**, **gt2l**, **gt2r**, **gt3l** and **gt3r** contain height measurements, ancillary data and quality flags at a fixed step of 100 metres.

The **gt1l**, **gt1r**, **gt2l**, **gt2r**, **gt3l** and **gt3r** groups consist of the data acquired by each laser beam at a specified ground track. It is important to note that these ground track labels may refer to different actual laser beams from one product to another, as the orientation of ICESat-2 changes over the time. The following figure illustrates the two possible orientations of the ATLAS instrument:

Figure 35 – Orientations of the ATLAS instrument, impact on the laser beams ground tracks labelling. (extracted from RD-22)

4.3.3.1.2 ATL08 footprint

The ATLAS instrument of ICESat-2 acquires data at 10 kHz (see green circles in attached figure).

The variables of the ATL08 product are generated from an aggregation of these acquisitions at a fixed distance of 100 metres along-track. Each ATL08 variable reported is computed from 100 metres of ICESat-2 acquisitions (50 metres before and after variable geolocation along-track). As a consequence, footprints of the ATL08 variables can be seen as a path instead of a circle, as they are generated from segments of ICESat-2 acquisitions. This particularity is taken into account in the explanations of the following height error studies.

Figure 36– ICESat-2 ATL08 footprint.

4.3.3.1.3 Data filtering

As illustrated in Figure 35, depending on the orientation of ICESat-2, a ground track label may refer to a weak laser beam or a strong laser beam. For the following studies, only strong laser beams acquisitions are considered to avoid potential biases, as the weak laser beams acquisitions are not suitable for determining both terrain and canopy height (see RD-23, under section 1). Such filtering depends on the orientation of the ATLAS instrument, which is obtained by reading the **sc_orient** variable of each ATL08 product, which can be equal to the following values:

sc_orient flag value	meaning
0	backward orientation
1	forward orientation
2	In transition between orientations

Table 14 – ATL08 sc_orient variable values.

Heights acquired in transition mode are not considered, as a transition between two orientations may lead to degraded acquisitions (see RD-25, under sc_orient variable description).

The following table summarizes the methods used to discriminate between strong and weak laser beams:

Type of beam	Forward orientation beam labels	Backward orientation beam labels
Strong	GT1R GT2R GT3R	GT1L GT2L GT3L
Weak	GT1L GT2L GT3L	GT1R GT2R GT3R

Table 15 – ATLAS laser beam labelling.

Terrain height acquisitions correspond to the **h_te_best_fit** attribute. ALT08 elevations are not retrieved at instrument measurement frequency, but at a fixed step of 100 metres based on photon data of the ATL03 product (see RD-22; under section 1.3.2).

Quality flags are available for each acquisition of each beam. Consequently, each beam acquisitions are filtered individually with the methods described here after. Acquisitions of each beam are filtered using the following flags:

- **segment_watermask**:inland water mask, equals 1 if inland water is detected, 0 otherwise,
- **n_te_photon**:number of photons classified as terrain in acquisition segment (100 metres segments of multiple acquisitions),
- **h_te_uncertainty**:uncertainty of mean terrain height for the current segment (100 metres segments of multiple acquisitions).

The following flag conditions have been applied in order to keep only valid terrain heights:

Flag	Condition	Meaning
segment_watermask	= 0	No inland water detected
n_te_photon	> 100	More than 100 photons return from terrain surface
h_te_uncertainty	< 7.5 m	Terrain height uncertainty is lower than 7.5 metres

Table 16 – ATL08 product terrain heights validity conditions.

Canopy height is retrieved using the **h_canopy** variable of each ATL08 product. This variable corresponds to the height of canopy above the estimated terrain surface (see RD-25, under the h_canopy variable description). Canopy height is only considered when the variable **canopy_flag** indicates the presence of canopy.

Invalid values of h_canopy have been filtered considering the filling values indicated in the ATL08 product (see RD-25, under the h_canopy variable description). The following table summarizes the criteria used to consider only valid canopy heights:

Variable	Condition	Meaning
canopy_flag	= 1	canopy is present
h_canopy	≠ 3.4028235E38f	canopy height is valid

Table 17 – ATL08 product canopy heights validity conditions.

As only strong beam acquisitions are taken into account, and as terrain and canopy heights have been filtered, the remaining terrain heights are considered as valid. These valid terrain heights are both used to assess the constancy of ICESat-2 height acquisitions (see section 4.3.3.3) and to assess the quality of Copernicus DEM EEA-10 (see section 4.3.4), Copernicus DEM GLO-30 (see section 4.3.5) and Copernicus DEM GLO-90 (see section 4.3.6).

4.3.3.2 Sampling of ICESat-2 / ATLAS data

Sampling equations used for ICESat-2 / ATLAS do not differ from equations used in the ICESat-1 / GLAS study. Please refer to section 4.2.3.2 for further details.

4.3.3.3 Collocated measurements on the same orbit

4.3.3.3.1 Scope

Multiple heights retrieved from the ATL08 product are analysed on the same orbit over multiple revolutions to assess ICESat-2's instrument reliability. This study has the same geographical extent than the study of ICESat-1's instrument reliability, over the Salt Lake of Salar de Uyuni (see section 4.2.3.3 and attached figure).

4.3.3.3.2 Method

Definitions

The following terminology is used in this study:

- **Terrain height:** terrain height given in the ATL08 product (identified as the h_te_best_fit variable) retrieved at a given geolocation (longitude, latitude). The terrain height is estimated over 100 m segments worth of terrain photons along-track, taken from the ATL03 product. The terrain height is estimated at the mid-point location of each 100 m segment (see RD-23 for further explanation),
- **Reference ground track:** segment of orbit identified by an id, which remains identical from one revolution to another. Given an ATL08 product, the reference ground track remains identical for every terrain height, only the laser ground track changes (see definition below),
- **Laser track #n:** track of acquisition of a specific laser beam emitted from the ATLAS instrument. An ATL08 product typically contains 6 laser ground tracks sharing the same reference ground track.
- **Profile:** set of terrain heights acquired contiguously along-track, sharing the same reference ground track and laser ground track.

Reliability assessment

The goal of this study is to ensure ICESat-2/ATLAS heights acquired over multiple revolutions on a common reference ground track do not largely differ (especially, the terrain heights retrieved in the ATL08 product). This study aims to evaluate the **constancy** of ICESat-2/ATLAS terrain height estimations over multiple revolutions.

Considering the large amount of reference ground tracks, and therefore, the large amount of data, a strict filtering procedure has been applied in order to keep the best terrain height estimations from ATL08 products. The following list summarizes the steps of filtering ICESat-2 ATL08 products:

1. Only terrain heights contained in the defined bounding box are considered,
2. Terrain heights flagged as invalid are excluded (see section 4.3.3.1 for filtering procedures),
3. Profiles containing invalid data due to the terrain height filtering are excluded, avoiding potential biases linked to different numbers of terrain heights among reference ground tracks,
4. Profiles not beginning (respectively ending) at the top (respectively bottom) of the bounding box are excluded, for the same reasons as explained in step 3,
5. Profiles not sharing a common reference ground track with any other close enough profile is excluded (< 500 metres between profiles), as the constancy of ICESat-2 ATL08 heights cannot be estimated from only one profile.

The results of this filtering are 10 pairs of profiles, in which the two profiles share the same reference ground track. The following figure gives an overview of the pairs of profiles kept for this study:

Figure 37 - Pairs of profiles considered for the ICESat-2 reliability study.

The following table gives the origin of every profile kept for this study:

Profile pair number	Product ID	Date of acquisition	Reference ground track	Laser track
1	ATL08_20200713012933_02700808_003_01.h5	13.07.2020	270	gt11/

Profile pair number	Product ID	Date of acquisition	Reference ground track	Laser track
	ATL08_20201011210920_02700908_003_01.h5	11.10.2020	270	gt3l/
2	ATL08_20200413054946_02700708_003_01.h5	13.04.2020	270	gt3r/
	ATL08_20201011210920_02700908_003_01.h5	11.10.2020	270	gt2l/
3	ATL08_20200413054946_02700708_003_01.h5	13.04.2020	270	gt2r/
	ATL08_20201011210920_02700908_003_01.h5	11.10.2020	270	gt1l/
4	ATL08_20200617145103_12680714_003_01.h5	17.06.2020	1268	gt3l/
	ATL08_20190919035142_12680414_003_01.h5	19.09.2019	1268	gt1r/
5	ATL08_20200916103051_12680814_003_01.h5	16.09.2020	1268	gt1l/
	ATL08_20190919035142_12680414_003_01.h5	19.09.2019	1268	gt2r/
6	ATL08_20200916103051_12680814_003_01.h5	16.09.2020	1268	gt2l/
	ATL08_20190919035142_12680414_003_01.h5	19.09.2019	1268	gt3r/
7	ATL08_20200811000536_07120808_003_01.h5	11.08.2020	712	gt1l/
	ATL08_20201109194524_07120908_003_01.h5	09.11.2020	712	gt3l/
8	ATL08_20200512042551_07120708_003_01.h5	12.05.2020	712	gt3r/
	ATL08_20201109194524_07120908_003_01.h5	09.11.2020	712	gt2l/
9	ATL08_20200512042551_07120708_003_01.h5	12.05.2020	712	gt2r/
	ATL08_20201109194524_07120908_003_01.h5	09.11.2020	712	gt1l/
10	ATL08_20191018022746_03230514_003_01.h5	18.10.2019	323	gt3r/
	ATL08_20200416174719_03230714_003_01.h5	16.04.2020	323	gt1r/

Table 18 – ICESat-2 ATL08 profile pairs origin.

In order to compute the terrain height difference between two paired profiles, heights are linearly interpolated every 100 metres (fixed step in latitude) on every profile (see section 4.3.3.2 for equations). As the valid profiles do not contain any invalid terrain height, the number of compared interpolated heights is constant from one pair profile to another. Then, the difference between interpolated terrain heights of the same profile pair is computed at each latitude step.

4.3.3.3 Results

The following figures and tables show the height difference statistics of each profile pair:

Figure 38 - Height difference statistics for every profile pair.

The height difference statistics show really good results, considering a RMSE of 0.091 m and a standard deviation of 0.038 m on profile pair 10, which are the worst results of this study.

4.3.3.4 Geographical distribution of ICESat-2 products

This study is based on **119 068** ATL08 products (**3.76 TB**), representing 9 orbit cycles of ICESat-2 data. Most of the products contain acquisitions over 1/14th of an orbit. The products are distributed all over the world as shown in the following figure.

Figure 39 - Distribution of the 119 068 ATL08 products.

4.3.4 Assessment of Copernicus DEM EEA-10 from ICESat-2 / ATLAS data

This section presents the quantitative evaluation of the vertical accuracy of **Copernicus DEM EEA-10** using reference data from **ICESat-2 / ATLAS (LiDAR)**. The methods and the notations of this study are given here after (see section 4.3.4.1). The methods used to process DEM heights are the same as the ones described in section 4.2, consequently, only a summary of the steps involved in comparing the **Copernicus DEM EEA-10** to **ICESat-2 / ATLAS** data is given, referencing other sections for further details. The same methods will apply for the evaluation of **Copernicus DEM GLO-30** (section 4.3.5) and **Copernicus DEM GLO-90** (section 4.3.6) and will not repeated.

4.3.4.1 Method and notations

4.3.4.1.1 Summary of the methods used

The ATL08 product includes terrain and canopy heights. Consequently, statistics concerning two quantitative studies are given, respectively comparing Copernicus DEM EEA-10 heights to ICESat-2 ATL08 **terrain heights only** and to ICESat-2 ATL08 **terrain heights including canopy**.

The main steps of this study are:

- Filtering bad acquisitions from ICESat-2 ATL08 products, retrieving reference ICESat-2 heights relative to the WGS84 ellipsoid,
- Interpolating Copernicus DEM EEA-10 heights at each ICESat-2 ATL08 reference height footprint location, retrieving interpolated DEM heights relative to the EGM2008 geoid,
- Convert the vertical reference system of the interpolated EGM2008 DEM heights to the WGS84 ellipsoid,
- Given ICESat-2 ATL08 heights of reference and Copernicus DEM EEA-10 heights expressed with respect to the WGS84 ellipsoid, compute height differences, both taking as reference ICESat-2 ATL08 terrain heights only and ICESat-2 ATL08 terrain with canopy heights.

Filtering ATL08 products is done using methods described in section 4.3.3.1. Consequently, only strong laser beams acquisitions of the ATL08 product have been considered, and invalid terrain and canopy heights have been filtered. ATL08 product heights are already expressed with respect to the WGS84 ellipsoid, therefore, no vertical reference system conversion is applied to this reference data.

Bilinear interpolation is used to retrieve Copernicus DEM EEA-10 heights at each ICESat-2 strong beam footprint. Then, the interpolated heights are converted from the EGM2008 geoid to the WGS84 ellipsoid (see section 4.2.4.2.3 for more details).

From this point, the difference between Copernicus DEM EEA-10 interpolated heights and ICESat-2 ATL08 heights can be calculated, as both are expressed relative to the WGS84 ellipsoid.

4.3.4.1.2 Computing the height difference

The following equation is used to compute the height difference between Copernicus DEM EEA-10 interpolated height and ICESat-2 ATL08 **terrain height only**:

$$\Delta h = h_{DEM} - h_{ICESat-2_terrain} \quad (\text{eq. 5})$$

Where:

- Δh is the height difference between Copernicus DEM EEA-10 and ICESat-2,
- $h_{ICESat-2_terrain}$ is the ICESat-2 terrain height (with respect to the WGS84 ellipsoid),
- h_{DEM} is the Copernicus DEM EEA-10 height (with respect to the WGS84 ellipsoid).

The following equation is used to compute the height difference between Copernicus DEM EEA-10 interpolated height and ICESat-2 ATL08 **terrain with canopy height**:

$$\Delta h = h_{DEM} - (h_{ICESat-2_terrain} + h_{ICESat-2_canopy_only}) \quad (\text{eq. 6})$$

Where:

- Δh is the height difference between Copernicus DEM EEA-10 and ICESat-2,
- $h_{ICESat-2_terrain}$ is the ICESat-2 terrain height (with respect to the WGS84 ellipsoid),
- $h_{ICESat-2_canopy_only}$ is the ICESat-2 canopy height above ICESat-2 terrain height,
- h_{DEM} is the Copernicus DEM EEA-10 height (with respect to the WGS84 ellipsoid).

4.3.4.2 Overall algorithm

The following diagram summarizes the steps involved in the comparison between the Copernicus DEM EEA-10 and ICESat-2 reference data:

Figure 40 – Summary of the Copernicus DEM EEA-10 assessment method using ICESat-2 ATL08 as a vertical reference.

4.3.4.3 Results

Here are the results of the **Copernicus DEM EEA-10 – ICESat-2** study. The results obtained in this study are compared with results obtained in the **Copernicus DEM EEA-10 – ICESat-1** study. Statistics have been computed for two types of heights: one keeping only ICESat-2 **terrain height**, the other taking into account **canopy height** when canopy is present. All the statistics are computed with a 95% linear error (**LE95**). The following table summarizes the results of these studies:

LE95 statistics	ICESat-1	ICESat-2 (terrain only)	ICESat-2 (terrain with canopy)
Number of compared heights	1 803 551	399 179	399 179
Min	-5.924 m	-8.415 m	-16.642 m
Max	5.924 m	8.421 m	16.600 m
Mean (metres)	0.270 m	0.822 m	-5.477 m
Standard deviation (metres)	1.389 m	1.944 m	4.838 m
RMSE (metres)	1.415 m	2.111 m	7.307 m
Skewness	1.091	1.283	0.251
Kurtosis	3.797	2.823	-0.777

Table 19 - Statistics of the (Copernicus DEM EEA-10 - ICESat-2) comparison.

Figure 41 - Error histogram of the (Copernicus DEM EEA-10 – ICESat-2) study, comparison with previous results using ICESat-1 as vertical reference.

The histogram and the statistics show good results for both ICESat-2 terrain height only and ICESat-2 terrain with canopy height. However, the ICESat-2 terrain with canopy statistics shows worse results than the ICESat-2 terrain only statistics. Moreover, the ICESat-2 terrain with canopy histogram shows a large number of negative errors, ranging from -2 metres to -17 metres approximately. These negative errors are caused by taking into account the canopy height measured by ICESat-2. At first glance, the ICESat-2 terrain with canopy histogram might indicate that Copernicus DEM EEA-10 is not strictly a Digital Surface Model (DSM), but it must be noticed that the h_{canopy} variable of the ATL08 product is an estimation of the canopy height (see section 4.3.4.4.1). The statistics show that the (Copernicus DEM EEA-10 – ICESat-1) study gives better results than the (Copernicus DEM EEA-10 – ICESat-2) studies. The better performance of ICESat-1 could be explained by the fact that Copernicus has been validated from ICESat-1 (see RD-15). Overall, the two terrain studies show that Copernicus DEM EEA-10 is an accurate DEM.

4.3.4.4 Typical sources of elevation errors

4.3.4.4.1 ICESat-2 elevation errors

ATL08 known issues

The RD-26 document references the known issues of the ATL08 product, release 003. One major issue certainly impacting this quantitative study is the incorrect labelling of returning photons. Dense vegetation areas can cause terrain photons to be labelled as noise. The document states that in such cases “the ground height would be reported incorrectly by **approximately 3-5 m**, and the relative canopy height would be under-estimated by that same amount”.

Figure 42 - Incorrect photon labelling in tropical forest (Brazil).
(extracted from RD-26)

In Figure 42, the lowest layer of photons is unclassified (blue), whereas it should be classified as ground (orange).

Such issues certainly affect the results of each Copernicus DEM instance quantitative assessment followed in this section. Other issues mentioned in the RD-26 document should not affect these studies, as they occurred in previous ATL08 product releases or describe geolocation/height errors within the geolocation and height uncertainties of this product.

h_canopy variable

The h_{canopy} variable of the ATL08 product is defined as the following: “the relative 98% height of classified canopy photon heights above the estimated terrain surface. Relative canopy heights have been computed by differencing the canopy photon height from the estimated terrain surface in the ATL08 processing. The relative canopy heights are sorted into a cumulative distribution, and the height associated with the 98% height is reported.” (see RD-23, section 2.2.6). As the retrieved canopy height is an estimation based on 100 metres worth of canopy photons, and not computed directly at the geolocation indicated in the ATL08 product, the h_{canopy} variable may introduce errors in the “Copernicus DEM EEA-10 – ICESat-2 terrain with canopy height” study, especially where the canopy height is varying.

4.3.4.4.2 Geomorphological and land use / land cover context causing elevation errors

This section aims to provide a better understanding of the sources of elevation errors by observing their repartition all over the geographical extent of Copernicus DEM EEA-10. In the figures of this section, negative height errors are depicted in blue (Copernicus DEM EEA-10 height is lower than the ICESat-2 reference height) whereas positive height errors are depicted in red (Copernicus DEM EEA-10 height is greater than the ICESat-2 reference height).

In that follow, the differences between Copernicus DEM EEA-10 and the ICESat-2 terrain (Δh_i) and the ICESat-2 terrain with canopy (Δh_c) are given at error geolocation, showing various geomorphological and/or land use / land cover contexts. Note that the footprint of ICESat-2 is not depicted (in opposite of the ICESat-1 study as illustrated in Figure 19 to Figure 27) because the elevation values are estimated from 100 metres segments of acquisition.

Canopy linked errors

As stated in 1.1.3, “The Copernicus DEM is a Digital Surface Model (DSM) which represents the surface of the Earth including buildings, infrastructure and vegetation”. Comparing Copernicus DEM EEA-10 heights relative to the top of canopy to ICESat-2 terrain heights result in positive errors, as illustrated in the case study of Figure 43.

Figure 43 - EEA-10 - ICESat-2 height differences – Case of Bois de la Mare Chantreuil near Galluis (France).

In Figure 43, an interpolated Copernicus DEM EEA-10 height is compared to a terrain height retrieved in the ATL08 product of ICESat-2. The resulting height difference is significant (+15.931 m) and highlights the major problems of comparing terrain to canopy relative heights.

Considering ICESat-2 terrain with canopy height for this comparison may be a solution for such cases, which results in a smaller but still significant height error (-8.806 m). However, the estimated canopy height is approximately equal to 25 metres, which may seem high for this case study. Bois de la Mare Chantreuil is part of the Rambouillet Forest, which has an area of 22 000 hectares. This forest is majorly known for its oak and pine trees. A reference picture of the Bois de la Mare Chantreuil have been found near the case study area of Figure 43, and is given hereafter in Figure 44.

Figure 44 - Reference picture of Bois de la Mare Chanteuil (France).

As seen in Figure 44, subfigure a, coniferous trees can be found in Bois de la Mare Chanteuil, which could reach 20 to 25 metres. As a consequence, the estimated canopy height of ICESat-2 may be accurate in this case study.

ICESat-2 canopy height estimation

Comparing Copernicus DEM EEA-10 canopy heights to ICESat-2 terrain heights can lead to important height errors, which may be reduced by considering ICESat-2 canopy heights (as seen in Figure 43). However, in some cases, this canopy height may increase errors, as the ATL08 product only provides an estimation of the canopy height based on 100 metres segments worth of canopy classified photons. The case study of Figure 45, concerning the vines of Léognan in France, is an example in which considering the canopy height estimation of ICESat-2 gives worse results than using only ICESat-2 terrain heights.

Figure 45 - EEA-10 - ICESat-2 height differences - Case of the vines of Léognan (France).

In that case study, an ICESat-2 terrain height and canopy height are retrieved over vines. Comparing Copernicus DEM EEA-10 to ICESat-2 terrain heights gives a small error of +0.497 metres. However, the height error reaches -20.041 metres when considering canopy height. The estimated canopy height seems enormous and certainly not corresponds to vines. In this case, the problem may come from the method of processing of the ATL08 product canopy height estimation, which may not be suitable for this quantitative assessment.

The ATL08 canopy height estimation is processed based on 100 metres of acquisition as follows: “The canopy heights are sorted into a cumulative distribution, and the height associated with the 98% height is reported.” (see RD-23, under section 2.2.6). In this case, the estimated canopy height of the ATL08 product may depend on the height of trees surrounding the vines. As a consequence, a Copernicus DEM EEA-10 height retrieved in the vines may be compared to ICESat-2 terrain height summed with a height estimation of the surrounding canopy.

Time-varying snow ice heights

Events occurring between the acquisition periods of TanDEM-X and ICESat-2 may lead to height errors. The case study of Figure 46 highlights a positive error between Copernicus DEM EEA-10 and ICESat-2 terrain height only (+9.079 m).

Figure 46 - EEA-10 - ICESat-2 height differences - Case of the Alps, near the Mont Blanc (Italy).

The Google Earth image used in Figure 46 was acquired on July 2015, and shows the study area partially covered by snow and ice. The Figure 47 shows another image acquired on May

2011, in which we can observe a different snow and ice repartition over the same study area. As a consequence, a cause of this error could be the snow and ice cover varying over the years.

Figure 47 - EEA-10 - ICESat-2 height differences – Varying snow cover – Case of the Alps, near the Mont Blanc (Italy).

A canopy height is available for this study area, whereas no canopy is visible. The comparison of Copernicus DEM EEA-10 and ICESat-2 terrain with canopy height gives a lower absolute height error than using ICESat-2 terrain height only (only -2.301 m height error when taking into account ICESat-2 canopy estimation). As no canopy is present, the canopy estimation of ICESat-2 may be linked to terrain height, which could explain why a smaller error is obtained considering ICESat-2 terrain and canopy height than using only ICESat-2 terrain height.

Time-varying land use

Another case of time-related errors is covered in Figure 48, which highlights a negative error over an industrial building in Bergen op Zoom (Netherlands).

Figure 48 - EEA-10 - ICESat-2 height differences - Case of a building construction in Bergen op Zoom (Netherlands).

Here, the comparison of Copernicus DEM EEA-10 and ICESat-2 terrain height results in a negative error of -12.077 metres. The Google Earth image used in Figure 48 (subfigure c) was acquired on March 2020, and highlights the geolocation of the error over an industrial building. Figure 49 shows the same area, but acquired on July 2014 (subfigure b), where no building is visible.

Figure 49 - EEA-10 - ICESat-2 height differences – Field before building construction in Bergen op Zoom (Netherlands).

As the building was constructed between the two acquisition periods of TanDEM-X and ICESat-2, the Copernicus DEM EEA-10 height is probably relative to the terrain, and the ICESat-2 terrain height is certainly relative to the top of the building.

In this case, a canopy height estimation is also available from ICESat-2 data, whereas no canopy is present. The comparison between the Copernicus DEM EEA-10 height and the ICESat-2 terrain with canopy height is high, almost two times higher than the results obtained using ICESat-2 terrain heights only. Given these facts, the ICESat-2 canopy height estimation may have been computed considering building heights instead of canopy heights.

4.3.5 Assessment of Copernicus DEM GLO-30 from ICESat-2 / ATLAS data

4.3.5.1 Spatial extent

Spatial extent of the Copernicus DEM GLO-30 is given in section 4.2.5.1.

As stated in section 4.2.5.1, Copernicus DEM GLO-30 is only assessed in the $[-60^\circ, 60^\circ]$ latitude interval in order to compare its results with SRTM-GL1, ASTER GDEM and ALOS World 3D. This limitation has been chosen considering the latitude limitation of SRTM-GL1 and the voids of ALOS World 3D.

4.3.5.2 Method and notations

The methodology used is the same as the one for the assessment of Copernicus DEM EEA-10 from ICESat-2 (see section 4.3.4.1).

4.3.5.3 Results

Here are the results of the **Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – ICESat-2** study. The results obtained in this study are compared with results obtained in the **Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – ICESat-1** study. Statistics have been computed for two types of heights: one keeping only ICESat-2 **terrain height**, the other considering **canopy height** when canopy is present. All the statistics are computed with a 95% linear error (**LE95**). The following table summarizes the results of these studies:

LE95 statistics	ICESat-1	ICESat-2 (terrain only)	ICESat-2 (terrain with canopy)
Number of compared heights	59 319 279	13 816 724	13 816 724
Min	-2.725 m	-5.012 m	-11.008 m
Max	2.725 m	5.012 m	11.008 m
Mean (metres)	0.033 m	0.195 m	-1.124 m
Standard deviation (metres)	0.627 m	0.979 m	2.680 m
RMSE (metres)	0.628 m	0.999 m	2.907 m
Skewness	0.943	1.667	-1.953
Kurtosis	3.594	6.085	3.318

Table 20 - Statistics of the (Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – ICESat-2) comparison.

Figure 50 - Error histogram of the (Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – ICESat-2) study, comparison with previous results using ICESat-1 as vertical reference.

The histogram and the statistics show good results for both ICESat-2 terrain height only and ICESat-2 terrain with canopy height. However, the ICESat-2 terrain with canopy statistics shows worse results than the ICESat-2 terrain only statistics. At first glance, the ICESat-2 terrain with canopy histogram might indicate that Copernicus DEM GLO-30 is not strictly a Digital Surface Model (DSM), but it must be noticed that the h_{canopy} variable of the ATL08 product is an estimation of the canopy height (see section 4.3.4.4.1). The statistics show that the (Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – ICESat-1) study gives better results than the (Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – ICESat-2) studies. The better performance of ICESat-1 could be explained by the fact that Copernicus has been validated from ICESat-1 (see RD-15). Overall, the three studies show that Copernicus DEM GLO-30 is a really accurate DEM.

4.3.6 Assessment of Copernicus DEM GLO-90 from ICESat-2 / ATLAS data

4.3.6.1 Spatial extent

Spatial extent of the Copernicus DEM GLO-90 is given in section 4.2.6.1.

As stated in section 4.2.6.1, Copernicus DEM GLO-90 is only assessed in the [-60, 60] latitude interval in order to compare its results with SRTM-GL1, ASTER GDEM and ALOS World 3D. This limitation has been chosen considering the latitude limitation of SRTM-GL1 and the voids of ALOS World 3D.

4.3.6.2 Method and notations

The methodology used is the same as the one for the assessment of Copernicus DEM EEA-10 from ICESat-2 (see section 4.3.4.1).

4.3.6.3 Results

Here are the results of the **Copernicus DEM GLO-90 – ICESat-2** study. The results obtained in this study are compared with results obtained in the **Copernicus DEM GLO-90 – ICESat-1** study. Statistics have been computed for two types of heights: one keeping only ICESat-2 **terrain height**, the other taking into account **canopy height** when canopy is present. All the statistics are computed with a 95% linear error (**LE95**). The following table summarizes the results of these studies:

LE95 statistics	ICESat-1	ICESat-2 (terrain only)	ICESat-2 (terrain with canopy)
Number of compared heights	59 396 074	13 838 239	13 838 239
Min	-3.015 m	-6.256 m	-11.308 m
Max	3.015 m	6.256 m	11.308 m
Mean (metres)	0.066 m	0.271 m	-1.102 m
Standard deviation (metres)	0.706 m	1.391 m	2.898 m
RMSE (metres)	0.709 m	1.417 m	3.100 m
Skewness	0.793	0.919	-1.587
Kurtosis	3.600	4.759	2.841

Table 21 - Statistics of the (Copernicus DEM GLO-90 – ICESat-2) comparison.

Figure 51 - Error histogram of the (Copernicus DEM GLO-90 – ICESat-2) study, comparison with previous results using ICESat-1 as vertical reference.

The histogram and the statistics show good results for both ICESat-2 terrain height only and ICESat-2 terrain with canopy height. However, the ICESat-2 terrain with canopy statistics shows worse results than the ICESat-2 terrain only statistics. At first glance, the ICESat-2 terrain with canopy histogram might indicate that Copernicus DEM GLO-90 is not strictly a Digital Surface Model (DSM), but it must be noticed that the h_{canopy} variable of the ATL08 product is an estimation of the canopy height (see section 4.3.4.4.1). The statistics show that the (Copernicus DEM GLO-90 – ICESat-1) study gives better results than the (Copernicus DEM GLO-90 – ICESat-2) studies. Once again, the better performance of ICESat-1 could be explained by the fact that Copernicus has been validated from ICESat-1 (see RD-15). Overall, the three studies show that Copernicus DEM GLO-90 is a really accurate DEM.

4.4 Elevation assessment from GEDI LiDAR – Quantitative assessment

4.4.1 History of GEDI

GEDI (Global Ecosystem Dynamics Investigation) was a mission led by the University of Maryland in collaboration with NASA Goddard Space Flight Center (GSFC). The GEDI instrument is a LiDAR launched to the ISS (International Space Station) on the 5th of December 2018. This LiDAR acquired data from March 2019 to March 2021. The main goal of this mission was to measure how deforestation has contributed to atmospheric CO₂ concentrations.

Figure 52 - GEDI onboard the ISS.
(<https://gedi.umd.edu/instrument/instrument-overview/>)

4.4.2 Technical specifications

Onboard the ISS, the GEDI instrument fires laser pulses at the frequency of **242 Hz**. This instrument acquires data over 8 ground tracks, as illustrated in the following figure.

Figure 53 - GEDI lasers, beams and ground tracks.
(<https://gedi.umd.edu/instrument/specifications/>)

Figure 54 - GEDI height profiles over Luxembourg (near Diekirch, 2019.04.18).

As illustrated, the GEDI instrument is composed of three lasers (one coverage laser and two full power lasers). The coverage laser is split into two beams, whereas the two full power lasers fire a unique beam, resulting in four laser beams fired simultaneously. Each laser beam alternates between two ground tracks, giving the eight ground tracks covered by the GEDI instrument.

The following table summarizes the characteristics of the GEDI instrument.

Technical specification	Value
Instrument name	Global Ecosystem Dynamics Investigation (GEDI)
First acquisition date	25.03.2019
Last acquisition date	Ongoing
Acquisition frequency	242 Hz
Ground sampling distance	~60 m (along track)
Central wavelength	1064 nm (near infrared)
Number of beams	8
Inter-beams distance	600 m
Repeat cycle	No repeat cycle
Footprint diameter	~25 m

Table 22 – GEDI technical specifications.

4.4.3 Assessment of GEDI measurement reliability

4.4.3.1 GEDI02_A product

4.4.3.1.1 Product organisation

The GEDI02_A product provides both waveform related variables and heights processed from the GEDI01_B product (geolocated waveforms). This product includes the ground elevation (elev_lowestmode) and the top of canopy height (elev_highestreturn). This product is available in the HDF5 format, which is composed of a hierarchical data structure (containing groups of variables). The root groups of these products are shown in Figure 55.

Figure 55 – Root group of GEDI02_A products.

All of these groups contain variables relative to one laser beam (except for the METADATA group, which contains dataset related metadata). The **BEAM0000**, **BEAM0001**, **BEAM0010** and **BEAM0011** groups contain acquisitions of the four coverage beams of GEDI, whereas the **BEAM0101**, **BEAM0110**, **BEAM1000** and **BEAM1011** groups contain acquisitions of the four full-power beams.

In each group, two height acquisitions are retrieved:

- **elev_lowestmode** - elevation of centre of lowest mode relative to reference ellipsoid,
- **elev_highestreturn** - elevation of highest detected return relative to reference ellipsoid.

Figure 56 – GEDI return waveform and footprint.

As illustrated in Figure 56, when canopy is present, the `elev_lowestmode` and `elev_highestreturn` variables respectively correspond to the ground and the top of canopy elevations (labelled “Ground Return” and “Highest Reflecting Surface Height” in Figure 56). These elevations are given relative to the WGS84 ellipsoid.

The following histogram highlights the difference between the lowest mode and highest return elevations of the GEDI02_A product (acquisitions from 2019.04.18 to 2019.05.18). Outliers have been filtered using the **surface_flag** of the GEDI02_A product (equal to 1).

Figure 57 – Histogram of the difference between GEDI lowest mode and highest return, filtered using surface_flag.

As illustrated in Figure 57, for nearly 20% of GEDI acquisitions from 2019.04.18 to 2019.05.18, the lowest mode and highest return elevations are equal. Most of the differences (54.24%) between those elevations are included in the [-4 m, -2 m] interval.

4.4.3.1.2 Data filtering

Considering valid reference data requires GEDI02_A products to be filtered. Hereafter, three instances of the same GEDI02_A height profile are compared using different filtering techniques.

Figure 58 – GEDI02_A BEAM0000 height filtering over Brazil (2019.04.19).

The three instances of the same GEDI profile are retrieved with the following methods:

- No filtering is applied to the data (subfigure a),
- quality_flag and degrade_flag are used to filter bad quality data (subfigure b),
- surface_flag is used to filter outliers (subfigure c).

Only removing outliers using the surface_flag (subfigure c) is a good approach for visualization purposes. Using the quality_flag and degrade_flag is more suitable for quality assessments, as the majority of bad quality data is removed (subfigure b).

For this assessment, the filtering method depicted in Figure 58, subfigure b is used to consider valid GEDI02_A data. The filtering conditions are described in the following table.

Flag	Condition	Meaning
quality_flag	= 1	Valid acquisition (based on energy, sensitivity, amplitude, real-time surface tracking quality)
degrade_flag	= 0	No degraded orbit (geolocation errors)

Table 23 – GEDI02_A product height validity conditions.

However, using these quality flags filter the acquisitions for which GEDI lowest mode and highest return elevation are equal (which is not the case using the surface_flag, see Figure 57). The difference between GEDI lowest mode and highest return elevations is illustrated by the following histogram (filtered with quality_flag and degrade_flag).

Figure 59 - Histogram of the difference between GEDI lowest mode and highest return, filtered using quality_flag and degrade_flag.

As illustrated in Figure 59, for the majority of GEDI acquisitions, the difference between lowest mode and highest return elevations is included in the [-4 m, -2 m] interval.

These filtered heights are both used to assess the accuracy of GEDI02_A heights (see section 0) and to assess the quality of Copernicus DEM EEA-10 (see section 4.4.4), Copernicus DEM GLO-30 (see section 4.4.5) and Copernicus DEM GLO-90 (see section 4.4.6).

4.4.3.2 Sampling of GEDI data

Sampling method (linear interpolation) used for GEDI data do not differ from the one used in the ICESat-1 / GLAS study. Please refer to section 4.2.3.2 for further details.

4.4.3.3 Height comparison with ICESat-1 and ICESat-2

4.4.3.3.1 Scope

In sections 4.2.3 and 4.3.3, ICESat-1 and ICESat-2 heights are compared on the same orbit over multiple revolutions to assess their constancy. Unfortunately, the ISS has no specific orbit repeat cycle, which prevents a similar study to be followed for the GEDI instrument.

As an alternative, this section presents multiple comparisons between GEDI (GEDI02_A) heights and ICESat-1 (GLAH14) / ICESat-2 (ATL08) heights over the Salt Lake Salar de Uyuni in Bolivia. This Salt Lake is known to be particularly flat and surrounded by mountains. Height comparisons are computed both on flat and mountainous areas, giving an overview of the similarities and differences between each LiDAR retrieved heights.

4.4.3.3.2 Method

The RD-43 presents multiple height comparisons over profile intersections between GEDI (GEDI02_A product) and ICESat-1/ICESat-2 (GLAH14 and ATL08 products) height profiles. The following figure highlights the study area and the intersecting height profiles.

Figure 60 – Intersection of GEDI and ICESat-1 / ICESat-2 height profiles over Salar de Uyuni.

Heights are interpolated on GEDI lowest mode, ICESat-1 and ICESat-2 terrain profiles at each intersection location. Then, the differences between the interpolated heights of GEDI and ICESat-1 / ICESat-2 is computed, named Δh in the following figures.

Figure 61 – Intersections between GEDI and ICESat-1 over Salar de Uyuni (left), outside of Salar de Uyuni (right).

As illustrated in Figure 61, a relatively important height difference is observed over the Salar de Uyuni (-1.40 metres); a smaller error may have been expected due to the flatness of this area. An even bigger height difference is observed on mountainous areas around the Salar de Uyuni (+8.32 metres).

Figure 62 – Intersections between GEDI and ICESat-2 over Salar de Uyuni.

As illustrated in Figure 62, small elevation differences may be observed when comparing GEDI lowest mode to ICESat-2 terrain heights. The differences between GEDI and ICESat-2 look smaller than those observed between GEDI and ICESat-1.

Figure 63 – Intersections between GEDI and ICESat-2 around Salar de Uyuni.

On the opposite of the small height differences observed in the Salar (see Figure 62), these differences are much larger in the mountainous areas around the Salar (see Figure 63).

This study is only performed on a few examples. The intercomparison of multiple LiDAR acquisitions should be performed on a more representative number of samples.

4.4.3.4 Geographical distribution of GEDI products

This study is based on **1628** GEDI02_A products (**2.44 TB**), representing one month of GEDI data (2019.04.18 to 2019.05.18). The products contain acquisitions up to 1/4th of an orbit. GEDI acquisitions are limited to the [-51.6°, +51.6°] latitude interval, as shown in the following figure.

Figure 64 - Distribution of the 1628 used GEDI02_A products.

4.4.4 Assessment of Copernicus DEM EEA-10 from GEDI data

This section presents the quantitative evaluation of the vertical accuracy of **Copernicus DEM EEA-10** using reference data from **GEDI (LiDAR)**. The methods and the notations of this study are given here after (see section 4.4.4.1). The methods used to process DEM heights are the same as the ones described in section 4.2, consequently, only a summary of the steps involved in comparing the **Copernicus DEM EEA-10** to **GEDI** data is given, referencing other sections for further details. The same methods will apply for the evaluation of **Copernicus DEM GLO-30** (section 4.4.5) and **Copernicus DEM GLO-90** (section 4.4.6) and will not be repeated.

4.4.4.1 Method and notations

4.4.4.1.1 Summary of the methods used

The GEDI02_A product includes two distinct elevations: the lowest mode elevation and the highest return elevation. Consequently, statistics concerning two quantitative studies are given, respectively comparing Copernicus DEM EEA-10 heights to GEDI02_A **lowest mode elevation** and to GEDI02_A **highest return elevation**.

The main steps of this study are:

- Filtering bad acquisitions from GEDI02_A products, retrieving reference GEDI heights relative to the WGS84 ellipsoid,
- Interpolating Copernicus DEM EEA-10 heights at each GEDI02_A reference height footprint location, retrieving interpolated DEM heights relative to the EGM2008 geoid,
- Convert the vertical reference system of the interpolated EGM2008 DEM heights to the WGS84 ellipsoid,
- Given GEDI20_A heights of reference and Copernicus DEM EEA-10 heights expressed with respect to the WGS84 ellipsoid, compute height differences, both taking as reference GEDI02_A lowest mode elevations and GEDI02_A highest return elevations.

Filtering GEDI02_A products is done using methods described in section 4.4.3.1. GEDI02_A product heights are already expressed with respect to the WGS84 ellipsoid. Therefore, no vertical reference system conversion is applied to this reference data.

Bilinear interpolation is used to retrieve Copernicus DEM EEA-10 heights at each GEDI acquisition footprint. Then, the interpolated heights are converted from the EGM2008 geoid to the WGS84 ellipsoid (see section 4.2.4.2.3 for more details).

From this point, the difference between Copernicus DEM EEA-10 and GEDI02_A heights can be calculated, as both are expressed relative to the WGS84 ellipsoid.

4.4.4.1.2 Computing the height difference

The following equation is used to compute the height difference between Copernicus DEM EEA-10 interpolated height and GEDI02_A **lowest mode**:

$$\Delta h = h_{DEM} - h_{GEDI_{lm}} \quad (\text{eq. 7})$$

Where:

- Δh is the height difference between Copernicus DEM EEA-10 and ICESat-2,
- $h_{GEDI_{lm}}$ is the GEDI02_A lowest mode height (with respect to the WGS84 ellipsoid),
- h_{DEM} is the Copernicus DEM EEA-10 height (with respect to the WGS84 ellipsoid).

The following equation is used to compute the height difference between Copernicus DEM EEA-10 interpolated height and GEDI02_A **highest return**:

$$\Delta h = h_{DEM} - h_{GEDI_{hr}} \quad (\text{eq. 8})$$

Where:

- Δh is the height difference between Copernicus DEM EEA-10 and ICESat-2,
- $h_{GEDI_{hr}}$ is the GEDI highest return height (with respect to the WGS84 ellipsoid),
- h_{DEM} is the Copernicus DEM EEA-10 height (with respect to the WGS84 ellipsoid).

4.4.4.2 Overall algorithm

The following diagram summarizes the steps involved in the comparison between the Copernicus DEM EEA-10 and GEDI reference data:

Figure 65 – Summary of the Copernicus DEM EEA-10 assessment method using GEDI as a vertical reference.

4.4.4.3 Results

Here are the results of the **Copernicus DEM EEA-10 – GEDI** study. The results obtained in this study are compared with results obtained in the **Copernicus DEM EEA-10 – ICESat-1** and **Copernicus DEM EEA-10 – ICESat-2** studies. Statistics have been computed for two types of heights, respectively considering the lowest mode and highest return elevations of GEDI02_A products. All the statistics are computed with a 95% linear error (**LE95**). The following table summarizes the results of these studies:

LE95 statistics	ICESat-1	ICESat-2 (terrain only)	ICESat-2 (terrain with canopy)	GEDI (lowest mode)	GEDI (highest return)
Number of compared heights	1 803 551	399 179	399 179	10 995 616	10 995 618
Min	-5.924 m	-8.415 m	-16.642 m	-19.490 m	-17.129 m
Max	5.924 m	8.421 m	16.600 m	19.540 m	16.960 m
Mean (metres)	0.270 m	0.822 m	-5.477 m	2.167 m	-6.834 m
Standard deviation (metres)	1.389 m	1.944 m	4.838 m	5.027 m	3.774 m
RMSE (metres)	1.415 m	2.111 m	7.307 m	5.474 m	7.807 m
Skewness	1.091	1.283	0.251	1.610	-0.218
Kurtosis	3.797	2.823	-0.777	2.031	2.017

Table 24 - Error statistics of the (Copernicus DEM EEA-10 - GEDI) study, comparison with previous results using ICESat-1 and ICESat-2 as vertical references.

Copernicus DEM EEA-10 - Comparison with ICESat-1, ICESat-2 and GEDI (LE95)

Figure 66 - Error histogram of the (Copernicus DEM EEA-10 - GEDI) study, comparison with previous results using ICESat-1 and ICESat-2 as vertical references.

The histogram and the statistics show better results using GEDI lowest mode than using GEDI highest return as a vertical reference. As a consequence, Copernicus DEM EEA-10 heights are closer to GEDI lowest mode (ground return) than to GEDI highest return (top of canopy return). Here, a difference of a few metres can be observed (algebraic mean difference of 9.001 m) between the modes of the (Copernicus DEM EEA-10 – GEDI lowest mode) and the (Copernicus DEM EEA-10 – GEDI highest return). This difference is linked to the GEDI02_A product, for which every valid acquisition has a different lowest mode and highest return elevations (see section 4.4.3.1.2 for further details). Considering ICESat-1 reference data still gives the best results, retrieving a mean, standard deviation and RMSE of respectively 0.270 metres, 1.389 metres and 1.415 metres. Considering GEDI highest return reference data gives the worst results for both mean height error and RMSE, respectively reaching - 6.834 metres and 7.807 metres. The worst standard deviation is obtained using GEDI lowest mode as reference data, reaching 5.027 metres.

4.4.4.4 Typical sources of elevation errors

4.4.4.4.1 GEDI elevation errors

Section 8 of RD-28 references known issues for GEDI02_A and GEDI02_B products. Concerning the GEDI02_A product, the following issues are mentioned:

- **Orbit degradation periods:** periods when the orbit is degraded may impact the quality of the geolocation. This issue is fixed by considering the `degrade_flag` of the GEDI02_A product, which indicates a non-degraded orbit.
- **Retrieval algorithms:** six different algorithm settings can be used to compute `elev_lowestmode` (ground height), `elev_highestreturn` (top of canopy elevation) as well as their respective geolocations. GEDI02_A geolocations and heights are retrieved from the algorithm settings giving the best global product performance. Locally, other algorithm settings may give better results. For this study, the algorithm giving the best global performance has been considered.
- **Surface flag:** The `surface_flag` may incorrectly be set to 0 in high elevation areas, causing the filtering of good acquisitions over these areas.
- **BEAM0000/BEAM0001:** RD-28 references a known bias affecting the BEAM0000 and BEAM0001 absolute heights (up to 60 centimetres of error). This issue was already fixed in the L1B products version 2 and does not occur in this study.

- **Degrade flag:** some elevation errors are stated not to be identified by the “\ade” flag (supposedly the “degrade” flag). Users are encouraged to use the “degrade_flag” and to consider the difference between GEDI and DEM heights to filter bad acquisitions. In the case of this study, the “quality_flag” already considers this difference to filter bad acquisitions.

4.4.4.4.2 Geomorphological and land use / land cover context causing elevation errors

This section aims to provide a better understanding of the sources of Copernicus DEM EEA-10 height errors by observing their repartition all over the geographical extent of this study. In the figures of this section, negative height errors are depicted in blue (Copernicus DEM EEA-10 height is lower than the GEDI reference height) whereas positive height errors are depicted in red (Copernicus DEM EEA-10 height is greater than the GEDI reference height).

In the following examples, the differences between Copernicus DEM EEA-10 and the GEDI lowest mode (Δh_{lm}) and the GEDI highest return (Δh_{hr}) are given at error geolocation, showing various geomorphological and/or land use / land cover contexts.

DSM heights vs. terrain heights

As stated in 1.1.3, “The Copernicus DEM is a Digital Surface Model (DSM) which represents the surface of the Earth including buildings, infrastructure and vegetation”. Comparing Copernicus DEM EEA-10 heights relative to the top of canopy to GEDI lowest mode heights (ground return) result in positive errors, as illustrated in the case study of Figure 67.

Figure 67 - EEA-10 - GEDI height differences – Case of dense forests near Chendrea (Romania).

In Figure 67, an interpolated Copernicus DEM EEA-10 height is compared to a lowest mode elevation retrieved in a GEDI02_A product. The resulting height difference is significant (+20.176 m) and highlights the major problems of comparing terrain to canopy heights.

Considering the GEDI02_A highest return elevation for this comparison may be a solution for such cases, which results in a smaller error (-2.475 m).

Sparse canopy

In this case study, GEDI02_A lowest mode and highest return elevations are retrieved from an acquisition over a small cluster of trees.

Figure 68 - EEA-10 - GEDI height differences – Case of sparse canopy near fields of Centro Tre Denari (Italy).

As shown in Figure 68, the Copernicus DEM EEA-10 height is really close to the lowest mode elevation of GEDI, retrieving a small height error (-0.131 m). On the opposite, a high error is retrieved when using the highest return elevation of GEDI (-24.980 m).

Excavations

In this case study, a Copernicus DEM EEA-10 height and GEDI02_A elevations are compared over the Tagebau Nochten mine in Germany.

Figure 69 - EEA-10 - GEDI height differences – Case of the Tagebau Nochten mine (Germany).

Excavations such as the Tagebau Nochten mine can lead to high height errors from one acquisition to another. Figure 70 highlights the evolution of the Tagebau Nochten mine from September 2014 to August 2016.

Figure 70 - EEA-10 - GEDI height differences – Evolution of the Tagebau Nochten mine (Germany).

As seen in Figure 70, the Tagebau Nochten mine have expanded from 2014 to 2016. The Copernicus DEM EEA-10 heights are retrieved from 2010 to 2015 TanDEM-X acquisitions, whereas the reference GEDI heights are retrieved from 2019 acquisitions. As a consequence, important height errors highlighted in Figure 69 (respectively +75.145 m and +78.586 m for highest return and lowest mode) are certainly linked to the activity of the Tagebau Nochten mine.

Buildings

In this case study, Copernicus DEM EEA-10 and GEDI heights are compared close to a building in Striesa (Germany).

Figure 71 - EEA-10 - GEDI height differences – Case of an industrial building in Striesa (Germany).

As illustrated in Figure 71, the footprint of the GEDI acquisition covers both ground and the roof of a building. As a consequence, the GEDI lowest mode and highest return elevations highly differ. In this case, the Copernicus DEM EEA-10 height is closer to the lowest mode elevation (-0.167 metres of difference) than to the highest return of GEDI (-20.438 metres of difference).

4.4.5 Assessment of Copernicus DEM GLO-30 from GEDI data

4.4.5.1 Spatial extent

Spatial extent of the Copernicus DEM GLO-30 is given in section 4.2.5.1.

Copernicus DEM GLO-30 is only assessed in the $[-51.6^\circ, 51.6^\circ]$ latitude interval, as GEDI acquisitions are restricted to this geographical extent due to the orbit of the ISS.

4.4.5.2 Method and notations

The methodology used is the same as the one for the assessment of Copernicus DEM EEA-10 from GEDI (see section 4.4.4.1).

4.4.5.3 Results

Here are the results of the **Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – GEDI** study. The results obtained in this study are compared with results obtained in the **Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – ICESat-1** and **Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – ICESat-2** studies. Statistics have been computed for two types of heights, respectively considering the lowest mode and highest return elevations of GEDI02_A products. All the statistics are computed with a 95% linear error (**LE95**). The following table summarizes the results of these studies:

LE95 statistics	ICESat-1	ICESat-2 (terrain only)	ICESat-2 (terrain with canopy)	GEDI (lowest mode)	GEDI (highest return)
Number of compared heights	59 319 279	13 816 724	13 816 724	205 139 948	205 139 948
Min	-2,725 m	-5,012 m	-11,008 m	-14,200 m	-15,320 m
Max	2,725 m	5,012 m	11,008 m	14,240 m	15,180 m
Mean (metres)	0,033 m	0,195 m	-1,124 m	1,001 m	-5,786 m
Standard deviation (metres)	0,627 m	0,979 m	2,680 m	3,281 m	3,180 m
RMSE (metres)	0,628 m	0,999 m	2,907 m	3,431 m	6,603 m
Skewness	0,943	1,667	-1,953	1,759	-0,663
Kurtosis	3,594	6,085	3,318	3,937	2,147

Table 25 - Error statistics of the (Copernicus DEM GLO-30 - GEDI) study, comparison with previous results using ICESat-1 and ICESat-2 as vertical references.

Copernicus DEM GLO-30 - Comparison with ICESat-1, ICESat-2 and GEDI (LE95)

LiDAR footprint diameters

Figure 72 - Error histogram of the (Copernicus DEM GLO-30 - GEDI) study, comparison with previous results using ICESat-1 and ICESat-2 as vertical references.

The histogram and the statistics show better results using GEDI lowest mode than using GEDI highest return as a vertical reference. As a consequence, Copernicus DEM GLO-30 heights are closer to GEDI lowest mode (ground return) than to GEDI highest return (top of canopy return). Here, a difference of a few metres (algebraic mean difference of 6,787 m) can be observed between the modes of the Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – GEDI lowest mode and the Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – GEDI highest return modes. This difference is linked to the GEDI02_A product, for which every valid acquisition has a different lowest mode and highest return elevations (see section 4.4.3.1.2 for further details). Considering ICESat-1 reference data still gives the best results, retrieving a mean, standard deviation and RMSE of respectively 0.033 metres, 0.627 metres and 0.628 metres. Considering GEDI highest return reference data gives the worst results for both mean height error and RMSE, respectively reaching - 5.786 metres and 6.603 metres. The worst standard deviation is obtained using GEDI lowest mode as reference data, reaching 3.281 metres.

4.4.6 Assessment of Copernicus DEM GLO-90 from GEDI data

4.4.6.1 Spatial extent

Spatial extent of the Copernicus DEM GLO-90 is given in section 4.2.6.1.

Copernicus DEM GLO-90 is only assessed in the $[-51.6^\circ, 51.6^\circ]$ latitude interval, as GEDI acquisitions are restricted to this geographical extent due to the orbit of the ISS.

4.4.6.2 Method and notations

The methodology used is the same as the one for the assessment of Copernicus DEM EEA-10 from GEDI (see section 4.3.4.1).

4.4.6.3 Results

Here are the results of the **Copernicus DEM GLO-90 – GEDI** study. The results obtained in this study are compared with results obtained in the **Copernicus DEM GLO-90 – ICESat-1** and **Copernicus DEM GLO-90 – ICESat-2** studies. Statistics have been computed for two types of heights, respectively considering the lowest mode and highest return elevations of GEDI02_A products. All the statistics are computed with a 95% linear error (**LE95**). The following table summarizes the results of these studies:

LE95 statistics	ICESat-1	ICESat-2 (terrain only)	ICESat-2 (terrain with canopy)	GEDI (lowest mode)	GEDI (highest return)
Number of compared heights	59 396 074	13 838 239	13 838 239	205 748 661	205 748 661
Min	-3.015 m	-6.256 m	-11.308 m	-15.010 m	-16.780 m
Max	3.015 m	6.256 m	11.308 m	15.050 m	16.639 m
Mean (metres)	0.066 m	0.271 m	-1.102 m	1.036 m	-5.704 m
Standard deviation (metres)	0.706 m	1.391 m	2.898 m	3.731 m	3.683 m
RMSE (metres)	0.709 m	1.417 m	3.100 m	3.872 m	6.789 m
Skewness	0.793	0.919	-1.587	1.198	-0.503
Kurtosis	3.600	4.759	2.841	3.325	2.294

Table 26 - Error statistics of the (Copernicus DEM GLO-90 - GEDI) study, comparison with previous results using ICESat-1 and ICESat-2 as vertical references.

Copernicus DEM GLO-90 - Comparison with ICESat-1, ICESat-2 and GEDI (LE95)

LIDAR footprint diameters

Figure 73 - Error histogram of the (Copernicus DEM GLO-90 - GEDI) study, comparison with previous results using ICESat-1 and ICESat-2 as vertical references.

The histogram and the statistics show better results using GEDI lowest mode than using GEDI highest return as a vertical reference. As a consequence, Copernicus DEM GLO-90 heights are closer to GEDI lowest mode (ground return) than to GEDI highest return (top of canopy return). Here, a difference of a few metres (algebraic mean difference of 6.740 m) can be observed between the modes of the Copernicus DEM GLO-90 – GEDI lowest mode and the Copernicus DEM GLO-90 – GEDI highest return modes. This difference is linked to the GEDI02_A product, for which every valid acquisition has a different lowest mode and highest return elevations (see section 4.4.3.1.2 for further details). Considering ICESat-1 reference data still gives the best results, retrieving a mean, standard deviation and RMSE of respectively 0.066 metres, 0.706 metres and 0.709 metres. Considering GEDI highest return reference data gives the worst results for both mean height error and RMSE, respectively reaching - 5.704 metres and 6.789 metres. The worst standard deviation is obtained using GEDI lowest mode as reference data, reaching 3.731 metres.

4.5 Spatial distribution of height errors – Qualitative and quantitative assessments

This section provides the spatial distribution Copernicus DEM EEA-10, GLO-30 and GLO-90 height errors. These height errors are computed with regard to ICESat-1, ICESat-2 and GEDI LiDARs reference data (see sections 4.2, 4.3 and 4.4).

4.5.1 Methodology

4.5.1.1 Selection of input data

Reference LiDAR data should be filtered in order to assess Copernicus DEMs. Hereafter, the different filtering conditions are discussed, as well as their effects on the spatial distribution of errors.

4.5.1.1.1 ICESat-1

The following flags have been used to filter ICESat-1 data.

Flag	Validity condition
elev_use_flg	= 0
sat_corr_flg	< 2
elv_cloud_flg	= 0

Table 27 - Filtering of ICESat-1 data

Further information concerning the correction of ICESat-1 data are available in section 4.2.3.1.2.

4.5.1.1.2 ICESat-2

The following flags have been used to filter ICESat-2 data.

Flag	Validity condition
n_te_photons	> 100
h_te_uncertainty	< 7.5 m

Table 28 - Filtering of ICESat-2 data.

Additionally, when canopy is present (canopy_flg = 1), only cases when both canopy and terrain data are valid are considered (see section 4.3.3.1.3 for further information). Only strong beams are considered.

4.5.1.1.3 GEDI

The following flags have been used to filter GEDI data (as described in section 4.4.3.1.2).

Flag	Validity condition
quality_flg	= 1
degrade_flg	= 0

Table 29 - Filtering of GEDI data.

4.5.1.2 Aggregation of lidar measurements

Copernicus DEM heights are compared to reference data from LiDARs. As these comparisons are punctual, errors need to be spatially aggregated in order to produce maps of their spatial distribution. This section provides the methodology used to aggregate these measurements.

4.5.1.2.1 Density

The following diagram illustrates the computation of the density map.

Figure 74 - Computation of the density $d(l,p)$.

Considering a pixel of coordinates (l,p) , the density $d(l,p)$ is the number of dh_i values within a neighbourhood disk centred on (l,p) , divided by the surface of this disk. The disk used in the study has a **radius of one (1) degree**. The ground sampling distance (GSD) of the computed image is **1/100 degree** leading to images of 3665 lines x 5545 columns for Europe and 12000 lines x 36000 columns for the world (latitudes being bounded in $[-60^\circ; +60^\circ]$).

4.5.1.2.2 Error sum

The following diagram illustrates the computation of the error sum map.

Figure 75 - Computation of the error sum $s(l,p)$.

Considering a pixel of coordinates (l,p) , the error sum $s(l,p)$ is the arithmetic sum of (dh_i) within a neighbourhood disk centred on (l,p) , divided by the surface of this disk.

4.5.1.2.3 Normalised errors

The computation of the normalised errors map is expressed by the following equation:

$$e(l,p) = s(l,p)/d(l,p) \quad (\text{eq. 9})$$

Where:

- $e(l,p)$ is the normalised error of pixel (l,p) ,
- $s(l,p)$ is the error sum of pixel (l,p) ,
- $d(l,p)$ is the density of pixel (l,p) .

4.5.2 Results

The following subsections give pixel statistics, histograms and overviews of the density, error sum and normalised error maps. These statistics and histograms are available both unfiltered (RAW) and considering a linear error at 95% threshold (LE95).

4.5.2.1 Copernicus DEM EEA-10 - ICESat-1

	RAW			LE95		
	d(l,p)	s(l,p)	e(l,p)	d(l,p)	s(l,p)	e(l,p)
Number of pixels	20 322 425	20 322 425	20 322 425	20 322 425	20 322 425	20 322 425
Computed pixels	11 517 443	11 517 443	11 517 443	11 514 092	11 514 092	11 514 092
Computed pixels (%)	56.67	56.67	56.67	56.66	56.66	56.66
Arithmetic mean	1605.758	943.829	0.491	1525.642	421.564	0.256
Standard deviation	1428.821	2334.983	2.039	1373.798	789.715	0.422
Min	0.318	-35426.293	-171.469	0.318	-959.246	-5.290
Max	10846.091	9663.461	69.281	10841.953	5016.596	5.488

Figure 76 - Copernicus DEM EEA-10 – ICESat-1 spatial distribution maps of occurrences (d), sum (s), mean error (e) statistics (RAW left, LE95 right).

4.5.2.2 Copernicus DEM EEA-10 - ICESat-2 terrain

	RAW			LE95		
	d(l,p)	s(l,p)	e(l,p)	d(l,p)	s(l,p)	e(l,p)
Number of pixels	20 322 425	20 322 425	20 322 425	20 322 425	20 322 425	20 322 425
Computed pixels	11 650 035	11 650 035	11 650 035	11 648 713	11 648 713	11 648 713
Computed pixels (%)	57.33	57.33	57.33	57.32	57.32	57.32
Arithmetic mean	353.682	503.625	1.796	335.997	282.707	1.016
Standard deviation	357.817	606.552	1.669	357.407	408.106	0.876
Min	0.318	-750.890	-33.069	0.318	-537.886	-5.772
Max	2454.488	3582.222	30.349	2453.533	2721.412	8.394

Figure 77 - Copernicus DEM EEA-10 – ICESat-2 terrain spatial distribution maps and statistics (RAW left, LE95 right).

4.5.2.1 Copernicus DEM EEA-10 - ICESat-2 terrain with canopy

	RAW			LE95		
	d(l,p)	s(l,p)	e(l,p)	d(l,p)	s(l,p)	e(l,p)
Number of pixels	20 322 425	20 322 425	20 322 425	20 322 425	20 322 425	20 322 425
Computed pixels	11 650 674	11 650 674	11 650 674	11 642 341	11 642 341	11 642 341
Computed pixels (%)	57.33	57.33	57.33	57.29	57.29	57.29
Arithmetic mean	353.682	-2236.827	-7.571	336.197	-1849.684	-6.616
Standard deviation	357.817	1936.339	3.258	357.185	1726.309	2.699
Min	0.318	-12022.155	-52.253	0.318	-11166.078	-16.638
Max	2454.488	113.760	29.377	2452.578	110.105	7.501

Figure 78 - Copernicus DEM EEA-10 – ICESat-2 terrain with canopy spatial distribution maps and statistics (RAW left, LE95 right).

4.5.2.2 Copernicus DEM EEA-10 – GEDI lowest mode

	RAW			LE95		
	d(l,p)	s(l,p)	e(l,p)	d(l,p)	s(l,p)	e(l,p)
Number of pixels	20 322 425	20 322 425	20 322 425	20 322 425	20 322 425	20 322 425
Computed pixels	6 413 715	6 413 715	6 413 715	6 413 648	6 413 648	6 413 648
Computed pixels (%)	31.56	31.56	31.56	31.56	31.56	31.56
Arithmetic mean	17135.168	43080.819	2.167	16265.956	37085.520	2.006
Standard deviation	15958.668	84910.091	4.137	14912.694	49571.790	1.610
Min	0.318	-478059.125	-310.314	0.318	-13352.455	-18.145
Max	95984.117	620010.625	43.121	87969.711	337366.813	18.025

Figure 79 - Copernicus DEM EEA-10 – GEDI lowest mode spatial distribution maps and statistics (RAW left, LE95 right).

4.5.2.3 Copernicus DEM EEA-10 – GEDI highest return

	RAW			LE95		
	d(l,p)	s(l,p)	e(l,p)	d(l,p)	s(l,p)	e(l,p)
Number of pixels	20 322 425	20 322 425	20 322 425	20 322 425	20 322 425	20 322 425
Computed pixels	6 413 903	6 413 903	6 413 903	6 413 709	6 413 709	6 413 709
Computed pixels (%)	31.56	31.56	31.56	31.56	31.56	31.56
Arithmetic mean	17135.176	-146607.714	-8.501	16264.123	-112426.340	-7.064
Standard deviation	15958.664	153327.734	4.047	15117.486	101196.244	1.198
Min	0.318	-1107262.625	-350.685	0.318	-639847.125	-17.608
Max	95982.523	35.406	25.064	90242.445	9.850	13.001

Figure 80 - Copernicus DEM EEA-10 – GEDI highest return spatial distribution maps and statistics (RAW left, LE95 right).

4.5.2.1 Copernicus DEM GLO-30 - ICESat-1

	RAW			LE95		
	d(l,p)	s(l,p)	e(l,p)	d(l,p)	s(l,p)	e(l,p)
Number of pixels	432 000 000	432 000 000	432 000 000	432 000 000	432 000 000	432 000 000
Computed pixels	149 494 779	149 494 779	149 494 779	149 190 594	149 190 594	149 190 594
Computed pixels (%)	34.61	34.61	34.61	34.53	34.53	34.53
Arithmetic mean	4174.333	1150.417	0.653	3973.634	132.675	0.150
Standard deviation	4466.457	3420.088	1.772	4477.157	1489.832	0.341
Min	0.318	-35444.223	-723.918	0.318	-16217.638	-2.695
Max	23516.098	50650.211	140.459	23418.059	14326.249	2.713

Figure 81 - Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – ICESat-1 spatial distribution maps and statistics (RAW left, LE95 right).

4.5.2.2 Copernicus DEM GLO-30 - ICESat-2 terrain only

	RAW			LE95		
	d(l,p)	s(l,p)	e(l,p)	d(l,p)	s(l,p)	e(l,p)
Number of pixels	432 000 000	432 000 000	432 000 000	432 000 000	432 000 000	432 000 000
Computed pixels	152 433 728	152 433 728	152 433 728	151 673 311	151 673 311	151 673 311
Computed pixels (%)	35.29	35.29	35.29	35.11	35.11	35.11
Arithmetic mean	953.638	623.204	2.336	910.523	177.745	0.779
Standard deviation	1175.479	1327.260	3.411	1189.769	482.129	0.855
Min	0.318	-5549.642	-80.033	0.318	-3241.673	-4.974
Max	4614.220	11661.858	108.630	4611.674	3818.265	5.009

Figure 82 - Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – ICESat-2 terrain only spatial distribution maps and statistics (RAW left, LE95 right).

4.5.2.1 Copernicus DEM GLO-30 - ICESat-2 terrain with canopy

	RAW			LE95		
	d(l,p)	s(l,p)	e(l,p)	d(l,p)	s(l,p)	e(l,p)
Number of pixels	432 000 000	432 000 000	432 000 000	432 000 000	432 000 000	432 000 000
Computed pixels	152 439 759	152 439 759	152 439 759	151 759 064	151 759 064	151 759 064
Computed pixels (%)	35.29	35.29	35.29	35.13	35.13	35.13
Arithmetic mean	953.638	-1690.806	-5.330	910.066	-1021.885	-3.826
Standard deviation	1175.479	2378.058	4.257	1189.135	1469.028	2.856
Min	0.318	-19670.293	-91.945	0.318	-15563.233	-11.005
Max	4614.220	4486.309	101.457	4614.220	2358.522	10.527

Figure 83 - Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – ICESat-2 terrain with canopy spatial distribution maps and statistics (RAW left, LE95 right).

4.5.2.1 Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – GEDI lowest mode

	RAW			LE95		
	d(l,p)	s(l,p)	e(l,p)	d(l,p)	s(l,p)	e(l,p)
Number of pixels	432 000 000	432 000 000	432 000 000	432 000 000	432 000 000	432 000 000
Computed pixels	122 017 821	122 017 821	122 017 821	122 022 742	122 022 742	122 022 742
Computed pixels (%)	28.24	28.24	28.24	28.25	28.25	28.25
Arithmetic mean	17118.791	31004.952	2.523	16244.529	17229.059	1.822
Standard deviation	14807.744	71328.344	7.003	14598.671	38556.850	2.540
Min	0.318	-478685.719	-621.974	0.318	-54911.551	-14.758
Max	130918.945	834304.938	111.544	130917.039	451862.719	15.005

Figure 84 - Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – GEDI lowest mode spatial distribution maps and statistics (RAW left, LE95 right).

4.5.2.1 Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – GEDI highest return

	RAW			LE95		
	d(l,p)	s(l,p)	e(l,p)	d(l,p)	s(l,p)	e(l,p)
Number of pixels	432 000 000	432 000 000	432 000 000	432 000 000	432 000 000	432 000 000
Computed pixels	122 110 137	122 110 137	122 110 137	122 008 589	122 008 589	122 008 589
Computed pixels (%)	28.27	28.27	28.27	28.24	28.24	28.24
Arithmetic mean	17099.390	-116073.742	-7.726	16258.941	-94772.645	-6.324
Standard deviation	14799.303	104953.888	6.655	14431.327	83083.659	1.838
Min	0.318	-1160637.250	-643.777	0.318	-775852.375	-15.769
Max	130923.406	1585.894	73.734	130761.703	250.190	14.812

Figure 85 - Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – GEDI highest return spatial distribution maps and statistics (RAW left, LE95 right).

4.5.2.2 Copernicus DEM GLO-90 - ICESat-1

	RAW			LE95		
	d(l,p)	s(l,p)	e(l,p)	d(l,p)	s(l,p)	e(l,p)
Number of pixels	432 000 000	432 000 000	432 000 000	432 000 000	432 000 000	432 000 000
Computed pixels	150 469 220	150 469 220	150 469 220	150 108 645	150 108 645	150 108 645
Computed pixels (%)	34.83	34.83	34.83	34.75	34.75	34.75
Arithmetic mean	4154.031	1154.667	0.646	3955.421	261.343	0.209
Standard deviation	4468.004	3442.533	1.823	4473.595	1562.458	0.383
Min	0.318	-35831.418	-723.406	0.318	-16210.236	-3.014
Max	23549.201	51194.266	133.296	23495.727	15679.385	3.015

Figure 86 - Copernicus DEM GLO-90 – ICESat-1 spatial distribution maps and statistics (RAW left, LE95 right).

4.5.2.3 Copernicus DEM GLO-90 - ICESat-2 terrain only

	RAW			LE95		
	d(l,p)	s(l,p)	e(l,p)	d(l,p)	s(l,p)	e(l,p)
Number of pixels	432 000 000	432 000 000	432 000 000	432 000 000	432 000 000	432 000 000
Computed pixels	153 363 454	153 363 454	153 363 454	152 652 690	152 652 690	152 652 690
Computed pixels (%)	35.50	35.50	35.50	35.34	35.34	35.34
Arithmetic mean	949.664	658.399	2.544	906.346	245.184	1.014
Standard deviation	1175.645	1322.300	3.634	1182.918	537.674	1.101
Min	0.318	-5341.918	-92.011	0.318	-3243.571	-6.246
Max	4623.133	11612.711	109.451	4617.722	3979.452	6.248

Figure 87 - Copernicus DEM GLO-90 – ICESat-2 terrain only spatial distribution maps and statistics (RAW left, LE95 right).

4.5.2.4 Copernicus DEM GLO-90 - ICESat-2 terrain with canopy

	RAW			LE95		
	d(l,p)	s(l,p)	e(l,p)	d(l,p)	s(l,p)	e(l,p)
Number of pixels	432 000 000	432 000 000	432 000 000	432 000 000	432 000 000	432 000 000
Computed pixels	153 368 719	153 368 719	153 368 719	152 854 677	152 854 677	152 854 677
Computed pixels (%)	35.50	35.50	35.50	35.38	35.38	35.38
Arithmetic mean	949.664	-1659.081	-5.169	905.201	-997.674	-3.728
Standard deviation	1175.645	2403.705	4.149	1187.462	1491.097	2.856
Min	0.318	-19778.002	-101.110	0.318	-16041.577	-11.307
Max	4623.133	4557.451	102.278	4620.905	2419.258	11.072

Figure 88 - Copernicus DEM GLO-90 – ICESat-2 terrain with canopy spatial distribution maps and statistics (RAW left, LE95 right).

4.5.2.5 Copernicus DEM GLO-90 – GEDI lowest mode

	RAW			LE95		
	d(l,p)	s(l,p)	e(l,p)	d(l,p)	s(l,p)	e(l,p)
Number of pixels	432 000 000	432 000 000	432 000 000	432 000 000	432 000 000	432 000 000
Computed pixels	122 073 745	122 073 745	122 073 745	122 047 694	122 047 694	122 047 694
Computed pixels (%)	28.26	28.26	28.26	28.25	28.25	28.25
Arithmetic mean	17098.584	30793.730	2.489	16236.062	17315.317	1.762
Standard deviation	14794.485	71070.689	6.984	14591.491	39207.767	2.510
Min	0.318	-479666.000	-621.020	0.318	-55219.539	-15.532
Max	130900.164	824003.500	81.507	130877.563	496234.125	15.519

Figure 89 - Copernicus DEM GLO-90 – GEDI lowest mode spatial distribution maps and statistics (RAW left, LE95 right).

4.5.2.6 Copernicus DEM GLO-90 – GEDI highest return

	RAW			LE95		
	d(l,p)	s(l,p)	e(l,p)	d(l,p)	s(l,p)	e(l,p)
Number of pixels	432 000 000	432 000 000	432 000 000	432 000 000	432 000 000	432 000 000
Computed pixels	122 082 506	122 082 506	122 082 506	122 019 276	122 019 276	122 019 276
Computed pixels (%)	28.26	28.26	28.26	28.25	28.25	28.25
Arithmetic mean	17098.585	-116195.804	-7.750	16248.990	-93161.463	-6.159
Standard deviation	14794.484	105026.424	6.658	14438.627	82687.336	1.787
Min	0.318	-1164344.125	-642.793	0.318	-763237.313	-17.185
Max	130899.852	1464.510	59.302	130741.969	568.342	16.692

Figure 90 - Copernicus DEM GLO-90 – GEDI highest return spatial distribution maps and statistics (RAW left, LE95 right).

4.5.3 Sources of elevation errors

4.5.3.1 Canopy

In Figure 91, the effect of canopy over (GLO-30 – ICESat-2 terrain only) and (GLO-30 – ICESat-2 terrain with canopy) is analysed over the Congolian rainforest.

Figure 91 - (Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – ICESat-2) height errors linked to canopy - Congolian rainforest.

One may note the area covered by Tree cover, broadleaved, evergreen, closed to open (>15%) class of the C3S-LC map coincides with the areas of most important errors of (GLO-30 – ICESat-2 terrain only) and (GLO-30 – ICESat-2 terrain with canopy). As positive errors are observable considering ICESat-2 terrain only, and as negative errors are observable considering ICESat-2 terrain with canopy, Copernicus DEM heights seem to be generated within the canopy.

In Figure 92, the effect of canopy over (EEA-30 – ICESat-1) is analysed over Norway, Sweden and Finland.

Figure 92 - (Copernicus DEM EEA-10 – ICESat-1) height errors linked to canopy – Norway, Sweden and Finland.

One may note the area covered by Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, closed to open (>15%) class of the C3S-LC map coincides with the areas of most important errors of (EEA-10 – ICESat-1). In these areas, Copernicus DEM is slightly higher than ICESat-1 surface elevations.

In Figure 93, the effect of canopy over (GLO-90 – GEDI lowest mode) and (GLO-90 – GEDI highest return) is analysed over the Amazon rainforest

Figure 93 - (Copernicus DEM GLO-90 – GEDI) height errors linked to canopy – Amazon rainforest.

One may note the area covered by Tree cover, broadleaved, evergreen, closed to open (>15%) class of the C3S-LC map coincides with the areas of most important errors of (GLO-90 – GEDI lowest mode) and (GLO-90 – GEDI highest return). As positive errors are observable considering GEDI lowest mode, and as negative errors are observable considering GEDI highest return, Copernicus DEM heights seem to be generated within the canopy.

4.5.3.2 LiDAR bad acquisitions

In Figure 94, singularities among the (EEA-10 – ICESat-1) qualitative assessment are studied.

Figure 94 - (Copernicus DEM EEA-10 – ICESat-1) height errors linked to clouds – France.

In this case, an error singularity is visible on the (EEA-10 – ICESat-1 RAW) error map. The negative errors are due to clouds obstructing ICESat-1 beam during acquisition. As a consequence, ICESat-1 elevations are erroneously high in this area. In the 3D view, one may note the difference of height between acquisitions over clouds and cloudless acquisitions over the Pyrenees. The background EEA-10 DEM highlights topographic changes near the Pyrenees, but not at ICESat-1 cloud acquisitions location.

In Figure 95, singularities among the (GLO-30 – ICESat-2 terrain only) qualitative assessment are studied.

Figure 95 - (Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – ICESat-2 terrain only) height errors linked to bad acquisitions – Global analysis.

In this case, areas of negative errors, coloured in blue, are clearly visible on the error map. These areas are linearly shaped, highlighting the orbit of ICESat-2. As a consequence, these errors must derive from ICESat-2 reference data. As these errors are negative, some of the ICESat-2 acquisitions may have been impacted by clouds, as illustrated in the preceding example.

4.6 Land use / land cover vs. DEM height errors – Quantitative assessment

This study is an extension to the previous quantitative assessments, in which Copernicus DEMs are compared to ICESat-1, ICESat-2 and GEDI reference data. The goal of this section is to find links between the (Copernicus DEM – LiDAR) height differences and the land use / land cover.

4.6.1 Methodology

This section aims to describe the methods used to classify Copernicus DEM height errors according to the land use / land cover. The first subsection (see 4.6.1.1) focuses on the source data used for this assessment, whereas the second subsection focuses on the methods used to compute Copernicus DEM height error statistics according to a land use / land cover classification.

4.6.1.1 Source data

4.6.1.1.1 DEM filtering

The Copernicus DEM pixels have been filtered considering the WBM, FLM and EDM layers. The filtering used does not differ from previous quantitative assessments (see section 4.2.4.2.4 for further information).

4.6.1.1.2 LiDAR filtering

Only valid LiDAR reference data is considered in order to assess Copernicus DEMs. The filtering of LiDAR data does not differ from previous quantitative assessments (see sections 4.2.3.1.2, 4.3.3.1.3 and 4.4.3.1.2 for further information).

4.6.1.1.3 Land use / land cover data

Classification of the errors relies on the C3S-LC classification map. The 2013 version of this map has been chosen for this study (as illustrated in Figure 96), as it roughly corresponds to the middle of TanDEM-X acquisitions used to generate Copernicus DEMs (2010-2015).

Figure 96 - Overview of the C3S-LC 2013 classification map.

The C3S-LC classification is divided into global and regional levels. Figure 96 is an overview of the global level classes. Regional level classes are a subdivision of the global level classes, giving more precise information about the land use and land cover when available.

The following table covers the full C3S-LC classification (including global and regional levels).

DN	Type	Class	Colour
0	Global	No Data	
10	Global	Cropland, rainfed	
11	Regional	Cropland, rainfed, herbaceous cover	
12	Regional	Cropland, rainfed, tree or shrub cover	
20	Global	Cropland, irrigated or post-flooding	
30	Global	Mosaic cropland (>50%) / natural vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (<50%)	
40	Global	Mosaic natural vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (>50%) / cropland (<50%)	
50	Global	Tree cover, broadleaved, evergreen, closed to open (>15%)	
60	Global	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%)	
61	Regional	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, closed (>40%)	
62	Regional	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, open (15-40%)	
70	Global	Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, closed to open (>15%)	
71	Regional	Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, closed (>40%)	
72	Regional	Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, open (15-40%)	
80	Global	Tree cover, needleleaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%)	
81	Regional	Tree cover, needleleaved, deciduous, closed (>40%)	
82	Regional	Tree cover, needleleaved, deciduous, open (15-40%)	
90	Global	Tree cover, mixed leaf type (broadleaved and needleleaved)	
100	Global	Mosaic tree and shrub (>50%) / herbaceous cover (<50%)	
110	Global	Mosaic herbaceous cover (>50%) / tree and shrub (<50%)	
120	Global	Shrubland	
121	Regional	Evergreen shrubland	
122	Regional	Deciduous shrubland	
130	Global	Grassland	
140	Global	Lichens and mosses	
150	Global	Sparse vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (<15%)	
151	Regional	Sparse tree (<15%)	
152	Regional	Sparse shrub (<15%)	
153	Regional	Sparse herbaceous cover (<15%)	
160	Global	Tree cover, flooded, fresh or brackish water	
170	Global	Tree cover, flooded, saline water	
180	Global	Shrub or herbaceous cover, flooded, fresh/saline/brackish water	
190	Global	Urban areas	
200	Global	Bare areas	
201	Regional	Consolidated bare areas	
202	Regional	Unconsolidated bare areas	
210	Global	Water bodies	
220	Global	Permanent snow and ice	

Table 30 – CCI-LC / C3S-LC full classification.

4.6.1.2 Statistics computation

The computation of the height difference between Copernicus DEMs and LiDAR reference data is detailed in previous quantitative assessment (see sections 4.2.4 for ICESat-1, 4.3.4 for ICESat-2 and 4.4.4 for GEDI).

A land use land cover class of the C3S-LC map is retrieved at each (DEM – LiDAR) comparison point. Then, statistics and histograms are computed per C3S-LC class.

When no samples have been found for a class, or when the count is too small, no statistics are computed for this class.

4.6.2 Results

Results are detailed for each (DEM – LiDAR) comparison in the following subsections. One may see three different figures per study, respectively corresponding to:

- **Per class statistics (table)** – For each class of the C3S-LC, height difference statistics are computed (including the count, mean, standard deviation, RMSE, min and max height differences)
- **Per class histograms** – The distribution of height differences is given in separated histograms for each class. The vertical scale of these histograms is in percentage, relative to the total amount of differences computed in all classes.
- **Summary histogram (board)** – The summary histogram includes all the “per class histograms”, highlighting the majority classes. This histogram is completed by a view of the C3S-LC 2013 map as well as a spatial distribution of errors map.

Only summary histograms are commented, as they highlight the most significant classes of each assessment.

4.6.2.1 Copernicus DEM EEA-10 – ICESat-1

DN	Class	Count	Mean	Std Dev	RMSE	Min	Max
0	No Data	-	-	-	-	-	-
10	Cropland, rainfed	235 217	0.131 m	1.128 m	1.136 m	-5.917 m	5.923 m
11	Cropland, rainfed, herbaceous cover	552 409	0.010 m	0.871 m	0.871 m	-5.920 m	5.924 m
12	Cropland, rainfed, tree or shrub cover	41 690	0.073 m	0.917 m	0.920 m	-5.885 m	5.915 m
20	Cropland, irrigated or post-flooding	84 120	-0.001 m	0.674 m	0.674 m	-5.919 m	5.910 m
30	Mosaic cropland (>50%) / natural vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (<50%)	72 818	0.334 m	1.460 m	1.498 m	-5.924 m	5.924 m
40	Mosaic natural vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (>50%) / cropland (<50%)	24 487	0.249 m	1.421 m	1.443 m	-5.911 m	5.918 m
50	Tree cover, broadleaved, evergreen, closed to open (>15%)	619	0.899 m	2.215 m	2.390 m	-5.908 m	5.906 m
60	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%)	41 464	0.999 m	2.084 m	2.311 m	-5.907 m	5.923 m
61	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, closed (>40%)	126	1.839 m	1.722 m	2.519 m	-2.701 m	5.861 m
62	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, open (15-40%)	-	-	-	-	-	-
70	Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, closed to open (>15%)	229 054	1.316 m	1.957 m	2.358 m	-5.922 m	5.924 m
71	Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, closed (>40%)	-	-	-	-	-	-
72	Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, open (15-40%)	-	-	-	-	-	-
80	Tree cover, needleleaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%)	50	0.206 m	1.890 m	1.901 m	-3.985 m	4.494 m
81	Tree cover, needleleaved, deciduous, closed (>40%)	-	-	-	-	-	-
82	Tree cover, needleleaved, deciduous, open (15-40%)	-	-	-	-	-	-
90	Tree cover, mixed leaf type (broadleaved and needleleaved)	25 145	1.484 m	2.193 m	2.648 m	-5.919 m	5.924 m
100	Mosaic tree and shrub (>50%) / herbaceous cover (<50%)	55 715	0.533 m	1.765 m	1.844 m	-5.923 m	5.923 m
110	Mosaic herbaceous cover (>50%) / tree and shrub (<50%)	27 855	-0.294 m	1.243 m	1.277 m	-5.894 m	5.907 m
120	Shrubland	4 003	-0.029 m	1.410 m	1.411 m	-5.843 m	5.920 m
121	Evergreen shrubland	-	-	-	-	-	-
122	Deciduous shrubland	2 282	-0.174 m	1.022 m	1.037 m	-5.093 m	5.296 m
130	Grassland	170 985	0.085 m	1.139 m	1.142 m	-5.867 m	5.923 m
140	Lichens and mosses	4 587	-0.289 m	0.936 m	0.980 m	-5.663 m	5.442 m
150	Sparse vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (<15%)	36 158	-0.307 m	1.276 m	1.313 m	-5.922 m	5.923 m
151	Sparse tree (<15%)	-	-	-	-	-	-
152	Sparse shrub (<15%)	878	0.164 m	1.401 m	1.411 m	-5.457 m	5.870 m
153	Sparse herbaceous cover (<15%)	2 909	-0.074 m	0.745 m	0.749 m	-5.766 m	5.920 m
160	Tree cover, flooded, fresh or brackish water	38	1.208 m	2.162 m	2.476 m	-1.795 m	5.919 m
170	Tree cover, flooded, saline water	160	1.672 m	1.704 m	2.387 m	-4.396 m	5.385 m
180	Shrub or herbaceous cover, flooded, fresh/saline/brackish water	92 622	0.126 m	1.113 m	1.121 m	-5.842 m	5.922 m
190	Urban areas	44 445	0.189 m	1.579 m	1.591 m	-5.914 m	5.923 m
200	Bare areas	18 659	-0.262 m	1.216 m	1.244 m	-5.806 m	5.893 m
201	Consolidated bare areas	224	-0.150 m	1.891 m	1.897 m	-5.659 m	5.411 m
202	Unconsolidated bare areas	122	-0.087 m	1.393 m	1.395 m	-5.282 m	4.504 m
210	Water bodies	30 276	0.190 m	1.556 m	1.568 m	-5.924 m	5.923 m
220	Permanent snow and ice	4 434	-2.002 m	2.829 m	3.466 m	-5.923 m	5.903 m
All	Total	1 803 551	0.270 m	1.389 m	1.415 m	-5.924 m	5.924 m

Table 31 – (Copernicus DEM EEA-10 – ICESat-1 LE95) error statistics - classified with C3S-LC 2013.

Figure 97 - (Copernicus DEM EEA-10 – ICESat-1 LE95) error histograms - classified with C3S-LC 2013.

C3S-LC 2013

EEA-10 – ICESat-1

	Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, closed to open (>15%)
	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%)
	Cropland, rainfed
	Shrubland
	Grassland

[See map and full legend on VtWeb](#)

	<= -9 metres
	-9 metres to -3 metres
	-3 metres to -1.5 metres
	-1.5 metres to -0.5 metres
	-0.5 metres to 0.5 metres
	0.5 metres to 1.5 metres
	1.5 metres to 3 metres
	3 metres to 9 metres
	>= 9 metres

Figure 98 - (Copernicus DEM EEA-10 – ICESat-1 LE95) errors histogram - classified with C3S-LC 2013.

Tree cover, and in particular “needleleaved evergreen” (70) that are in majority in Europe (in particular in Scandinavia), shows a long tail of distribution of positive values leading to a high standard deviation (1.957m). This rightward skewness illustrates that Copernicus DEM EEA-10 is above the ICESat-1 LiDAR data for this class.

4.6.2.2 Copernicus DEM EEA-10 – ICESat-2 terrain only

DN	Class	Count	Mean	Std Dev	RMSE	Min	Max
0	No Data	-	-	-	-	-	-
10	Cropland, rainfed	43 952	0.444 m	1.449 m	1.516 m	-8.350 m	8.410 m
11	Cropland, rainfed, herbaceous cover	76 797	0.241 m	1.170 m	1.194 m	-8.360 m	8.390 m
12	Cropland, rainfed, tree or shrub cover	18 714	0.459 m	1.006 m	1.106 m	-8.050 m	8.330 m
20	Cropland, irrigated or post-flooding	17 238	0.068 m	0.884 m	0.887 m	-7.900 m	8.310 m
30	Mosaic cropland (>50%) / natural vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (<50%)	15 043	0.869 m	1.751 m	1.954 m	-8.220 m	8.410 m
40	Mosaic natural vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (>50%) / cropland (<50%)	12 442	0.651 m	1.532 m	1.664 m	-8.110 m	8.380 m
50	Tree cover, broadleaved, evergreen, closed to open (>15%)	96	1.716 m	2.086 m	2.701 m	-2.850 m	8.120 m
60	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%)	16 385	1.564 m	2.296 m	2.778 m	-6.710 m	8.410 m
61	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, closed (>40%)	32	3.041 m	2.075 m	3.681 m	-0.490 m	7.450 m
62	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, open (15-40%)	-	-	-	-	-	-
70	Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, closed to open (>15%)	67 740	2.522 m	2.311 m	3.421 m	-8.370 m	8.410 m
71	Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, closed (>40%)	-	-	-	-	-	-
72	Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, open (15-40%)	-	-	-	-	-	-
80	Tree cover, needleleaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%)	21	0.507 m	2.692 m	2.739 m	-5.620 m	5.180 m
81	Tree cover, needleleaved, deciduous, closed (>40%)	-	-	-	-	-	-
82	Tree cover, needleleaved, deciduous, open (15-40%)	-	-	-	-	-	-
90	Tree cover, mixed leaf type (broadleaved and needleleaved)	6 918	2.724 m	2.496 m	3.695 m	-8.200 m	8.420 m
100	Mosaic tree and shrub (>50%) / herbaceous cover (<50%)	19 458	0.971 m	1.892 m	2.127 m	-8.160 m	8.410 m
110	Mosaic herbaceous cover (>50%) / tree and shrub (<50%)	9 783	-0.310 m	1.456 m	1.489 m	-8.380 m	8.390 m
120	Shrubland	4 505	0.332 m	1.248 m	1.291 m	-5.910 m	8.210 m
121	Evergreen shrubland	-	-	-	-	-	-
122	Deciduous shrubland	615	-0.143 m	1.280 m	1.288 m	-4.680 m	7.570 m
130	Grassland	27 310	0.332 m	1.602 m	1.636 m	-8.350 m	8.400 m
140	Lichens and mosses	925	-0.261 m	1.456 m	1.479 m	-8.240 m	6.460 m
150	Sparse vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (<15%)	20 758	-0.438 m	1.503 m	1.565 m	-8.350 m	8.300 m
151	Sparse tree (<15%)	-	-	-	-	-	-
152	Sparse shrub (<15%)	250	0.608 m	1.718 m	1.822 m	-4.480 m	8.220 m
153	Sparse herbaceous cover (<15%)	1 327	-0.045 m	0.836 m	0.837 m	-5.030 m	6.860 m
160	Tree cover, flooded, fresh or brackish water	6	0.940 m	1.356 m	1.650 m	-0.360 m	3.300 m
170	Tree cover, flooded, saline water	25	1.825 m	2.199 m	2.858 m	-0.740 m	7.390 m
180	Shrub or herbaceous cover, flooded, fresh/saline/brackish water	9 511	0.783 m	1.592 m	1.774 m	-4.860 m	8.410 m
190	Urban areas	16 947	1.102 m	1.966 m	2.254 m	-8.390 m	8.420 m
200	Bare areas	8 909	-0.407 m	1.722 m	1.769 m	-8.300 m	8.400 m
201	Consolidated bare areas	365	-1.031 m	2.279 m	2.502 m	-7.800 m	7.950 m
202	Unconsolidated bare areas	41	0.901 m	1.630 m	1.863 m	-1.220 m	4.880 m
210	Water bodies	2 215	1.212 m	2.298 m	2.598 m	-8.160 m	8.410 m
220	Permanent snow and ice	851	-0.293 m	3.975 m	3.986 m	-8.380 m	8.410 m
All	Total	399 179	0.822 m	1.944 m	2.111 m	-8.390 m	8.420 m

Table 32 – (Copernicus DEM EEA-10 – ICESat-2 terrain only LE95) error statistics - classified with C3S-LC 2013.

Figure 99 - (Copernicus DEM EEA-10 – ICESat-2 terrain only LE95) errors classified with C3S-LC 2013.

C3S-LC 2013

EEA-10 – ICESat-2 terrain only

	Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, closed to open (>15%)
	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%)
	Cropland, rainfed
	Shrubland
	Grassland

[See map and full legend on VtWeb](#)

	<= -9 metres
	-9 metres to -3 metres
	-3 metres to -1.5 metres
	-1.5 metres to -0.5 metres
	-0.5 metres to 0.5 metres
	0.5 metres to 1.5 metres
	1.5 metres to 3 metres
	3 metres to 9 metres
	>= 9 metres

Figure 100 - (Copernicus DEM EEA-10 – ICESat-2 terrain only LE95) errors histogram - classified with C3S-LC 2013.

As observed for the (EEA-10 – ICESat-1) study (Figure 98), tree cover, and in particular “needleleaved evergreen” (70), shows a long tail of distribution of positive values leading to an even greater mean (2.522m) and standard deviation (2.311m) than the ones computed for ICESat-1 (mean of 1.316m and standard deviation of 1.957m). This rightward skewness illustrates that Copernicus DEM EEA-10 shows an even greater height above the “ICESat-2 terrain only” data for this class.

4.6.2.3 Copernicus DEM EEA-10 – ICESat-2 terrain with canopy

DN	Class	Count	Mean	Std Dev	RMSE	Min	Max
0	No Data	-	-	-	-	-	-
10	Cropland, rainfed	42 474	-4.280 m	4.707 m	6.362 m	-16.640 m	16.350 m
11	Cropland, rainfed, herbaceous cover	74 833	-3.436 m	4.436 m	5.611 m	-16.640 m	16.400 m
12	Cropland, rainfed, tree or shrub cover	18 557	-2.802 m	3.925 m	4.823 m	-16.630 m	14.400 m
20	Cropland, irrigated or post-flooding	17 127	-1.202 m	2.977 m	3.211 m	-16.640 m	14.870 m
30	Mosaic cropland (>50%) / natural vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (<50%)	14 036	-6.571 m	4.679 m	8.067 m	-16.640 m	14.860 m
40	Mosaic natural vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (>50%) / cropland (<50%)	12 169	-5.384 m	4.337 m	6.913 m	-16.640 m	14.180 m
50	Tree cover, broadleaved, evergreen, closed to open (>15%)	192	-8.420 m	4.164 m	9.393 m	-16.610 m	1.610 m
60	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%)	18 837	-6.773 m	4.324 m	8.036 m	-16.640 m	16.510 m
61	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, closed (>40%)	47	-6.900 m	6.137 m	9.235 m	-16.470 m	14.800 m
62	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, open (15-40%)	-	-	-	-	-	-
70	Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, closed to open (>15%)	72 070	-9.542 m	3.493 m	10.161 m	-16.650 m	16.360 m
71	Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, closed (>40%)	-	-	-	-	-	-
72	Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, open (15-40%)	-	-	-	-	-	-
80	Tree cover, needleleaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%)	19	-6.216 m	3.836 m	7.304 m	-15.290 m	4.9E-324
81	Tree cover, needleleaved, deciduous, closed (>40%)	-	-	-	-	-	-
82	Tree cover, needleleaved, deciduous, open (15-40%)	-	-	-	-	-	-
90	Tree cover, mixed leaf type (broadleaved and needleleaved)	8 052	-9.154 m	4.089 m	10.026 m	-16.650 m	16.490 m
100	Mosaic tree and shrub (>50%) / herbaceous cover (<50%)	18 968	-6.831 m	4.366 m	8.107 m	-16.640 m	16.500 m
110	Mosaic herbaceous cover (>50%) / tree and shrub (<50%)	9 635	-4.316 m	3.641 m	5.647 m	-16.640 m	16.240 m
120	Shrubland	4 414	-5.014 m	3.816 m	6.301 m	-16.640 m	9.400 m
121	Evergreen shrubland	-	-	-	-	-	-
122	Deciduous shrubland	612	-3.105 m	3.346 m	4.565 m	-15.680 m	4.030 m
130	Grassland	25 658	-5.558 m	4.778 m	7.330 m	-16.650 m	15.720 m
140	Lichens and mosses	918	-4.730 m	3.265 m	5.748 m	-16.570 m	2.900 m
150	Sparse vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (<15%)	20 635	-3.033 m	3.519 m	4.646 m	-16.640 m	15.900 m
151	Sparse tree (<15%)	-	-	-	-	-	-
152	Sparse shrub (<15%)	245	-6.707 m	3.975 m	7.796 m	-16.350 m	1.650 m
153	Sparse herbaceous cover (<15%)	1 327	-0.837 m	2.437 m	2.577 m	-16.510 m	9.160 m
160	Tree cover, flooded, fresh or brackish water	24	-8.403 m	2.075 m	8.656 m	-14.280 m	4.9E-324
170	Tree cover, flooded, saline water	29	-5.111 m	3.471 m	6.178 m	-12.110 m	4.000 m
180	Shrub or herbaceous cover, flooded, fresh/saline/brackish water	9 313	-6.827 m	4.061 m	7.943 m	-16.620 m	8.880 m
190	Urban areas	16 609	-6.687 m	4.224 m	7.909 m	-16.640 m	14.020 m
200	Bare areas	8 870	-3.221 m	3.930 m	5.081 m	-16.580 m	16.380 m
201	Consolidated bare areas	363	-4.501 m	3.784 m	5.881 m	-16.340 m	9.120 m
202	Unconsolidated bare areas	40	-5.149 m	4.471 m	6.820 m	-14.720 m	0.840 m
210	Water bodies	2 160	-5.549 m	5.166 m	7.582 m	-16.540 m	13.310 m
220	Permanent snow and ice	946	-3.333 m	6.748 m	7.527 m	-16.440 m	16.200 m
All	Total	399 179	-5.477 m	4.838 m	7.307 m	-16.650 m	16.510 m

Table 33 – (Copernicus DEM EEA-10 – ICESat-2 terrain with canopy LE95) error statistics - classified with C3S-LC 2013.

Figure 101 - (Copernicus DEM EEA-10 – ICESat-2 terrain with canopy LE95) errors classified with C3S-LC 2013.

C3S-LC 2013

	Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, closed to open (>15%)
	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%)
	Cropland, rainfed
	Shrubland
	Grassland

[See map and full legend on VtWeb](#)

EEA-10 – ICESat-2 terrain with canopy

	<= -9 metres
	-9 metres to -3 metres
	-3 metres to -1.5 metres
	-1.5 metres to -0.5 metres
	-0.5 metres to 0.5 metres
	0.5 metres to 1.5 metres
	1.5 metres to 3 metres
	3 metres to 9 metres
	>= 9 metres

Copernicus DEM EEA-10 - ICESat-2 terrain with canopy

Figure 102 - (Copernicus DEM EEA-10 – ICESat-2 terrain with canopy LE95) errors histogram - classified with C3S-LC 2013.

One may observe that tree cover, and in particular “needleleaved evergreen” (70) that are in majority in Europe, shows a long tail of distribution of negative values. As opposed to the rightward skewness of the (EEA-10 – ICESat-2 terrain only) histogram (see Figure 100), this leftward skewness illustrates that Copernicus DEM EEA-10 is below the ICESat-2 terrain with canopy data for this class. Other classes among this study also show important leftward skewness but with a lower leftward shift.

4.6.2.4 Copernicus DEM EEA-10 – GEDI lowest mode

DN	Class	Count	Mean	Std Dev	RMSE	Min	Max
0	No Data	-	-	-	-	-	-
10	Cropland, rainfed	1 138 116	0.768 m	3.375 m	3.461 m	-19.300 m	19.540 m
11	Cropland, rainfed, herbaceous cover	3 268 395	0.110 m	2.168 m	2.170 m	-19.450 m	19.540 m
12	Cropland, rainfed, tree or shrub cover	289 563	0.459 m	2.329 m	2.374 m	-19.310 m	19.540 m
20	Cropland, irrigated or post-flooding	230 847	-0.130 m	1.522 m	1.527 m	-19.400 m	19.490 m
30	Mosaic cropland (>50%) / natural vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (<50%)	629 749	1.668 m	4.214 m	4.532 m	-19.410 m	19.540 m
40	Mosaic natural vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (>50%) / cropland (<50%)	373 545	1.295 m	3.917 m	4.126 m	-19.460 m	19.530 m
50	Tree cover, broadleaved, evergreen, closed to open (>15%)	55 631	9.739 m	6.205 m	11.547 m	-18.620 m	19.540 m
60	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%)	982 727	7.157 m	6.505 m	9.672 m	-19.490 m	19.540 m
61	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, closed (>40%)	2 258	6.601 m	6.265 m	9.101 m	-9.570 m	19.530 m
62	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, open (15-40%)	-	-	-	-	-	-
70	Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, closed to open (>15%)	879 761	7.656 m	6.536 m	10.067 m	-19.380 m	19.540 m
71	Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, closed (>40%)	-	-	-	-	-	-
72	Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, open (15-40%)	-	-	-	-	-	-
80	Tree cover, needleleaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%)	615	1.832 m	5.063 m	5.384 m	-15.860 m	19.170 m
81	Tree cover, needleleaved, deciduous, closed (>40%)	-	-	-	-	-	-
82	Tree cover, needleleaved, deciduous, open (15-40%)	-	-	-	-	-	-
90	Tree cover, mixed leaf type (broadleaved and needleleaved)	270 693	9.023 m	6.425 m	11.077 m	-19.410 m	19.540 m
100	Mosaic tree and shrub (>50%) / herbaceous cover (<50%)	747 887	3.111 m	5.450 m	6.275 m	-19.490 m	19.540 m
110	Mosaic herbaceous cover (>50%) / tree and shrub (<50%)	42 550	2.552 m	5.106 m	5.708 m	-18.340 m	19.520 m
120	Shrubland	137 945	1.012 m	3.792 m	3.924 m	-19.030 m	19.540 m
121	Evergreen shrubland	-	-	-	-	-	-
122	Deciduous shrubland	593	0.042 m	3.320 m	3.321 m	-14.120 m	17.780 m
130	Grassland	1 294 953	0.803 m	3.511 m	3.602 m	-19.420 m	19.540 m
140	Lichens and mosses	124	2.649 m	4.589 m	5.299 m	-7.640 m	17.680 m
150	Sparse vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (<15%)	78 258	-0.345 m	3.696 m	3.712 m	-19.150 m	19.520 m
151	Sparse tree (<15%)	-	-	-	-	-	-
152	Sparse shrub (<15%)	-	-	-	-	-	-
153	Sparse herbaceous cover (<15%)	6 128	-0.218 m	3.059 m	3.067 m	-16.980 m	19.480 m
160	Tree cover, flooded, fresh or brackish water	1 619	9.996 m	5.867 m	11.591 m	-5.390 m	19.540 m
170	Tree cover, flooded, saline water	2 371	1.113 m	4.425 m	4.563 m	-10.270 m	19.480 m
180	Shrub or herbaceous cover, flooded, fresh/saline/brackish water	52 109	0.575 m	2.803 m	2.862 m	-17.260 m	19.540 m
190	Urban areas	411 505	1.308 m	2.668 m	2.971 m	-19.430 m	19.540 m
200	Bare areas	54 314	-0.168 m	3.827 m	3.830 m	-19.470 m	19.530 m
201	Consolidated bare areas	8 975	-1.151 m	5.390 m	5.512 m	-19.470 m	19.530 m
202	Unconsolidated bare areas	666	0.580 m	2.953 m	3.009 m	-5.990 m	17.570 m
210	Water bodies	29 296	1.289 m	4.141 m	4.337 m	-19.220 m	19.540 m
220	Permanent snow and ice	4 423	-1.341 m	6.027 m	6.174 m	-18.250 m	19.290 m
All	Total	10 995 616	2.167 m	5.027 m	5.474 m	-19.490 m	19.540 m

Table 34 – (Copernicus DEM EEA-10 – GEDI lowest mode LE95) error statistics - classified with C3S-LC 2013.

Figure 103 - (Copernicus DEM EEA-10 – GEDI lowest mode LE95) errors classified with C3S-LC 2013.

C3S-LC 2013

EEA-10 – GEDI lowest mode

	Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, closed to open (>15%)
	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%)
	Cropland, rainfed
	Shrubland
	Grassland

[See map and full legend on VtWeb](#)

	<= -9 metres
	-9 metres to -3 metres
	-3 metres to -1.5 metres
	-1.5 metres to -0.5 metres
	-0.5 metres to 0.5 metres
	0.5 metres to 1.5 metres
	1.5 metres to 3 metres
	3 metres to 9 metres
	>= 9 metres

Figure 104 - (Copernicus DEM EEA-10 – GEDI lowest mode LE95) errors histogram - classified with C3S-LC 2013.

One may observe that tree cover classes, and in particular “needleleaved evergreen” and “broad leaved deciduous” (70 and 60), show a long tail of distribution of positive values. This rightward skewness illustrates that Copernicus DEM EEA-10 is over the GEDI lowest mode data for these classes. Similar observations are made considering ICESat-2 terrain reference data.

4.6.2.5 Copernicus DEM EEA-10 – GEDI highest return

DN	Class	Count	Mean	Std Dev	RMSE	Min	Max
0	No Data	-	-	-	-	-	-
10	Cropland, rainfed	1 111 031	-6.149 m	3.288 m	6.973 m	-17.120 m	16.960 m
11	Cropland, rainfed, herbaceous cover	3 221 326	-5.148 m	2.547 m	5.743 m	-17.120 m	16.960 m
12	Cropland, rainfed, tree or shrub cover	285 539	-6.022 m	2.729 m	6.612 m	-17.120 m	16.560 m
20	Cropland, irrigated or post-flooding	228 807	-4.788 m	2.210 m	5.273 m	-17.120 m	16.950 m
30	Mosaic cropland (>50%) / natural vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (<50%)	610 911	-6.837 m	3.702 m	7.775 m	-17.120 m	16.960 m
40	Mosaic natural vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (>50%) / cropland (<50%)	362 833	-7.410 m	3.446 m	8.172 m	-17.120 m	16.910 m
50	Tree cover, broadleaved, evergreen, closed to open (>15%)	73 131	-10.541 m	3.704 m	11.172 m	-17.120 m	16.880 m
60	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%)	1 061 621	-9.004 m	4.245 m	9.955 m	-17.120 m	16.960 m
61	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, closed (>40%)	2 291	-9.532 m	4.578 m	10.574 m	-17.100 m	16.540 m
62	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, open (15-40%)	-	-	-	-	-	-
70	Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, closed to open (>15%)	941 184	-9.131 m	4.415 m	10.142 m	-17.130 m	16.960 m
71	Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, closed (>40%)	-	-	-	-	-	-
72	Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, open (15-40%)	-	-	-	-	-	-
80	Tree cover, needleleaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%)	591	-8.178 m	3.906 m	9.063 m	-17.090 m	4.820 m
81	Tree cover, needleleaved, deciduous, closed (>40%)	-	-	-	-	-	-
82	Tree cover, needleleaved, deciduous, open (15-40%)	-	-	-	-	-	-
90	Tree cover, mixed leaf type (broadleaved and needleleaved)	312 440	-9.461 m	4.587 m	10.514 m	-17.130 m	16.960 m
100	Mosaic tree and shrub (>50%) / herbaceous cover (<50%)	726 579	-8.361 m	4.002 m	9.269 m	-17.120 m	16.960 m
110	Mosaic herbaceous cover (>50%) / tree and shrub (<50%)	41 451	-7.164 m	4.007 m	8.209 m	-17.130 m	16.860 m
120	Shrubland	134 165	-7.694 m	3.339 m	8.387 m	-17.120 m	16.400 m
121	Evergreen shrubland	-	-	-	-	-	-
122	Deciduous shrubland	579	-7.322 m	3.326 m	8.042 m	-16.610 m	3.770 m
130	Grassland	1 260 002	-6.331 m	3.375 m	7.175 m	-17.130 m	16.950 m
140	Lichens and mosses	124	-8.169 m	3.013 m	8.707 m	-15.850 m	4.9E-324
150	Sparse vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (<15%)	74 735	-7.578 m	3.640 m	8.407 m	-17.130 m	16.310 m
151	Sparse tree (<15%)	-	-	-	-	-	-
152	Sparse shrub (<15%)	-	-	-	-	-	-
153	Sparse herbaceous cover (<15%)	5 954	-6.646 m	3.256 m	7.400 m	-17.130 m	10.730 m
160	Tree cover, flooded, fresh or brackish water	1 753	-9.379 m	2.312 m	9.659 m	-17.030 m	1.570 m
170	Tree cover, flooded, saline water	2 500	-6.067 m	2.661 m	6.625 m	-17.030 m	16.810 m
180	Shrub or herbaceous cover, flooded, fresh/saline/brackish water	51 164	-5.506 m	2.962 m	6.252 m	-17.120 m	16.690 m
190	Urban areas	394 174	-7.985 m	3.423 m	8.688 m	-17.130 m	16.710 m
200	Bare areas	50 729	-7.594 m	3.765 m	8.476 m	-17.120 m	15.620 m
201	Consolidated bare areas	7 465	-10.372 m	3.996 m	11.115 m	-17.120 m	16.660 m
202	Unconsolidated bare areas	648	-5.861 m	3.001 m	6.585 m	-16.420 m	4.010 m
210	Water bodies	27 944	-6.714 m	3.745 m	7.688 m	-17.130 m	16.960 m
220	Permanent snow and ice	3 947	-8.599 m	5.795 m	10.370 m	-17.110 m	16.120 m
All	Total	10 995 618	-6.834 m	3.774 m	7.807 m	-17.130 m	16.960 m

Table 35 – (Copernicus DEM EEA-10 – GEDI highest return LE95) error statistics - classified with C3S-LC 2013.

Figure 105 - (Copernicus DEM EEA-10 – GEDI highest return LE95) errors classified with C3S-LC 2013.

C3S-LC 2013

EEA-10 – GEDI highest return

	Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, closed to open (>15%)
	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%)
	Cropland, rainfed
	Shrubland
	Grassland

[See map and full legend on VtWeb](#)

	<= -9 metres
	-9 metres to -3 metres
	-3 metres to -1.5 metres
	-1.5 metres to -0.5 metres
	-0.5 metres to 0.5 metres
	0.5 metres to 1.5 metres
	1.5 metres to 3 metres
	3 metres to 9 metres
	>= 9 metres

Figure 106 - (Copernicus DEM EEA-10 – GEDI highest return LE95) errors histogram - classified with C3S-LC 2013.

One may observe that tree cover classes, and in particular “needle leaved evergreen” and “broad leaved deciduous” (70 and 60), show a long tail of distribution of negative values. As opposed to the rightward skewness of the (EEA-10 - GEDI lowest mode) histogram, this leftward skewness illustrates that Copernicus DEM EEA-10 is below the GEDI highest return data for this class. Similar observations are made considering ICESat-2 terrain with canopy data (see Figure 102).

4.6.2.6 Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – ICESat-1

DN	Class	Count	Mean	Std Dev	RMSE	Min	Max
0	No Data	-	-	-	-	-	-
10	Cropland, rainfed	4 600 451	0.094 m	0.610 m	0.617 m	-2.720 m	2.730 m
11	Cropland, rainfed, herbaceous cover	4 980 645	0.049 m	0.561 m	0.563 m	-2.720 m	2.730 m
12	Cropland, rainfed, tree or shrub cover	51 726	0.117 m	0.730 m	0.739 m	-2.720 m	2.720 m
20	Cropland, irrigated or post-flooding	1 830 284	0.171 m	0.621 m	0.644 m	-2.720 m	2.720 m
30	Mosaic cropland (>50%) / natural vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (<50%)	1 403 816	0.119 m	0.684 m	0.695 m	-2.720 m	2.730 m
40	Mosaic natural vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (>50%) / cropland (<50%)	1 094 460	0.128 m	0.709 m	0.720 m	-2.720 m	2.720 m
50	Tree cover, broadleaved, evergreen, closed to open (>15%)	274 283	0.505 m	1.120 m	1.229 m	-2.720 m	2.730 m
60	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%)	629 734	0.799 m	1.036 m	1.309 m	-2.720 m	2.720 m
61	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, closed (>40%)	127 021	0.793 m	0.886 m	1.189 m	-2.720 m	2.720 m
62	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, open (15-40%)	792 627	0.590 m	0.911 m	1.085 m	-2.720 m	2.720 m
70	Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, closed to open (>15%)	822 732	0.447 m	0.990 m	1.087 m	-2.720 m	2.730 m
71	Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, closed (>40%)	659 428	0.724 m	0.997 m	1.232 m	-2.720 m	2.730 m
72	Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, open (15-40%)	140	-0.030 m	0.936 m	0.936 m	-2.190 m	2.640 m
80	Tree cover, needleleaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%)	712 943	0.695 m	1.028 m	1.241 m	-2.720 m	2.720 m
81	Tree cover, needleleaved, deciduous, closed (>40%)	59	0.120 m	1.173 m	1.179 m	-2.610 m	2.610 m
82	Tree cover, needleleaved, deciduous, open (15-40%)	-	-	-	-	-	-
90	Tree cover, mixed leaf type (broadleaved and needleleaved)	155 918	0.832 m	1.127 m	1.401 m	-2.720 m	2.730 m
100	Mosaic tree and shrub (>50%) / herbaceous cover (<50%)	1 008 319	0.205 m	0.785 m	0.811 m	-2.720 m	2.720 m
110	Mosaic herbaceous cover (>50%) / tree and shrub (<50%)	374 085	0.080 m	0.625 m	0.630 m	-2.720 m	2.730 m
120	Shrubland	5 599 261	0.153 m	0.589 m	0.609 m	-2.720 m	2.720 m
121	Evergreen shrubland	8 895	0.274 m	1.149 m	1.181 m	-2.710 m	2.720 m
122	Deciduous shrubland	1 023 155	0.251 m	0.895 m	0.930 m	-2.720 m	2.720 m
130	Grassland	6 806 975	-0.013 m	0.539 m	0.540 m	-2.720 m	2.730 m
140	Lichens and mosses	121 086	-0.083 m	0.723 m	0.728 m	-2.720 m	2.710 m
150	Sparse vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (<15%)	5 609 933	-0.227 m	0.484 m	0.534 m	-2.720 m	2.730 m
151	Sparse tree (<15%)	-	-	-	-	-	-
152	Sparse shrub (<15%)	36 067	-0.118 m	0.400 m	0.417 m	-2.710 m	2.730 m
153	Sparse herbaceous cover (<15%)	280 224	-0.031 m	0.366 m	0.367 m	-2.720 m	2.730 m
160	Tree cover, flooded, fresh or brackish water	239 988	0.293 m	0.878 m	0.925 m	-2.720 m	2.720 m
170	Tree cover, flooded, saline water	70 759	0.340 m	1.077 m	1.129 m	-2.720 m	2.730 m
180	Shrub or herbaceous cover, flooded, fresh/saline/brackish water	1 246 225	-0.060 m	0.654 m	0.657 m	-2.720 m	2.720 m
190	Urban areas	238 680	0.313 m	0.964 m	1.014 m	-2.720 m	2.730 m
200	Bare areas	18 018 863	-0.095 m	0.408 m	0.419 m	-2.720 m	2.720 m
201	Consolidated bare areas	59 483	-0.060 m	0.390 m	0.395 m	-2.710 m	2.720 m
202	Unconsolidated bare areas	63 676	-0.030 m	0.391 m	0.392 m	-2.720 m	2.710 m
210	Water bodies	370 776	-0.138 m	0.944 m	0.954 m	-2.720 m	2.730 m
220	Permanent snow and ice	6 562	-0.567 m	1.426 m	1.534 m	-2.720 m	2.720 m
All	Total	59 319 279	0.033 m	0.627 m	0.628 m	-2.720 m	2.730 m

Table 36 – (Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – ICESat-1 LE95) error statistics - classified with C3S-LC 2013.

Figure 107 - (Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – ICESat-1 LE95) errors classified with C3S-LC 2013.

	Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, closed to open (>15%)
	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%)
	Cropland, rainfed
	Shrubland
	Grassland

[See map and full legend on VtWeb](#)

	<= -9 metres
	-9 metres to -3 metres
	-3 metres to -1.5 metres
	-1.5 metres to -0.5 metres
	-0.5 metres to 0.5 metres
	0.5 metres to 1.5 metres
	1.5 metres to 3 metres
	3 metres to 9 metres
	>= 9 metres

Figure 108 - (Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – ICESat-1 LE95) errors histogram - classified with C3S-LC 2013.

A first observation is to underline the differences between the distribution over Europe (see Figure 98) and those over the whole globe. In particular the forest classes are much less represented at worldwide level than in Europe.

One may observe that the “sparse vegetation” class shows a tail of distribution of negative values. This indicates that Copernicus DEM GLO-30 is below ICESat-1 reference data for many samples of this class. Other classes are mostly right-skewed, with positive errors indicating GLO-30 is higher than ICESat-1 data for these classes.

4.6.2.7 Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – ICESat-2 terrain only

DN	Class	Count	Mean	Std Dev	RMSE	Min	Max
0	No Data	-	-	-	-	-	-
10	Cropland, rainfed	687 482	0.312 m	0.890 m	0.943 m	-4.990 m	5.000 m
11	Cropland, rainfed, herbaceous cover	727 209	0.240 m	0.835 m	0.869 m	-4.990 m	5.000 m
12	Cropland, rainfed, tree or shrub cover	20 087	0.487 m	0.959 m	1.076 m	-4.900 m	5.000 m
20	Cropland, irrigated or post-flooding	218 395	0.283 m	0.880 m	0.924 m	-4.980 m	5.000 m
30	Mosaic cropland (>50%) / natural vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (<50%)	223 345	0.454 m	1.076 m	1.168 m	-4.990 m	5.000 m
40	Mosaic natural vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (>50%) / cropland (<50%)	239 573	0.386 m	1.092 m	1.158 m	-4.990 m	5.000 m
50	Tree cover, broadleaved, evergreen, closed to open (>15%)	35 382	1.755 m	1.619 m	2.387 m	-4.900 m	5.000 m
60	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%)	129 496	1.938 m	1.698 m	2.577 m	-4.990 m	5.000 m
61	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, closed (>40%)	18 166	2.081 m	1.471 m	2.549 m	-4.860 m	5.000 m
62	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, open (15-40%)	127 414	1.608 m	1.322 m	2.082 m	-4.710 m	5.000 m
70	Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, closed to open (>15%)	181 865	1.520 m	1.688 m	2.271 m	-4.980 m	5.010 m
71	Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, closed (>40%)	170 070	1.847 m	1.522 m	2.393 m	-4.970 m	5.010 m
72	Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, open (15-40%)	51	-0.069 m	1.907 m	1.909 m	-3.310 m	4.650 m
80	Tree cover, needleleaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%)	236 738	1.766 m	1.723 m	2.467 m	-4.990 m	5.000 m
81	Tree cover, needleleaved, deciduous, closed (>40%)	27	0.450 m	1.694 m	1.752 m	-2.270 m	4.820 m
82	Tree cover, needleleaved, deciduous, open (15-40%)	-	-	-	-	-	-
90	Tree cover, mixed leaf type (broadleaved and needleleaved)	51 657	2.321 m	1.697 m	2.875 m	-4.890 m	5.010 m
100	Mosaic tree and shrub (>50%) / herbaceous cover (<50%)	165 943	0.641 m	1.276 m	1.428 m	-4.990 m	5.000 m
110	Mosaic herbaceous cover (>50%) / tree and shrub (<50%)	820 14	0.250 m	0.980 m	1.011 m	-4.990 m	5.010 m
120	Shrubland	1 395 135	0.319 m	0.867 m	0.924 m	-4.990 m	5.000 m
121	Evergreen shrubland	6 258	0.466 m	1.745 m	1.806 m	-4.990 m	5.000 m
122	Deciduous shrubland	257 821	0.631 m	1.341 m	1.482 m	-4.990 m	5.000 m
130	Grassland	1 646 447	0.045 m	0.764 m	0.765 m	-4.990 m	5.010 m
140	Lichens and mosses	20 318	-0.265 m	0.945 m	0.982 m	-4.980 m	5.000 m
150	Sparse vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (<15%)	1 540 351	-0.194 m	0.574 m	0.606 m	-4.990 m	5.010 m
151	Sparse tree (<15%)	-	-	-	-	-	-
152	Sparse shrub (<15%)	8 526	-0.044 m	0.712 m	0.714 m	-4.910 m	5.010 m
153	Sparse herbaceous cover (<15%)	94 224	-0.027 m	0.557 m	0.558 m	-4.990 m	5.000 m
160	Tree cover, flooded, fresh or brackish water	21 210	1.249 m	1.428 m	1.897 m	-4.930 m	5.000 m
170	Tree cover, flooded, saline water	8 182	0.983 m	1.652 m	1.923 m	-4.000 m	5.010 m
180	Shrub or herbaceous cover, flooded, fresh/saline/brackish water	85 461	0.252 m	1.026 m	1.057 m	-4.990 m	5.000 m
190	Urban areas	75 423	1.044 m	1.440 m	1.778 m	-4.990 m	5.010 m
200	Bare areas	5 272 138	-0.067 m	0.593 m	0.597 m	-4.990 m	5.000 m
201	Consolidated bare areas	16 124	-0.056 m	0.713 m	0.715 m	-4.970 m	4.950 m
202	Unconsolidated bare areas	18 504	-0.024 m	0.627 m	0.627 m	-4.920 m	4.810 m
210	Water bodies	25 918	0.493 m	1.471 m	1.551 m	-4.980 m	5.010 m
220	Permanent snow and ice	9 770	-0.082 m	2.502 m	2.504 m	-4.990 m	5.000 m
All	Total	13 816 724	0.195 m	0.979 m	0.999 m	-4.990 m	5.010 m

Table 37 – (Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – ICESat-2 terrain only LE95) error statistics - classified with C3S-LC 2013.

Figure 109 - (Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – ICESat-2 terrain only LE95) errors classified with C3S-LC 2013.

	Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, closed to open (>15%)
	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%)
	Cropland, rainfed
	Shrubland
	Grassland

[See map and full legend on VtWeb](#)

	<= -9 metres
	-9 metres to -3 metres
	-3 metres to -1.5 metres
	-1.5 metres to -0.5 metres
	-0.5 metres to 0.5 metres
	0.5 metres to 1.5 metres
	1.5 metres to 3 metres
	3 metres to 9 metres
	>= 9 metres

Figure 110 - (Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – ICESat-2 terrain only LE95) errors histogram - classified with C3S-LC 2013.

As observed for the (GLO-30 – ICESat-1) study, the leftward skewness of the “sparse vegetation” class (150) indicates that GLO-30 is below ICESat-2 terrain only reference data. Other classes are mostly right-skewed, with positive errors indicating GLO-30 is higher than ICESat-2 terrain only data for these classes.

4.6.2.8 Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – ICESat-2 terrain with canopy

DN	Class	Count	Mean	Std Dev	RMSE	Min	Max
0	No Data	-	-	-	-	-	-
10	Cropland, rainfed	661 634	-1.016 m	2.746 m	2.928 m	-11.010 m	10.970 m
11	Cropland, rainfed, herbaceous cover	699 518	-1.106 m	2.708 m	2.925 m	-11.010 m	10.960 m
12	Cropland, rainfed, tree or shrub cover	19 047	-2.445 m	3.346 m	4.144 m	-11.010 m	10.790 m
20	Cropland, irrigated or post-flooding	212 311	-1.076 m	2.674 m	2.883 m	-11.000 m	10.950 m
30	Mosaic cropland (>50%) / natural vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (<50%)	208 644	-2.087 m	3.369 m	3.964 m	-11.010 m	10.960 m
40	Mosaic natural vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (>50%) / cropland (<50%)	228 895	-1.755 m	3.162 m	3.616 m	-11.000 m	10.970 m
50	Tree cover, broadleaved, evergreen, closed to open (>15%)	45 797	-5.804 m	3.746 m	6.908 m	-11.010 m	10.970 m
60	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%)	185 860	-6.304 m	3.337 m	7.133 m	-11.010 m	10.970 m
61	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, closed (>40%)	22 632	-6.261 m	2.819 m	6.867 m	-11.000 m	10.880 m
62	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, open (15-40%)	120 709	-5.384 m	3.467 m	6.404 m	-11.000 m	10.930 m
70	Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, closed to open (>15%)	220 474	-6.396 m	3.039 m	7.081 m	-11.010 m	10.970 m
71	Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, closed (>40%)	202 112	-6.440 m	2.502 m	6.909 m	-11.010 m	10.970 m
72	Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, open (15-40%)	55	-5.120 m	3.545 m	6.227 m	-10.730 m	5.260 m
80	Tree cover, needleleaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%)	223 578	-6.507 m	3.160 m	7.233 m	-11.010 m	10.960 m
81	Tree cover, needleleaved, deciduous, closed (>40%)	26	-2.474 m	6.003 m	6.493 m	-10.490 m	10.500 m
82	Tree cover, needleleaved, deciduous, open (15-40%)	-	-	-	-	-	-
90	Tree cover, mixed leaf type (broadleaved and needleleaved)	96 655	-7.054 m	2.939 m	7.642 m	-11.010 m	10.950 m
100	Mosaic tree and shrub (>50%) / herbaceous cover (<50%)	158 220	-3.402 m	3.603 m	4.955 m	-11.010 m	10.970 m
110	Mosaic herbaceous cover (>50%) / tree and shrub (<50%)	80 036	-1.428 m	2.909 m	3.241 m	-11.010 m	10.970 m
120	Shrubland	1 376 504	-1.277 m	2.719 m	3.003 m	-11.010 m	10.950 m
121	Evergreen shrubland	6 251	-4.949 m	2.780 m	5.677 m	-11.010 m	10.710 m
122	Deciduous shrubland	224 610	-4.045 m	3.900 m	5.619 m	-11.010 m	10.940 m
130	Grassland	1 621 560	-0.543 m	1.905 m	1.981 m	-11.010 m	10.960 m
140	Lichens and mosses	20 158	-1.832 m	2.404 m	3.022 m	-10.990 m	10.860 m
150	Sparse vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (<15%)	1 538 720	-0.333 m	1.032 m	1.084 m	-11.010 m	10.960 m
151	Sparse tree (<15%)	-	-	-	-	-	-
152	Sparse shrub (<15%)	8 502	-0.272 m	1.309 m	1.337 m	-10.920 m	6.940 m
153	Sparse herbaceous cover (<15%)	94 265	-0.050 m	0.695 m	0.697 m	-11.000 m	10.910 m
160	Tree cover, flooded, fresh or brackish water	25 323	-5.602 m	2.944 m	6.329 m	-11.010 m	10.960 m
170	Tree cover, flooded, saline water	9 439	-3.823 m	3.257 m	5.023 m	-11.010 m	10.930 m
180	Shrub or herbaceous cover, flooded, fresh/saline/brackish water	83 356	-2.052 m	3.040 m	3.668 m	-11.010 m	10.950 m
190	Urban areas	68 209	-4.157 m	3.938 m	5.726 m	-11.010 m	10.850 m
200	Bare areas	5 279 811	-0.085 m	0.720 m	0.725 m	-11.010 m	10.970 m
201	Consolidated bare areas	16 155	-0.199 m	1.185 m	1.201 m	-10.870 m	9.700 m
202	Unconsolidated bare areas	18 534	-0.051 m	0.781 m	0.782 m	-10.740 m	10.870 m
210	Water bodies	25 830	-2.930 m	3.431 m	4.512 m	-11.010 m	10.660 m
220	Permanent snow and ice	13 294	-1.256 m	4.988 m	5.144 m	-11.010 m	10.970 m
All	Total	13 816 724	-1.124 m	2.680 m	2.907 m	-11.010 m	10.970 m

Table 38 – (Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – ICESat-2 terrain with canopy LE95) error statistics - classified with C3S-LC 2013.

Figure 111 - (Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – ICESat-2 terrain with canopy LE95) errors classified with C3S-LC 2013.

	Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, closed to open (>15%)
	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%)
	Cropland, rainfed
	Shrubland
	Grassland

[See map and full legend on VtWeb](#)

	<= -9 metres
	-9 metres to -3 metres
	-3 metres to -1.5 metres
	-1.5 metres to -0.5 metres
	-0.5 metres to 0.5 metres
	0.5 metres to 1.5 metres
	1.5 metres to 3 metres
	3 metres to 9 metres
	>= 9 metres

Figure 112 - (Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – ICESat-2 terrain with canopy LE95) errors histogram - classified with C3S-LC 2013.

As opposed to the (GLO-30 – ICESat-2 terrain only) histogram, one may observe a long tail of distribution of negative values, mostly represented by the shrubland class. This leftward skewness illustrates that Copernicus DEM GLO-30 is below the ICESat-2 terrain with canopy for this class. One may suppose that trees of various heights (even great) are disseminated in these shrublands.

4.6.2.9 Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – GEDI lowest mode

DN	Class	Count	Mean	Std Dev	RMSE	Min	Max
0	No Data	-	-	-	-	-	-
10	Cropland, rainfed	13 739 268	0.295 m	2.061 m	2.082 m	-14.200 m	14.230 m
11	Cropland, rainfed, herbaceous cover	17 798 779	0.110 m	1.695 m	1.699 m	-14.200 m	14.230 m
12	Cropland, rainfed, tree or shrub cover	395 927	1.218 m	3.184 m	3.409 m	-14.130 m	14.230 m
20	Cropland, irrigated or post-flooding	3 975 208	0.205 m	1.625 m	1.638 m	-14.200 m	14.230 m
30	Mosaic cropland (>50%) / natural vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (<50%)	5 733 990	1.011 m	3.154 m	3.312 m	-14.200 m	14.230 m
40	Mosaic natural vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (>50%) / cropland (<50%)	6 489 333	1.094 m	3.336 m	3.511 m	-14.200 m	14.230 m
50	Tree cover, broadleaved, evergreen, closed to open (>15%)	7 279 706	6.315 m	4.925 m	8.008 m	-14.200 m	14.230 m
60	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%)	9 020 629	4.611 m	4.352 m	6.341 m	-14.200 m	14.230 m
61	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, closed (>40%)	1 265 356	4.217 m	4.323 m	6.039 m	-14.190 m	14.230 m
62	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, open (15-40%)	4 983 322	2.141 m	2.791 m	3.517 m	-14.200 m	14.230 m
70	Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, closed to open (>15%)	6 384 856	4.523 m	4.752 m	6.561 m	-14.200 m	14.230 m
71	Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, closed (>40%)	4 076 933	3.834 m	3.871 m	5.448 m	-14.200 m	14.230 m
72	Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, open (15-40%)	1 829	0.878 m	4.809 m	4.888 m	-13.870 m	14.230 m
80	Tree cover, needleleaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%)	4 419 415	4.244 m	4.144 m	5.932 m	-14.200 m	14.230 m
81	Tree cover, needleleaved, deciduous, closed (>40%)	8 074	4.214 m	5.318 m	6.786 m	-14.200 m	14.230 m
82	Tree cover, needleleaved, deciduous, open (15-40%)	-	-	-	-	-	-
90	Tree cover, mixed leaf type (broadleaved and needleleaved)	2 572 154	5.228 m	4.415 m	6.843 m	-14.200 m	14.240 m
100	Mosaic tree and shrub (>50%) / herbaceous cover (<50%)	4 798 181	1.752 m	3.845 m	4.225 m	-14.200 m	14.230 m
110	Mosaic herbaceous cover (>50%) / tree and shrub (<50%)	1 724 623	0.684 m	3.043 m	3.119 m	-14.200 m	14.240 m
120	Shrubland	19 764 622	0.287 m	2.192 m	2.211 m	-14.200 m	14.230 m
121	Evergreen shrubland	215 384	5.718 m	5.032 m	7.617 m	-14.200 m	14.230 m
122	Deciduous shrubland	2 857 617	0.644 m	2.040 m	2.139 m	-14.200 m	14.230 m
130	Grassland	28 788 091	-0.048 m	2.121 m	2.122 m	-14.200 m	14.240 m
140	Lichens and mosses	21 163	-0.260 m	2.763 m	2.775 m	-14.120 m	14.230 m
150	Sparse vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (<15%)	16 987 246	-0.406 m	1.397 m	1.455 m	-14.200 m	14.240 m
151	Sparse tree (<15%)	-	-	-	-	-	-
152	Sparse shrub (<15%)	70 551	0.018 m	3.043 m	3.043 m	-14.200 m	14.230 m
153	Sparse herbaceous cover (<15%)	768 782	-0.214 m	1.608 m	1.622 m	-14.170 m	14.230 m
160	Tree cover, flooded, fresh or brackish water	897 921	3.455 m	4.703 m	5.835 m	-14.170 m	14.230 m
170	Tree cover, flooded, saline water	239 698	2.451 m	4.091 m	4.769 m	-14.100 m	14.240 m
180	Shrub or herbaceous cover, flooded, fresh/saline/brackish water	1 719 145	-0.037 m	1.754 m	1.754 m	-14.200 m	14.230 m
190	Urban areas	1 277 103	1.124 m	2.272 m	2.534 m	-14.200 m	14.240 m
200	Bare areas	35 518 378	-0.311 m	1.422 m	1.455 m	-14.200 m	14.230 m
201	Consolidated bare areas	164 570	-0.155 m	2.634 m	2.639 m	-14.190 m	14.230 m
202	Unconsolidated bare areas	175 514	-0.312 m	1.343 m	1.379 m	-14.100 m	14.140 m
210	Water bodies	692 020	0.836 m	3.163 m	3.271 m	-14.200 m	14.240 m
220	Permanent snow and ice	314 560	0.862 m	5.271 m	5.341 m	-14.200 m	14.230 m
All	Total	205 139 948	1.001 m	3.281 m	3.431 m	-14.200 m	14.240 m

Table 39 – (Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – GEDI lowest mode LE95) error statistics - classified with C3S-LC 2013.

Figure 113 - (Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – GEDI lowest mode LE95) errors classified with C3S-LC 2013.

	Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, closed to open (>15%)
	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%)
	Cropland, rainfed
	Shrubland
	Grassland

	<= -9 metres
	-9 metres to -3 metres
	-3 metres to -1.5 metres
	-1.5 metres to -0.5 metres
	-0.5 metres to 0.5 metres
	0.5 metres to 1.5 metres
	1.5 metres to 3 metres
	3 metres to 9 metres
	>= 9 metres

[See map and full legend on VtWeb](#)

Figure 114 - (Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – GEDI lowest mode LE95) errors histogram - classified with C3S-LC 2013.

One may observe a long tail of distribution of positive values, mostly represented by the “broad-leaved” tree cover classes (50 and 60). This rightward skewness illustrates that Copernicus DEM GLO-30 is over the GEDI lowest mode for these classes.

4.6.2.10 Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – GEDI highest return

DN	Class	Count	Mean	Std Dev	RMSE	Min	Max
0	No Data	-	-	-	-	-	-
10	Cropland, rainfed	13 470 677	-5.083 m	2.610 m	5.714 m	-15.310 m	15.180 m
11	Cropland, rainfed, herbaceous cover	17 531 824	-4.756 m	2.274 m	5.271 m	-15.310 m	15.180 m
12	Cropland, rainfed, tree or shrub cover	387 055	-6.343 m	3.156 m	7.085 m	-15.310 m	15.140 m
20	Cropland, irrigated or post-flooding	3 883 095	-4.991 m	2.643 m	5.648 m	-15.310 m	15.180 m
30	Mosaic cropland (>50%) / natural vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (<50%)	5 568 715	-5.893 m	3.296 m	6.752 m	-15.310 m	15.180 m
40	Mosaic natural vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (>50%) / cropland (<50%)	6 320 780	-5.925 m	3.345 m	6.804 m	-15.310 m	15.180 m
50	Tree cover, broadleaved, evergreen, closed to open (>15%)	9 435 651	-8.966 m	4.300 m	9.944 m	-15.320 m	15.180 m
60	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%)	9 456 576	-8.027 m	4.011 m	8.973 m	-15.310 m	15.180 m
61	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, closed (>40%)	1 239 215	-8.252 m	3.583 m	8.997 m	-15.310 m	15.160 m
62	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, open (15-40%)	4 886 755	-7.430 m	3.164 m	8.075 m	-15.310 m	15.170 m
70	Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, closed to open (>15%)	6 478 989	-8.499 m	4.358 m	9.551 m	-15.320 m	15.180 m
71	Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, closed (>40%)	4 118 532	-7.962 m	3.830 m	8.835 m	-15.320 m	15.180 m
72	Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, open (15-40%)	1 574	-8.388 m	4.167 m	9.366 m	-15.310 m	12.040 m
80	Tree cover, needleleaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%)	4 228 770	-7.603 m	4.436 m	8.802 m	-15.310 m	15.180 m
81	Tree cover, needleleaved, deciduous, closed (>40%)	5 328	-6.214 m	7.880 m	10.035 m	-15.310 m	15.180 m
82	Tree cover, needleleaved, deciduous, open (15-40%)	-	-	-	-	-	-
90	Tree cover, mixed leaf type (broadleaved and needleleaved)	2 698 820	-8.597 m	4.020 m	9.491 m	-15.320 m	15.180 m
100	Mosaic tree and shrub (>50%) / herbaceous cover (<50%)	4 742 043	-6.754 m	3.603 m	7.655 m	-15.310 m	15.180 m
110	Mosaic herbaceous cover (>50%) / tree and shrub (<50%)	1 677 461	-6.032 m	3.074 m	6.770 m	-15.320 m	15.150 m
120	Shrubland	19 480 603	-5.605 m	2.529 m	6.149 m	-15.310 m	15.180 m
121	Evergreen shrubland	256 691	-7.521 m	5.044 m	9.056 m	-15.310 m	15.180 m
122	Deciduous shrubland	2 760 133	-7.133 m	3.204 m	7.819 m	-15.310 m	15.090 m
130	Grassland	28 149 898	-5.188 m	2.498 m	5.758 m	-15.320 m	15.180 m
140	Lichens and mosses	20 636	-6.399 m	2.693 m	6.942 m	-15.310 m	12.000 m
150	Sparse vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (<15%)	16 862 030	-4.725 m	1.742 m	5.036 m	-15.320 m	15.170 m
151	Sparse tree (<15%)	-	-	-	-	-	-
152	Sparse shrub (<15%)	68 055	-5.656 m	2.973 m	6.390 m	-15.320 m	15.040 m
153	Sparse herbaceous cover (<15%)	760 423	-4.762 m	2.054 m	5.186 m	-15.320 m	14.770 m
160	Tree cover, flooded, fresh or brackish water	963 788	-7.584 m	3.731 m	8.452 m	-15.310 m	15.180 m
170	Tree cover, flooded, saline water	247 104	-6.776 m	3.161 m	7.477 m	-15.320 m	15.160 m
180	Shrub or herbaceous cover, flooded, fresh/saline/brackish water	1 704 371	-5.035 m	2.174 m	5.484 m	-15.310 m	14.840 m
190	Urban areas	1 179 832	-7.389 m	3.244 m	8.070 m	-15.320 m	15.140 m
200	Bare areas	35 256 533	-4.441 m	1.673 m	4.746 m	-15.310 m	15.180 m
201	Consolidated bare areas	158 421	-5.388 m	2.805 m	6.074 m	-15.310 m	15.090 m
202	Unconsolidated bare areas	174 436	-4.452 m	1.562 m	4.718 m	-15.310 m	13.410 m
210	Water bodies	673 180	-5.849 m	3.147 m	6.641 m	-15.320 m	15.150 m
220	Permanent snow and ice	291 954	-5.276 m	6.101 m	8.066 m	-15.310 m	15.180 m
All	Total	205 139 948	-5.786 m	3.180 m	6.603 m	-15.320 m	15.180 m

Table 40 – (Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – GEDI highest return LE95) error statistics - classified with C3S-LC 2013.

Figure 115 - (Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – GEDI highest return LE95) errors classified with C3S-LC 2013.

	Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, closed to open (>15%)
	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%)
	Cropland, rainfed
	Shrubland
	Grassland

[See map and full legend on VtWeb](#)

	<= -9 metres
	-9 metres to -3 metres
	-3 metres to -1.5 metres
	-1.5 metres to -0.5 metres
	-0.5 metres to 0.5 metres
	0.5 metres to 1.5 metres
	1.5 metres to 3 metres
	3 metres to 9 metres
	>= 9 metres

Figure 116 - (Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – GEDI highest return LE95) errors histogram - classified with C3S-LC 2013.

One may observe a long tail of distribution of negative values, mostly represented by the “broad-leaved” tree cover classes (50 and 60). As opposed to the rightward skewness of the (GLO-30 – GEDI lowest mode) tree cover histograms, this leftward skewness illustrates that Copernicus DEM GLO-30 is lower than GEDI highest return.

4.6.2.11 Copernicus DEM GLO-90 – ICESat-1

DN	Class	Count	Mean	Std Dev	RMSE	Min	Max
0	No Data	-	-	-	-	-	-
10	Cropland, rainfed	4 616 146	0.132 m	0.672 m	0.685 m	-3.010 m	3.020 m
11	Cropland, rainfed, herbaceous cover	4 993 175	0.077 m	0.633 m	0.638 m	-3.010 m	3.010 m
12	Cropland, rainfed, tree or shrub cover	51 572	0.163 m	0.860 m	0.876 m	-3.010 m	3.010 m
20	Cropland, irrigated or post-flooding	1 851 661	0.218 m	0.665 m	0.699 m	-3.010 m	3.010 m
30	Mosaic cropland (>50%) / natural vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (<50%)	1 405 517	0.172 m	0.784 m	0.802 m	-3.010 m	3.020 m
40	Mosaic natural vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (>50%) / cropland (<50%)	1 095 083	0.183 m	0.810 m	0.830 m	-3.010 m	3.010 m
50	Tree cover, broadleaved, evergreen, closed to open (>15%)	282 802	0.619 m	1.232 m	1.379 m	-3.010 m	3.020 m
60	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%)	639 401	0.991 m	1.140 m	1.510 m	-3.010 m	3.010 m
61	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, closed (>40%)	128 463	0.888 m	0.944 m	1.296 m	-3.010 m	3.010 m
62	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, open (15-40%)	811 906	0.652 m	0.970 m	1.169 m	-3.010 m	3.010 m
70	Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, closed to open (>15%)	836 538	0.554 m	1.103 m	1.234 m	-3.010 m	3.020 m
71	Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, closed (>40%)	683 966	0.850 m	1.085 m	1.379 m	-3.010 m	3.020 m
72	Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, open (15-40%)	143	-0.092 m	0.909 m	0.913 m	-2.970 m	2.590 m
80	Tree cover, needleleaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%)	735 572	0.879 m	1.115 m	1.420 m	-3.010 m	3.010 m
81	Tree cover, needleleaved, deciduous, closed (>40%)	57	0.449 m	1.625 m	1.686 m	-3.000 m	3.010 m
82	Tree cover, needleleaved, deciduous, open (15-40%)	-	-	-	-	-	-
90	Tree cover, mixed leaf type (broadleaved and needleleaved)	158 609	1.066 m	1.234 m	1.630 m	-3.010 m	3.020 m
100	Mosaic tree and shrub (>50%) / herbaceous cover (<50%)	1 012 106	0.263 m	0.864 m	0.903 m	-3.010 m	3.010 m
110	Mosaic herbaceous cover (>50%) / tree and shrub (<50%)	372 216	0.104 m	0.695 m	0.703 m	-3.010 m	3.020 m
120	Shrubland	5 585 661	0.170 m	0.650 m	0.672 m	-3.010 m	3.010 m
121	Evergreen shrubland	8 829	0.412 m	1.304 m	1.367 m	-3.010 m	3.010 m
122	Deciduous shrubland	1 033 891	0.311 m	0.951 m	1.000 m	-3.010 m	3.010 m
130	Grassland	6 781 919	0.012 m	0.628 m	0.628 m	-3.010 m	3.020 m
140	Lichens and mosses	120 161	-0.113 m	0.822 m	0.830 m	-3.010 m	3.010 m
150	Sparse vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (<15%)	5 586 243	-0.216 m	0.545 m	0.587 m	-3.010 m	3.020 m
151	Sparse tree (<15%)	-	-	-	-	-	-
152	Sparse shrub (<15%)	35 600	-0.094 m	0.479 m	0.488 m	-3.010 m	3.020 m
153	Sparse herbaceous cover (<15%)	278 655	-0.022 m	0.477 m	0.477 m	-3.010 m	3.020 m
160	Tree cover, flooded, fresh or brackish water	244 271	0.364 m	0.935 m	1.004 m	-3.010 m	3.010 m
170	Tree cover, flooded, saline water	73 542	0.413 m	1.155 m	1.227 m	-3.010 m	3.020 m
180	Shrub or herbaceous cover, flooded, fresh/saline/brackish water	1 254 719	-0.037 m	0.683 m	0.684 m	-3.010 m	3.010 m
190	Urban areas	244 200	0.394 m	1.043 m	1.115 m	-3.010 m	3.020 m
200	Bare areas	17 964 222	-0.082 m	0.480 m	0.487 m	-3.010 m	3.010 m
201	Consolidated bare areas	58 964	-0.046 m	0.517 m	0.519 m	-3.010 m	3.010 m
202	Unconsolidated bare areas	63 488	-0.018 m	0.478 m	0.479 m	-3.010 m	3.010 m
210	Water bodies	379 785	-0.151 m	0.994 m	1.006 m	-3.010 m	3.020 m
220	Permanent snow and ice	6 991	-0.620 m	1.608 m	1.723 m	-3.010 m	3.010 m
All	Total	59 396 074	0.066 m	0.706 m	0.709 m	-3.010 m	3.020 m

Table 41 – (Copernicus DEM GLO-90 – ICESat-1 LE95) error statistics - classified with C3S-LC 2013.

Figure 117 - (Copernicus DEM GLO-90 – ICESat-1 LE95) errors classified with C3S-LC 2013.

	Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, closed to open (>15%)
	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%)
	Cropland, rainfed
	Shrubland
	Grassland

[See map and full legend on VtWeb](#)

	<= -9 metres
	-9 metres to -3 metres
	-3 metres to -1.5 metres
	-1.5 metres to -0.5 metres
	-0.5 metres to 0.5 metres
	0.5 metres to 1.5 metres
	1.5 metres to 3 metres
	3 metres to 9 metres
	>= 9 metres

Figure 118 - (Copernicus DEM GLO-90 – ICESat-1 LE95) errors histogram - classified with C3S-LC 2013.

Globally, one may observe similar distributions of errors per classes between GLO-30 and GLO-90. This remark applies to the five LIDAR (see the next sections).

One may observe that the “sparse vegetation” class (150) shows a tail of distribution of negative values, which is also observed for the (GLO-30 – ICESat-1) study. This indicates that Copernicus DEM GLO-90 is below ICESat-1 reference data for many pixels of this class. Histograms of the other classes are mostly right-skewed, with positive errors indicating GLO-90 is higher than ICESat-2 terrain only data for these classes.

4.6.2.12 Copernicus DEM GLO-90 – ICESat-2 terrain only

DN	Class	Count	Mean	Std Dev	RMSE	Min	Max
0	No Data	-	-	-	-	-	-
10	Cropland, rainfed	687 147	0.366 m	1.201 m	1.255 m	-6.240 m	6.250 m
11	Cropland, rainfed, herbaceous cover	728 620	0.281 m	1.168 m	1.202 m	-6.240 m	6.250 m
12	Cropland, rainfed, tree or shrub cover	19 868	0.518 m	1.641 m	1.721 m	-6.210 m	6.250 m
20	Cropland, irrigated or post-flooding	219 131	0.326 m	1.057 m	1.106 m	-6.230 m	6.250 m
30	Mosaic cropland (>50%) / natural vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (<50%)	222 784	0.558 m	1.512 m	1.611 m	-6.240 m	6.250 m
40	Mosaic natural vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (>50%) / cropland (<50%)	238 154	0.486 m	1.583 m	1.656 m	-6.230 m	6.250 m
50	Tree cover, broadleaved, evergreen, closed to open (>15%)	37 745	2.372 m	2.112 m	3.176 m	-6.240 m	6.250 m
60	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%)	142 331	2.469 m	2.291 m	3.369 m	-6.230 m	6.250 m
61	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, closed (>40%)	19 447	2.477 m	1.912 m	3.129 m	-6.210 m	6.250 m
62	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, open (15-40%)	131 904	1.786 m	1.565 m	2.375 m	-6.220 m	6.250 m
70	Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, closed to open (>15%)	196 926	1.961 m	2.374 m	3.079 m	-6.240 m	6.250 m
71	Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, closed (>40%)	184 452	2.139 m	2.086 m	2.988 m	-6.240 m	6.250 m
72	Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, open (15-40%)	48	-0.304 m	3.150 m	3.164 m	-6.230 m	5.810 m
80	Tree cover, needleleaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%)	255 813	2.118 m	2.356 m	3.168 m	-6.230 m	6.250 m
81	Tree cover, needleleaved, deciduous, closed (>40%)	24	0.275 m	2.091 m	2.109 m	-4.560 m	5.210 m
82	Tree cover, needleleaved, deciduous, open (15-40%)	-	-	-	-	-	-
90	Tree cover, mixed leaf type (broadleaved and needleleaved)	61 612	3.068 m	2.221 m	3.788 m	-6.240 m	6.250 m
100	Mosaic tree and shrub (>50%) / herbaceous cover (<50%)	165 633	0.762 m	1.800 m	1.954 m	-6.240 m	6.250 m
110	Mosaic herbaceous cover (>50%) / tree and shrub (<50%)	80 578	0.285 m	1.504 m	1.531 m	-6.240 m	6.250 m
120	Shrubland	1 382 086	0.344 m	1.280 m	1.325 m	-6.240 m	6.250 m
121	Evergreen shrubland	5 843	0.388 m	2.620 m	2.649 m	-6.230 m	6.250 m
122	Deciduous shrubland	257 267	0.694 m	1.708 m	1.844 m	-6.240 m	6.250 m
130	Grassland	1 633 855	0.086 m	1.208 m	1.211 m	-6.240 m	6.250 m
140	Lichens and mosses	19 956	-0.289 m	1.667 m	1.691 m	-6.230 m	6.240 m
150	Sparse vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (<15%)	1 532 349	-0.176 m	0.932 m	0.948 m	-6.240 m	6.250 m
151	Sparse tree (<15%)	-	-	-	-	-	-
152	Sparse shrub (<15%)	8 299	-0.017 m	1.308 m	1.308 m	-6.220 m	6.200 m
153	Sparse herbaceous cover (<15%)	92 979	-0.020 m	1.135 m	1.135 m	-6.240 m	6.250 m
160	Tree cover, flooded, fresh or brackish water	22 416	1.572 m	1.840 m	2.420 m	-6.210 m	6.250 m
170	Tree cover, flooded, saline water	8 683	1.300 m	1.949 m	2.343 m	-6.130 m	6.250 m
180	Shrub or herbaceous cover, flooded, fresh/saline/brackish water	86 362	0.312 m	1.196 m	1.236 m	-6.220 m	6.250 m
190	Urban areas	77 336	1.184 m	1.690 m	2.064 m	-6.240 m	6.250 m
200	Bare areas	5 248 617	-0.035 m	0.991 m	0.992 m	-6.240 m	6.250 m
201	Consolidated bare areas	15 770	-0.001 m	1.224 m	1.224 m	-6.230 m	6.220 m
202	Unconsolidated bare areas	18 504	-0.014 m	1.076 m	1.076 m	-6.170 m	6.240 m
210	Water bodies	25 709	0.508 m	1.892 m	1.959 m	-6.220 m	6.250 m
220	Permanent snow and ice	9 991	0.337 m	3.142 m	3.160 m	-6.240 m	6.250 m
All	Total	13 838 239	0.271 m	1.391 m	1.417 m	-6.240 m	6.250 m

Table 42 – (Copernicus DEM GLO-90 – ICESat-2 terrain only LE95) error statistics - classified with C3S-LC 2013.

Figure 119 - (Copernicus DEM GLO-90 – ICESat-2 terrain only LE95) errors classified with C3S-LC 2013.

	Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, closed to open (>15%)
	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%)
	Cropland, rainfed
	Shrubland
	Grassland

[See map and full legend on VtWeb](#)

	<= -9 metres
	-9 metres to -3 metres
	-3 metres to -1.5 metres
	-1.5 metres to -0.5 metres
	-0.5 metres to 0.5 metres
	0.5 metres to 1.5 metres
	1.5 metres to 3 metres
	3 metres to 9 metres
	>= 9 metres

Figure 120 - (Copernicus DEM GLO-90 – ICESat-2 terrain only LE95) errors histogram - classified with C3S-LC 2013.

As observed for the (GLO-90 – ICESat-1) study, the leftward skewness of the “sparse vegetation” class (150) indicates that GLO-90 is below ICESat-2 terrain only reference data. Other classes are mostly right-skewed, with positive errors indicating GLO-90 is higher than ICESat-2 terrain only data.

4.6.2.13 Copernicus DEM GLO-90 – ICESat-2 terrain with canopy

DN	Class	Count	Mean	Std Dev	RMSE	Min	Max
0	No Data	-	-	-	-	-	-
10	Cropland, rainfed	663 605	-1.020 m	2.905 m	3.079 m	-11.310 m	11.270 m
11	Cropland, rainfed, herbaceous cover	701 252	-1.113 m	2.848 m	3.057 m	-11.310 m	11.250 m
12	Cropland, rainfed, tree or shrub cover	19 091	-2.423 m	3.608 m	4.346 m	-11.300 m	11.190 m
20	Cropland, irrigated or post-flooding	212 971	-1.088 m	2.783 m	2.988 m	-11.300 m	11.240 m
30	Mosaic cropland (>50%) / natural vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (<50%)	210 221	-2.084 m	3.539 m	4.107 m	-11.310 m	11.270 m
40	Mosaic natural vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (>50%) / cropland (<50%)	230 058	-1.729 m	3.392 m	3.807 m	-11.300 m	11.250 m
50	Tree cover, broadleaved, evergreen, closed to open (>15%)	49 031	-5.591 m	4.045 m	6.901 m	-11.310 m	11.270 m
60	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%)	188 151	-6.265 m	3.786 m	7.320 m	-11.310 m	11.270 m
61	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, closed (>40%)	22 897	-6.180 m	3.228 m	6.972 m	-11.300 m	11.260 m
62	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, open (15-40%)	122 909	-5.448 m	3.551 m	6.503 m	-11.300 m	11.260 m
70	Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, closed to open (>15%)	223 280	-6.398 m	3.434 m	7.261 m	-11.310 m	11.260 m
71	Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, closed (>40%)	201 158	-6.424 m	2.802 m	7.009 m	-11.310 m	11.270 m
72	Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, open (15-40%)	54	-4.720 m	4.618 m	6.604 m	-11.170 m	7.800 m
80	Tree cover, needleleaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%)	224 529	-6.476 m	3.709 m	7.463 m	-11.310 m	11.270 m
81	Tree cover, needleleaved, deciduous, closed (>40%)	29	-1.776 m	6.401 m	6.643 m	-10.350 m	9.950 m
82	Tree cover, needleleaved, deciduous, open (15-40%)	-	-	-	-	-	-
90	Tree cover, mixed leaf type (broadleaved and needleleaved)	98 892	-7.121 m	3.227 m	7.818 m	-11.310 m	11.270 m
100	Mosaic tree and shrub (>50%) / herbaceous cover (<50%)	158 563	-3.352 m	3.842 m	5.099 m	-11.310 m	11.260 m
110	Mosaic herbaceous cover (>50%) / tree and shrub (<50%)	79 928	-1.359 m	3.137 m	3.419 m	-11.310 m	11.240 m
120	Shrubland	1 375 487	-1.260 m	2.949 m	3.207 m	-11.310 m	11.270 m
121	Evergreen shrubland	6 128	-4.652 m	3.782 m	5.996 m	-11.310 m	11.190 m
122	Deciduous shrubland	225 701	-4.056 m	4.122 m	5.783 m	-11.310 m	11.260 m
130	Grassland	1 619 950	-0.505 m	2.188 m	2.246 m	-11.310 m	11.270 m
140	Lichens and mosses	20 017	-1.803 m	2.807 m	3.336 m	-11.280 m	11.260 m
150	Sparse vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (<15%)	1 536 871	-0.307 m	1.332 m	1.367 m	-11.310 m	11.270 m
151	Sparse tree (<15%)	-	-	-	-	-	-
152	Sparse shrub (<15%)	8 440	-0.256 m	2.026 m	2.042 m	-11.300 m	11.010 m
153	Sparse herbaceous cover (<15%)	94 070	-0.054 m	1.488 m	1.489 m	-11.290 m	11.190 m
160	Tree cover, flooded, fresh or brackish water	25 569	-5.699 m	3.096 m	6.485 m	-11.310 m	11.270 m
170	Tree cover, flooded, saline water	9 460	-3.849 m	3.350 m	5.102 m	-11.310 m	11.040 m
180	Shrub or herbaceous cover, flooded, fresh/saline/brackish water	83 425	-2.076 m	3.116 m	3.744 m	-11.310 m	11.190 m
190	Urban areas	69 101	-4.170 m	4.016 m	5.790 m	-11.310 m	11.240 m
200	Bare areas	5 285 125	-0.044 m	1.227 m	1.228 m	-11.310 m	11.270 m
201	Consolidated bare areas	16 072	-0.130 m	1.808 m	1.812 m	-11.260 m	11.120 m
202	Unconsolidated bare areas	18 559	-0.042 m	1.218 m	1.219 m	-11.310 m	11.130 m
210	Water bodies	24 631	-2.852 m	3.608 m	4.599 m	-11.310 m	11.190 m
220	Permanent snow and ice	13 014	-0.757 m	5.284 m	5.338 m	-11.310 m	11.260 m
All	Total	13 838 239	-1.102 m	2.898 m	3.100 m	-11.310 m	11.270 m

Table 43 – (Copernicus DEM GLO-90 – ICESat-2 terrain with canopy LE95) error statistics - classified with C3S-LC 2013.

Figure 121 - (Copernicus DEM GLO-90 – ICESat-2 terrain with canopy LE95) errors classified with C3S-LC 2013.

	Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, closed to open (>15%)
	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%)
	Cropland, rainfed
	Shrubland
	Grassland

[See map and full legend on VtWeb](#)

	<= -9 metres
	-9 metres to -3 metres
	-3 metres to -1.5 metres
	-1.5 metres to -0.5 metres
	-0.5 metres to 0.5 metres
	0.5 metres to 1.5 metres
	1.5 metres to 3 metres
	3 metres to 9 metres
	>= 9 metres

Figure 122 - (Copernicus DEM GLO-90 – ICESat-2 terrain with canopy LE95) errors histogram - classified with C3S-LC 2013.

As opposed to the (GLO-90 – ICESat-2 terrain only) histogram, one may observe a long tail of distribution of negative values, mostly represented by the “shrubland” class (120). This leftward skewness illustrates that Copernicus DEM GLO-90 is below the ICESat-2 terrain with canopy.

4.6.2.14 Copernicus DEM GLO-90 – GEDI lowest mode

DN	Class	Count	Mean	Std Dev	RMSE	Min	Max
0	No Data	-	-	-	-	-	-
10	Cropland, rainfed	13 747 584	0.316 m	2.434 m	2.455 m	-15.010 m	15.040 m
11	Cropland, rainfed, herbaceous cover	17 822 325	0.131 m	1.963 m	1.968 m	-15.010 m	15.040 m
12	Cropland, rainfed, tree or shrub cover	395 792	1.205 m	3.657 m	3.850 m	-15.000 m	15.040 m
20	Cropland, irrigated or post-flooding	3 975 075	0.203 m	1.826 m	1.837 m	-15.010 m	15.040 m
30	Mosaic cropland (>50%) / natural vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (<50%)	5 739 108	1.037 m	3.661 m	3.805 m	-15.010 m	15.040 m
40	Mosaic natural vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (>50%) / cropland (<50%)	6 477 938	1.090 m	3.923 m	4.072 m	-15.010 m	15.040 m
50	Tree cover, broadleaved, evergreen, closed to open (>15%)	7 708 975	6.400 m	5.557 m	8.476 m	-15.010 m	15.040 m
60	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%)	9 179 840	4.667 m	4.839 m	6.723 m	-15.010 m	15.040 m
61	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, closed (>40%)	1 255 088	3.989 m	4.887 m	6.308 m	-15.010 m	15.040 m
62	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, open (15-40%)	4 987 798	2.134 m	2.975 m	3.661 m	-15.010 m	15.040 m
70	Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, closed to open (>15%)	6 511 744	4.548 m	5.403 m	7.063 m	-15.010 m	15.050 m
71	Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, closed (>40%)	4 109 168	3.845 m	4.169 m	5.672 m	-15.010 m	15.040 m
72	Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, open (15-40%)	1 779	0.875 m	6.125 m	6.187 m	-15.000 m	15.000 m
80	Tree cover, needleleaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%)	4 440 054	4.248 m	4.559 m	6.231 m	-15.010 m	15.040 m
81	Tree cover, needleleaved, deciduous, closed (>40%)	8 190	3.993 m	6.308 m	7.466 m	-14.970 m	15.040 m
82	Tree cover, needleleaved, deciduous, open (15-40%)	-	-	-	-	-	-
90	Tree cover, mixed leaf type (broadleaved and needleleaved)	2 639 180	5.355 m	4.856 m	7.229 m	-15.010 m	15.050 m
100	Mosaic tree and shrub (>50%) / herbaceous cover (<50%)	4 812 715	1.738 m	4.433 m	4.762 m	-15.010 m	15.040 m
110	Mosaic herbaceous cover (>50%) / tree and shrub (<50%)	1 716 948	0.686 m	3.867 m	3.927 m	-15.010 m	15.050 m
120	Shrubland	19 674 941	0.263 m	2.840 m	2.852 m	-15.010 m	15.040 m
121	Evergreen shrubland	215 047	4.852 m	6.191 m	7.865 m	-15.010 m	15.040 m
122	Deciduous shrubland	2 855 213	0.638 m	2.444 m	2.526 m	-15.010 m	15.040 m
130	Grassland	28 674 290	-0.023 m	2.838 m	2.838 m	-15.010 m	15.050 m
140	Lichens and mosses	20 943	-0.228 m	3.588 m	3.595 m	-14.950 m	15.040 m
150	Sparse vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (<15%)	16 939 899	-0.406 m	1.968 m	2.010 m	-15.010 m	15.050 m
151	Sparse tree (<15%)	-	-	-	-	-	-
152	Sparse shrub (<15%)	68 423	-0.020 m	4.426 m	4.426 m	-15.010 m	15.050 m
153	Sparse herbaceous cover (<15%)	765 804	-0.212 m	2.597 m	2.606 m	-15.010 m	15.050 m
160	Tree cover, flooded, fresh or brackish water	929 770	3.825 m	4.971 m	6.272 m	-14.980 m	15.040 m
170	Tree cover, flooded, saline water	242 622	2.510 m	4.247 m	4.933 m	-15.010 m	15.050 m
180	Shrub or herbaceous cover, flooded, fresh/saline/brackish water	1 719 784	-0.048 m	1.812 m	1.812 m	-15.010 m	15.040 m
190	Urban areas	1 285 126	1.153 m	2.342 m	2.610 m	-15.000 m	15.050 m
200	Bare areas	35 492 208	-0.289 m	2.084 m	2.104 m	-15.010 m	15.040 m
201	Consolidated bare areas	162 417	-0.115 m	3.625 m	3.627 m	-15.010 m	15.040 m
202	Unconsolidated bare areas	175 848	-0.307 m	1.865 m	1.890 m	-15.000 m	15.040 m
210	Water bodies	686 825	0.612 m	3.240 m	3.297 m	-15.010 m	15.050 m
220	Permanent snow and ice	310 200	1.277 m	5.979 m	6.114 m	-15.010 m	15.040 m
All	Total	205 748 661	1.036 m	3.731 m	3.872 m	-15.010 m	15.050 m

Table 44 – (Copernicus DEM GLO-90 – GEDI lowest mode LE95) error statistics - classified with C3S-LC 2013.

Figure 123 - (Copernicus DEM GLO-90 – GEDI lowest mode LE95) errors classified with C3S-LC 2013.

	Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, closed to open (>15%)
	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%)
	Cropland, rainfed
	Shrubland
	Grassland

[See map and full legend on VtWeb](#)

	<= -9 metres
	-9 metres to -3 metres
	-3 metres to -1.5 metres
	-1.5 metres to -0.5 metres
	-0.5 metres to 0.5 metres
	0.5 metres to 1.5 metres
	1.5 metres to 3 metres
	3 metres to 9 metres
	>= 9 metres

Figure 124 - (Copernicus DEM GLO-90 – GEDI lowest mode LE95) errors histogram - classified with C3S-LC 2013.

One may observe a long tail of distribution of positive values, mostly represented by the “broad-leaved” tree cover classes (50 and 60). This rightward skewness illustrates that Copernicus DEM GLO-90 is higher than GEDI lowest mode for these classes.

4.6.2.15 Copernicus DEM GLO-90 – GEDI highest return

DN	Class	Count	Mean	Std Dev	RMSE	Min	Max
0	No Data	-	-	-	-	-	-
10	Cropland, rainfed	13 492 123	-5.048 m	2.994 m	5.869 m	-16.770 m	16.640 m
11	Cropland, rainfed, herbaceous cover	17 562 156	-4.748 m	2.591 m	5.409 m	-16.770 m	16.640 m
12	Cropland, rainfed, tree or shrub cover	388 283	-6.268 m	3.676 m	7.267 m	-16.770 m	16.620 m
20	Cropland, irrigated or post-flooding	3 899 495	-5.005 m	2.956 m	5.813 m	-16.770 m	16.610 m
30	Mosaic cropland (>50%) / natural vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (<50%)	5 575 916	-5.768 m	3.846 m	6.933 m	-16.770 m	16.640 m
40	Mosaic natural vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (>50%) / cropland (<50%)	6 311 977	-5.751 m	3.960 m	6.982 m	-16.770 m	16.640 m
50	Tree cover, broadleaved, evergreen, closed to open (>15%)	9 751 923	-8.769 m	5.288 m	10.240 m	-16.780 m	16.640 m
60	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%)	9 534 721	-7.906 m	4.857 m	9.279 m	-16.770 m	16.640 m
61	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, closed (>40%)	1 237 877	-7.898 m	4.524 m	9.102 m	-16.770 m	16.640 m
62	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, open (15-40%)	4 917 660	-7.456 m	3.534 m	8.251 m	-16.770 m	16.640 m
70	Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, closed to open (>15%)	6 603 483	-8.270 m	5.403 m	9.879 m	-16.780 m	16.640 m
71	Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, closed (>40%)	4 161 304	-7.951 m	4.484 m	9.128 m	-16.780 m	16.640 m
72	Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, open (15-40%)	1 566	-7.656 m	5.652 m	9.516 m	-16.750 m	16.530 m
80	Tree cover, needleleaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%)	4 288 753	-7.578 m	5.138 m	9.155 m	-16.770 m	16.640 m
81	Tree cover, needleleaved, deciduous, closed (>40%)	6 274	-6.121 m	8.709 m	10.645 m	-16.770 m	16.630 m
82	Tree cover, needleleaved, deciduous, open (15-40%)	-	-	-	-	-	-
90	Tree cover, mixed leaf type (broadleaved and needleleaved)	2 750 896	-8.493 m	4.876 m	9.793 m	-16.780 m	16.640 m
100	Mosaic tree and shrub (>50%) / herbaceous cover (<50%)	4 740 990	-6.554 m	4.382 m	7.884 m	-16.770 m	16.640 m
110	Mosaic herbaceous cover (>50%) / tree and shrub (<50%)	1 673 478	-5.886 m	3.734 m	6.971 m	-16.780 m	16.640 m
120	Shrubland	19 417 363	-5.500 m	3.024 m	6.277 m	-16.770 m	16.640 m
121	Evergreen shrubland	250 288	-6.532 m	6.583 m	9.274 m	-16.770 m	16.640 m
122	Deciduous shrubland	2 785 486	-7.175 m	3.583 m	8.019 m	-16.770 m	16.640 m
130	Grassland	28 069 298	-5.063 m	2.986 m	5.878 m	-16.780 m	16.640 m
140	Lichens and mosses	20 504	-6.200 m	3.367 m	7.055 m	-16.770 m	15.680 m
150	Sparse vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (<15%)	16 823 781	-4.663 m	2.103 m	5.116 m	-16.780 m	16.640 m
151	Sparse tree (<15%)	-	-	-	-	-	-
152	Sparse shrub (<15%)	66 429	-5.018 m	4.120 m	6.493 m	-16.780 m	16.630 m
153	Sparse herbaceous cover (<15%)	756 622	-4.645 m	2.589 m	5.318 m	-16.780 m	16.590 m
160	Tree cover, flooded, fresh or brackish water	989 391	-7.753 m	4.186 m	8.811 m	-16.770 m	16.640 m
170	Tree cover, flooded, saline water	247 681	-6.858 m	3.573 m	7.733 m	-16.780 m	16.620 m
180	Shrub or herbaceous cover, flooded, fresh/saline/brackish water	1 706 605	-5.056 m	2.393 m	5.594 m	-16.770 m	16.510 m
190	Urban areas	1 201 118	-7.484 m	3.677 m	8.339 m	-16.780 m	16.510 m
200	Bare areas	35 222 240	-4.347 m	2.064 m	4.812 m	-16.770 m	16.640 m
201	Consolidated bare areas	157 163	-5.092 m	3.490 m	6.173 m	-16.770 m	16.590 m
202	Unconsolidated bare areas	174 792	-4.419 m	1.881 m	4.803 m	-16.770 m	15.700 m
210	Water bodies	663 440	-5.716 m	3.658 m	6.786 m	-16.780 m	16.630 m
220	Permanent snow and ice	297 585	-4.682 m	6.733 m	8.201 m	-16.770 m	16.640 m
All	Total	205 748 661	-5.704 m	3.683 m	6.789 m	-16.780 m	16.640 m

Table 45 – (Copernicus DEM GLO-90 – GEDI highest return LE95) error statistics - classified with C3S-LC 2013.

Figure 125 - (Copernicus DEM GLO-90 – GEDI highest return LE95) errors classified with C3S-LC 2013.

	Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, closed to open (>15%)
	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%)
	Cropland, rainfed
	Shrubland
	Grassland

[See map and full legend on VtWeb](#)

	<= -9 metres
	-9 metres to -3 metres
	-3 metres to -1.5 metres
	-1.5 metres to -0.5 metres
	-0.5 metres to 0.5 metres
	0.5 metres to 1.5 metres
	1.5 metres to 3 metres
	3 metres to 9 metres
	>= 9 metres

Figure 126 - (Copernicus DEM GLO-90 – GEDI highest return LE95) errors histogram - classified with C3S-LC 2013.

One may observe a long tail of distribution of negative values, mostly represented by the “broad-leaved” tree cover classes (50 and 60). As opposed to the rightward skewness of the (GLO-90 – GEDI highest return) tree cover histograms, this leftward skewness illustrates that Copernicus DEM GLO-90 is lower than GEDI highest return.

4.6.3 Canopy classes vs. height errors

This section aims to give an overview of the Copernicus DEMs vs. LiDARs errors over canopy. The (Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – GEDI lowest mode) and the (Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – GEDI highest return) are chosen for this study, as the high number of valid GEDI samples ensures representative amounts of differences over tree cover classes.

To enable the comparison of patterns (acting as “signatures” of each class), all the curves of this section have been normalized; i.e., the frequency of one class is not computed dividing by the total number of samples but by the number of samples for this class only.

4.6.3.1 Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – GEDI lowest mode

4.6.3.1.1 Canopy opening vs. height errors

DN	Class	Count	Mean	Std Dev	RMSE	Min	Max
60	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%)	9 020 629	4.611 m	4.352 m	6.341 m	-14.200 m	14.230 m
61	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, closed (>40%)	1 265 356	4.217 m	4.323 m	6.039 m	-14.190 m	14.230 m
62	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, open (15-40%)	4 983 322	2.141 m	2.791 m	3.517 m	-14.200 m	14.230 m

Figure 127 - (Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – GEDI lowest mode LE95) errors vs. C3S-LC 2013 varying canopy opening.

In Figure 127, the height differences between GLO-30 and GEDI lowest mode are analysed over tree cover classes of C3S-LC 2013. In this example, the **same leaf shape** and the **same leaf life span** are considered, **only the canopy opening varies**.

- Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, open (15-40%) - Height differences over open tree cover (DN = 62) result in a unimodal distribution, reaching a mode around 0.15 cm

with a positive skewness. For this class, GEDI and TanDEM-X are coinciding at terrain level.

- Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, closed (>40%) - One may see three different modes over closed tree cover (**DN = 61**), respectively reaching 1.64 m for the main mode (m_1), 0.17 m for the second mode (m_2), 6.95 m for the third mode (m_3). For this class, mode m_2 shows the coincidence of GEDI and TanDEM-X at terrain level. Mode m_3 demonstrates the ability of GEDI data to get a terrain level measurement while TanDEM-X has been backscattered at the top of canopy. Mode m_1 looks more enigmatic and could exhibit the cases when GEDI reaches the terrain while TanDEM-X is backscattered at the top of low vegetation like shrubs.
- Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%) - The most represented class corresponds to the unspecified canopy opening (**DN = 60**), for which a high positive skewness is visible. For this class, the long tail of distribution looks like an addition of the tails of distribution of the two precedent classes. One may be surprised by the linearity of the positive tail of distribution, which witnesses that all the tree heights are represented proportionally with regular decreasing rate.

4.6.3.1.2 Leaf shape vs. height errors

Figure 128 - (Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – GEDI lowest mode LE95) errors vs. C3S-LC 2013 varying leaf shape.

In Figure 128, the height differences between GLO-30 and GEDI lowest mode are analysed over tree cover classes of C3S-LC 2013. In this example, the **same leaf life span** and the **same canopy opening** are considered, **only the leaf shape varies**.

Very similar statistics and histograms are observable between the Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%) and Tree cover, needleleaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%) classes. In this case, considering needle leaved vs. broad leaved trees does not seem to have an impact on the difference between Copernicus DEM GLO-30 and GEDI lowest mode.

4.6.3.1.3 Leaf life span vs. height errors

Figure 129 - (Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – GEDI lowest mode LE95) errors vs. C3S-LC 2013 varying leaf life span.

In Figure 129, the height differences between GLO-30 and GEDI lowest mode are analysed over tree cover classes of C3S-LC 2013. In this example, the **same leaf shape** and the **same canopy opening** are considered, **only the leaf life span varies**.

- Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%) – Height differences over deciduous tree cover (**DN = 60**) highlight a high positive skewness, for which all the tree heights are represented proportionally with regular decreasing rate.
- Tree cover, broadleaved, evergreen, closed to open (>15%) – As opposed to the previous class, the evergreen tree cover (**DN = 50**) is not decreasing in the positive errors. One may see two modes over this distribution, respectively reaching -0.34 m for the first mode (m_1) and 14.23 m for the second mode. For this class, mode m_1 shows the coincidence of GEDI and TanDEM-X at terrain level, probably in cases of open canopy. Mode m_2 demonstrates the ability of GEDI data to get a terrain level measurement while TanDEM-X has been backscattered at the top of canopy.

4.6.3.2 Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – GEDI highest return

4.6.3.2.1 Canopy opening vs. height errors

DN	Class	Count	Mean	Std Dev	RMSE	Min	Max
60	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%)	9 456 576	-8.027 m	4.011 m	8.973 m	-15.310 m	15.180 m
61	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, closed (>40%)	1 239 215	-8.252 m	3.583 m	8.997 m	-15.310 m	15.160 m
62	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, open (15-40%)	4 886 755	-7.430 m	3.164 m	8.075 m	-15.310 m	15.170 m

Figure 130 - (Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – GEDI highest return LE95) errors vs. C3S-LC 2013 varying canopy opening.

In Figure 130, the height differences between GLO-30 and GEDI highest return are analysed over tree cover classes of C3S-LC 2013. In this example, the **same leaf shape** and the **same leaf life span** are considered, **only the canopy opening varies**.

The overall shape of the three distributions is similar. One may see that each of the three distributions can be decomposed into two modes:

- **Mode m_1** – The closest mode to 0 metres of error. The presence of this mode can be explained by the (GEDI lowest mode – highest return) difference, which is always negative **even in bare areas, the most represented class**. One may see that the more open the canopy is, the more predominant the m_1 mode is in every distribution. As a consequence, the m_1 mode may correspond to cases where both Copernicus DEM and GEDI highest return correspond to the ground or low vegetation.
- **Mode m_2** – Multiple events may explain the negative differences forming mode M_2 . One may note that the highest elevation within GEDI footprint corresponds to the GEDI highest return. As a consequence, punctual high features, such as high trees, or sudden height changes, as the openings of the canopy, can lead to big height differences. In such cases, GEDI highest return corresponds to the top of the highest

tree within its footprint, whereas the Copernicus DEM height corresponds to a top of canopy height or terrain height, explaining such height differences.

4.6.3.2.2 Leaf shape vs. height errors

Figure 131 - (Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – GEDI highest return LE95) errors vs. C3S-LC 2013 varying leaf shape.

In Figure 131, the height differences between GLO-30 and GEDI highest return are analysed over tree cover classes of C3S-LC 2013. In this example, the **same leaf life span** and the **same canopy opening** are considered, **only the leaf shape varies**.

The overall shape of the two distributions is similar. One may see that each distribution can be decomposed into two modes:

- Mode m_1 – The closest mode to 0 metres of error. One may see this mode higher for needle leaved trees than to broad leaved trees.
- Mode m_2 – The furthest mode to 0 metres of error. One may see this mode lower for needle leaved trees than to broad leaved trees.

Overall, one may see that the main mode of the needleleaved class is m_1 , whereas the main mode of the broadleaved class is m_2 .

4.6.3.2.3 Leaf life span vs. height errors

Figure 132 - (Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – GEDI highest return LE95) errors vs. C3S-LC 2013 varying leaf life span.

In Figure 132, the height differences between GLO-30 and GEDI highest return are analysed over tree cover classes of C3S-LC 2013. In this example, the **same leaf shape** and the **same canopy opening** are considered, **only the leaf life span varies**.

The overall shape of the two distributions is similar. One may see that each distribution can be decomposed into two modes:

- Mode m₁ – The closest mode to 0 metres of error. One may see this mode higher for deciduous trees than to evergreen trees.
- Mode m₂ – The furthest mode to 0 metres of error. One may see this mode lower for deciduous trees than to evergreen trees.

Overall, one may see that the main mode of the deciduous class is m₁, whereas the main mode of the evergreen class is m₂.

4.7 Sentinel-2 orthorectification - Comparison of Copernicus DEM GLO-30 vs. GLO-90

In this section, Copernicus DEM GLO-30 and GLO-90 are used to orthorectify Sentinel-2 data. The goal of this study is to estimate the **delta parallax** between Sentinel-2 products respectively orthorectified with Copernicus DEM GLO-30 and GLO-90. If the estimated **delta parallax** is high, using the highest resolution DEM (GLO-30) is recommended, otherwise, using the lowest resolution DEM (GLO-90) should be sufficient.

4.7.1 Principle

The **delta parallax** is illustrated in the following figure.

Figure 133 - Illustration of the difference of parallax corrections.

The “**delta parallax**” matches the difference of parallax corrections by using COP-DEM GLO-90 or COP-DEM GLO-30. This difference can be estimated using the following equation.

$$\Delta_{parallax} \approx (h_{90} - h_{30}) \times \tan(\alpha) \quad (\text{eq. 10})$$

Where:

- h_{90} is the height of Copernicus DEM GLO-90
- h_{30} is the height of Copernicus DEM GLO-30
- α is the incidence angle

4.7.2 Case studies

4.7.2.1 Global view

Hereafter, the delta parallax is compared over two study areas: the Grand Canyon (Arizona) and the surroundings of Kabul (Afghanistan). These regions have been selected because of their high relief variation, featuring cliffs and valleys.

Figure 134 - Global view of the two study areas for evaluation of DEMs impact on orthorectification.

Figure 135 - Close up view to the two study areas: Grand Canyon and north of Kabul.

Figure 134 and Figure 135 respectively show a global view and close up view of the two study areas in a natural colour composite. The footprint of each tile that composes the full swath is displayed in black.

For each study area, the following views show the **incidence angle** retrieved from the metadata of Sentinel-2 products, the **height difference** between Copernicus DEM GLO-90 and Copernicus DEM GLO-30 and the **delta parallax** computed with the associated formula.

4.7.2.2 Delta parallax over the Grand Canyon (Arizona)

The following figure illustrates the computation of the estimated **delta parallax** over the Grand Canyon (Arizona).

Figure 136 - Grand Canyon - S2 incidence angle, DEMs delta height and estimated delta parallax ([2D view](#)).

Figure 137- Grand Canyon – 3D view of the delta parallax ([3D view](#)).

As shown in the 3D view above (Figure 137), the maximum difference in parallax correction, and therefore the error induced by a less resolved 90m DEM, is greatest at the cliff edges of Grand Canyon. This phenomenon is further accentuated in the enclosed parts forming a small diameter circus.

As seen in the incidence angle view, the incidence angle varies from 0° to 11.587°. The MSI (Multi-Spectral Instrument) onboard Sentinel-2A and Sentinel-2B has a Field of View of 20.6°. Flying at 786 km of altitude, the maximum theoretical incidence angle is about 11.587°.

In Figure 136, the mean of **delta parallax** is close to 0 metre but **the maximum delta parallax is greater than 10 metres**, which is the Ground Sampling Distance (GSD) of Sentinel-2 data.

4.7.2.3 Delta parallax over the North of Kabul (Afghanistan)

The following figure illustrates the computation of the estimated **delta parallax** over the North of Kabul (Afghanistan).

Figure 138 - North of Kabul - S2 incidence angle, DEMs delta height and estimated delta parallax (2D view).

Figure 139- North of Kabul – 3D view of the delta parallax ([3D view](#)).

As shown in the 3D view above (Figure 139), the maximum difference in parallax correction is observed in very narrow valleys (here the Darrahe Ajar Valley located about 130 km east-northeast of Kabul). More precisely, the maxima are located at the places of the slope breaks where the GLO-90 will smooth out these first derivative discontinuities.

As seen in the previous case study (see section 4.7.2.2), the mean of **delta parallax** is close to 0 metre but **the maximum delta parallax is greater than 10 metres**, which is the Ground Sampling Distance (GSD) of Sentinel-2 data.

To obtain the best quality of orthorectification, we strongly recommend using COP-DEM GLO-30 and not GLO-90.

5. CONCLUSIONS

5.1 Mission / product assessment overview

5.1.1 Comparing the “FAIR”

As indicated in section 3.2.1, VisioTerra has introduced an individual notation of the four FAIR principles to assess a global notation more traceable. Table below summarizes these notations comparing the capabilities of Copernicus DEMs with those of the other global DEMs.

	Findable /4	Accessible /3	Interoperable /3	Reusable /4	FAIR /14
SRTM	3	3	1.5	3	10.5
ASTER GDEM	3	3	2	3	11
ALOS World 3D	4	3	1.5	4	12.5
Copernicus DEMs	4	3	3	4	14

Table 46 - Comparison of the detailed FAIR notations.

The Copernicus DEMs fully meet the FAIR principles and are given the best FAIR note among tested DEMs.

5.1.2 Features of Copernicus DEMs compared to other global DEMs

Copernicus DEMs and the three other DEMs have many common features:

- **CRS** - they are expressed in the same “Geographic CRS” that sacrifices the deformations at higher latitudes but is simple to describe.
- **GSD** – the ground sampling distance (size of pixels) is 1” (1 arc-second) matching approximately 30 metres along equator but tending to 0 metres of width when getting closer to the poles.
- **VRS** – the vertical reference system is a geoid model and not an ellipsoid. This is certainly due to the fact that sea-level altitudes have a value 0 above the geoid and this is that users are expecting. One may nevertheless deplore the fact that EGM96 has been chosen and not a more recent Earth gravity model like EGM2008 for the latest versions of the geoid.

DEM	version	mode ⁽¹⁾	observation interval	CRS ⁽²⁾	GSD ⁽³⁾	extents	VRS ⁽⁴⁾
SRTM GL1	3.0 (2015)	IF	11 Feb.2000 - 22 Feb.2000	Geo.	1”	56°S – 60°N	EGM96
ASTER GDEM	2.0 (2011)	PG	Dec.1999 - Feb.2011	Geo.	1”	Global	EGM96
ALOS World 3D	2.2 (Apr.2019)	PG	2006 - 2011	Geo.	1”	Global	EGM96
Copernicus DEMs	2019 v1	IF	2010 - 2015	Geo.	0.4” 1” 3”	Europe Global	EGM2008

- (1) mode IF: interferometry – PG: photogrammetry
 (2) CRS Coordinates Reference System – “Geo” for Geographic ([EPSPG:4326](https://epsg.org/EPSPG:4326)).
 (3) GSD Ground Sampling Distance (size of the pixel)
 (4) VRS Vertical Reference System – EGM: Earth Gravity Model (or geoid).

Table 47 - DEM features.

5.2 Intercomparison of DEMS (qualitative assessment)

Copernicus DEM is compared to ALOS World 3D because this one has been assessed as being the best one in a previous study (see RD-37).

Intercomparison of DEMs (see section 4.1) is a qualitative assessment performed by different users. The first example seems to be “objective” in the sense that water surfaces (here the Lake of Garda in Italy) appear as being flat (see section 5.2.1). The second example is more “subjective” depending on the domain of photo-interpretation, here a geologist (

5.2.1 Lakes are more homogenous in COP-DEM

By computing on-the-fly the difference between two DEMS, one may perform a qualitative assessment to very easily detect defects both at global scale and at large scale:

- **Global scale** - comparison between “ALOS World 3D” (best DEM against SRTMGL1 and ASTER GDEM) and “Copernicus DEM GLO-30” shows defects at high latitudes and along the mountainous chains...
- **Large scale** – local differences are observed that could be due to the difference of ice or snow heights between the acquisition dates, or change of mine depths, or changes of land covers, landslides...

By computing on-the-fly the difference between two DEMs at any scale, one may immediately detect artefacts in few views. The sign and magnitude of the difference often enables to guess which DEM contains the artefact (see the attached figure copied from Figure 5 showing the Lake Garda in Italy).

Depending on the scales, the height variations (roughness) of the landscapes change. For low-scale views (large extents of a region), the relief is smoothed by the pyramidal organisation of the layer and the rendering shall be strongly stretched (for example in the range [-10m;+10m] in the upper attached figure). At high-scale (small extent or zoomed view), variations are more apparent and the stretching may be released (for example in the range [-30m;+30m] as shown in the lower attached figure).

5.2.2 Fine roughness has been smoothed by COP-DEM

Professor [Jean CHOROWICZ](#), specialist in structural geology, has kindly photo-interpreted a Sentinel-2 scene and the two DEMs ALOS World 3D and COP-DEM GLO-30 in the region of the Afar Triangle about which he has published several articles.

Figure 140 shows the three products around the Mount Musa Ali Terara volcano and the Sentinel-2 image makes it possible to distinguish the age of the basaltic flows (the most recent flows being darker) as well as the small volcanoes at the end of rash and slag rich in iron that appear in red colour. The Professor believes that the DEM ALOS World 3D better renders the details of the terrain, the contours of the relief and the rugged ridges of the edge of the caldera.

Figure 141 is located in an area of extension faults. The Sentinel-2 image as well as the DEMs make it possible to distinguish the fault planes and the dip of the fault mirror. The Professor considers once again that the DEM ALOS World 3D better reproduces the rolling landscape (*modelé du terrain* in French) which has been too strongly smoothed by COP-DEM GLO-30.

Figure 140– Afar triangle, Mount Musa Ali Terara ([3D view](#) [2D animation](#)).

Figure 141– Afar triangle, region of Balho, west of Randa ([3D view](#) [2D animation](#)).

5.3 Global analysis of height errors

Five quantitative studies are performed in order to assess the quality of the three (3) Copernicus DEMs, respectively using the five (5) LiDAR measurements: -ICESat-1, -ICESat-2 terrain heights only, -ICESat-2 terrain with canopy heights, -GEDI lowest mode elevation and -GEDI highest return elevation. This section provides a summary of the results obtained in the quantitative assessments of this technical note.

5.3.1 ICESat-1, ICESat-2 and GEDI: technical specifications

The Copernicus DEMs are assessed using reference heights from ICESat-1, ICESat-2 and GEDI missions. The characteristics of these missions are compared and summarized in the following table.

Technical specification	ICESat-1	ICESat-2	GEDI
Instrument name	Geoscience Laser Altimeter System (GLAS)	Advanced Topographic Laser Altimeter System (ATLAS)	Global Ecosystem Dynamics Investigation (GEDI)
First acquisition date	02.20.2003	13.10.2018	25.03.2019
Last acquisition date	11.10.2009	Ongoing	Ongoing
Acquisition frequency	40 Hz	10 KHz / 70 Hz ¹	242 Hz
Ground sampling distance	~170 m	~0.7 m / 100 m ²	~60 m
Central wavelength	532 nm (green) / 1064 nm (near infrared)	532 nm (green)	1064 nm (near infrared)
Number of beams	1	6	8
Repeat cycle	Phase 1 – 8 days – [20/02/2003; 04/10/2003] Phase 2 – 91 days – [04/10/2003; 11/10/2009]	91 days	No repeat cycle
Footprint diameter	~70 m	~13 m / 100 m ³	~25 m

Table 48 - Technical specifications of ICESat-1, ICESat-2 and GEDI missions.

The GLAH14 product of the ICESat-1 mission, the ATL08 product of the ICESat-2 mission and the GEDI02_A product of the GEDI mission are used as vertical references in the quantitative studies. The results of the quantitative studies considering ICESat-1, ICESat-2 and GEDI products as vertical references are shown and discussed hereafter in next section 5.3.2.

¹ This high frequency matches the primary frequency of the ATLAS instrument. The ATL08 product that has been used to assess the accuracy of the DEMs is an aggregation of the elementary beams in segments of 100 m along track (see section 4.3.3.1.2).

² See previous note 1.

³ See previous note 1

5.3.2 Results of the EEA-10, GLO-30 and GLO-90 quantitative assessments

The LE95 height error statistics of Copernicus DEM EEA-10, Copernicus DEM GLO-30 and Copernicus DEM GLO-90 are summarized in the following table and histograms.

Copernicus DEM instance	Reference heights	Count	Min	Max	Mean	Standard Deviation	RMSE	Skewness	Kurtosis
EEA-10	ICESat-1	1 803 551	-5.924 m	5.924 m	0.270 m	1.389 m	1.415 m	1.091	3.797
	ICESat-2 terrain only	399 179	-8.415 m	8.421 m	0.822 m	1.944 m	2.111 m	1.283	2.823
	ICESat-2 terrain with canopy	399 179	-16.642 m	16.600 m	-5.477 m	4.838 m	7.307 m	0.251	-0.777
	GED1 lowest mode	10 995 616	-19.490 m	19.540 m	2.167 m	5.027 m	5.474 m	1.610	2.031
	GED1 highest return	10 995 618	-17.129 m	16.960 m	-6.834 m	3.774 m	7.807 m	-0.218	2.017
GLO-30	ICESat-1	59 319 279	-2.725 m	2.725 m	0.033 m	0.627 m	0.628 m	0.943	3.594
	ICESat-2 terrain only	13 816 724	-5.012 m	5.012 m	0.195 m	0.979 m	0.999 m	1.667	6.085
	ICESat-2 terrain with canopy	13 816 724	-11.008 m	11.008 m	-1.124 m	2.680 m	2.907 m	-1.953	3.318
	GED1 lowest mode	205 139 948	-14.200 m	14.240 m	1.001 m	3.281 m	3.431 m	1.759	3.937
	GED1 highest return	205 139 948	-15.320 m	15.180 m	-5.786 m	3.180 m	6.603 m	-0.663	2.147
GLO-90	ICESat-1	59 396 074	-3.015 m	3.015 m	0.066 m	0.706 m	0.709 m	0.793	3.600
	ICESat-2 terrain only	13 838 239	-6.256 m	6.256 m	0.271 m	1.391 m	1.417 m	0.919	4.759
	ICESat-2 terrain with canopy	13 838 239	-11.308 m	11.308 m	-1.102 m	2.898 m	3.100 m	-1.587	2.841
	GED1 lowest mode	205 748 661	-15.010 m	15.050 m	1.036 m	3.731 m	3.872 m	1.198	3.325
	GED1 highest return	205 748 661	-16.780 m	16.639 m	-5.704 m	3.683 m	6.789 m	-0.503	2.294

Table 49 - Copernicus DEM EEA-10, GLO-30 and GLO-90 LE95 height errors statistics.

Copernicus DEM EEA-10 - Comparison with ICESat-1, ICESat-2 and GEDI (LE95)

Copernicus DEM EEA-10 - Comparison with ICESat-1, ICESat-2 and GEDI (LE95)

Figure 142 - Copernicus DEM EEA-10 height error histogram from -17 m to 17 m (left) – from -3 m to 3 m (right).

Copernicus DEM GLO-30 - Comparison with ICESat-1, ICESat-2 and GEDI (LE95)

Copernicus DEM GLO-30 - Comparison with ICESat-1, ICESat-2 and GEDI (LE95)

Figure 143 - Copernicus DEM GLO-30 height error histogram from -17 m to 17 m (left) – from -3 m to 3 m (right).

Copernicus DEM GLO-90 - Comparison with ICESat-1, ICESat-2 and GEDI (LE95)

Copernicus DEM GLO-90 - Comparison with ICESat-1, ICESat-2 and GEDI (LE95)

Figure 144 - Copernicus DEM GLO-90 height error histogram from -17 m to 17 m (left) – from -3 m to 3 m (right).

5.3.2.1 GLO-30 gets the best results

The height error statistics of Table 49 show that the Copernicus DEM GLO-30 has the lowest mean (0.033 metres), standard deviation (0.627 metres) and RMSE (0.628 metres) of all the quantitative studies (ICESat-1 quantitative study). The Copernicus DEM GLO-90 shows similar height error statistics, with a mean of 0.066 metres, a standard deviation of 0.706 m and a RMSE of 0.709 metres (ICESat-1 quantitative study). The worst results are obtained with Copernicus DEM EEA-10, for which the height error statistics result in a mean of 0.270 metres, a standard deviation of 1.389 metres and a RMSE of 1.415 metres (ICESat-1 quantitative

study). These results are also visible on the height error histograms, for which the Copernicus DEM GLO-30 and Copernicus DEM GLO-90 obtain similar distributions with a low standard deviation. The Copernicus DEM EEA-10 height error histogram differs from this distribution, with a lower mode and a greater standard deviation. The same ranking applies for the ICESat-2 terrain only, ICESat-2 terrain with canopy, GEDI lowest mode and GEDI highest return quantitative studies. Among the three DEMs, according to these quantitative studies, **Copernicus DEM GLO-30** obtains the best statistics. Further studies are followed in section 5.3.3, for which Copernicus DEM EEA-10, GLO-30 and GLO-90 are compared over the EEA-10 geographical extent.

5.3.2.2 ICESat-1 leads to the best results

The height error statistics also show that using ICESat-1 as a vertical reference gives the best results for every instance of the Copernicus DEM assessed. Relatively similar results are obtained with ICESat-2 terrain heights only. Worse results are obtained considering ICESat-2 terrain with canopy, which is depicted in the histogram by a large number of negative errors. The height error may increase accounting ICESat-2 canopy heights, as these canopy heights are only estimations (see sections 4.3.4.4.1 and 4.3.4.4.2 for further explanations). For the three DEMs, GEDI lowest mode obtains the highest height error standard deviation, and GEDI highest return obtains the highest absolute mean and RMSE. As a consequence, the recommended reference data is the **GLAH14 product of ICESat-1**, which gives the best results for all the quantitative studies. Such conclusion could be due to the fact that Copernicus DEM has been validated (but may be also calibrated) from ICESat-1 data (see RD-15).

5.3.3 Comparison of EEA-10, GLO-30 and GLO-90 over Europe

5.3.3.1 Comparison of the 3 DEMs in their original spatial extents

In section 4.2, EEA-10, GLO-30 and GLO-90 are compared to ICESat-1 data over their respective geographical extent (whole globe for GLO-30 and GLO-90, only Europe for EEA-10). Despite having a better spatial resolution, the **EEA-10 product shows worse height error statistics than the GLO-30 and GLO-90 products** (see Table 10, Table 11, and Table 12).

The following statistics show the results of this study at variable headcounts.

	EEA-10 – ICESat-1	GLO-30 – ICESat-1	GLO-90 – ICESat-1
Number of ICESat-1 samples	1 803 551	59 319 279	59 396 074
Min	-5.924 m	-2,725 m	-3.015 m
Max	5.924 m	2,725 m	3.015 m
Arithmetic mean (metres)	0.270 m	0,033 m	0.066 m
Standard deviation (metres)	1.389 m	0,627 m	0.706 m
RMSE (metres)	1.415 m	0,628 m	0.709 m

Table 50 - Copernicus DEM EEA-10, GLO-30 and GLO-90 height errors statistics over Europe.

The differences observed between the results of the three DEMs may be due to the different spatial extents (Europe only for EEA-10 and whole world for GLO-30 and GLO-90). To avoid this possible bias, a specific study has been performed (see next section 5.3.3.2).

Height error statistics of each DEM over Europe only are really close in Table 51. Consequently, EEA-10 height errors statistics in Table 50 are worse than the global statistics of GLO-30 and GLO-90 mostly because of EEA-10 geographical extent.

5.3.3.2 Comparison of the 3 DEMs restricted to European extents

In this section, the EEA-10, GLO-30 and GLO-90 DEMs height error statistics are compared (linear error at 95% statistics) from the same LiDAR samples. These height errors are computed using ICESat-1 data as a reference (see section 4.2). The goal of this study is to compare the EEA-10, GLO-30 and GLO-90 products on the EEA-10 product's geographical extent (Europe continent and worldwide European islands).

The following statistics show the results of this study at constant headcount.

	EEA-10 – ICESat-1	GLO-30 – ICESat-1	GLO-90 – ICESat-1
Number of ICESat-1 samples	1 803 551		
Min	-5.924 m	-5.460 m	-5.289 m
Max	5.924 m	5.460 m	5.289 m
Arithmetic mean (metres)	0.270°m	0.297°m	0.351°m
Standard deviation (metres)	1.389°m	1.264°m	1.339 m
RMSE (metres)	1.415 m	1.298 m	1.384 m

Table 51 - Copernicus DEM EEA-10, GLO-30 and GLO-90 height errors statistics over Europe.

Figure 145 - Copernicus DEM EEA-10, GLO-30 and GLO-90 height errors histogram over Europe.

The height error histogram of the EEA-10, GLO-30 and GLO-90 products also show similar error distributions. It must be noticed that the EEA-10 product still performs worse than GLO-30 and GLO-90. This difference may be linked to ICESat-1's footprint diameter of 70 m, which is 7 times the 10 metres resolution of Copernicus DEM EEA-10 at equator.

5.3.4 Comparison of GLO-30 vs. SRTM, ASTER-GDEM and ALOS World 3D

In this section, the Copernicus DEM GLO-30 error statistics are compared to other global DEM statistics. The table here after sums up the quantitative assessment of the GLO-30 DEM,

SRTM, ASTER GDEM and ALOS World 3D with regard to the ICESat-1 and ICESat-2 reference data (LE95).

LE95 statistics	Reference data	Number of heights compared	Arithmetic mean (metres)	Standard deviation (metres)	RMSE (metres)	Median (metres)
SRTMGL1	ICESat-1	57 152 763	-0.561 m	2.491 m	2.554 m	-0.60 m
ASTER GDEM	ICESat-1	88 267 823	-2.709 m	7.432 m	7.911 m	-2.62 m
ALOS World 3D	ICESat-1	57 968 266	-0.151 m	1.653 m	1.660 m	-0.15 m
Copernicus DEM GLO-30	ICESat-1	59 319 279	<u>0.033 m</u>	<u>0.627°m</u>	<u>0.628°m</u>	0.04 m
	ICESat-2 terrain only	13 816 724	0.195 m	0.979 m	0.999 m	<u>-0.01 m</u>
	ICESat-2 terrain with canopy	13 816 724	-1.124 m	2.680 m	2.907 m	0.14 m
	GEDI lowest mode	205 139 948	1.001 m	3.281 m	3.431 m	-0.10 m
	GEDI highest return	205 139 948	-5.786 m	3.180 m	6.603 m	-4.51 m

Table 52 - Quantitative assessment of GLO-30 compared to other global DEMs.

The statistics tend to show that Copernicus DEM GLO-30 is the most accurate DEM among those being assessed. This is also highlighted by comparing the height error histograms of each DEM.

The following histograms show the distribution of the four qualified DEMs in percentage of occurrence (LE95). One can see the distribution of:

- SRTMGL1 – ICESat-1 in orange,
- ASTER GDEM – ICESat-1 in blue,
- ALOS World 3D – ICESat-1 in purple,
- Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – ICESat-1 in black,
- Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – ICESat-2 terrain only in yellow,
- Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – ICESat-2 terrain with canopy in green,
- Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – GEDI lowest mode in red,
- Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – GEDI highest return in cyan.

Figure 146 - Histogram of height differences between ICESat-1/ICESat-2 and global DEMs (LE95).

The height error histograms of the (Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – ICESat-1) and (Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – ICESat-2 terrain only) quantitative studies show that Copernicus DEM GLO-30 significantly outperforms SRTMGL1, ASTER GDEM and ALOS World 3D in terms of **precision**. Even for the (Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – GEDI lowest mode) histogram, one may observe a higher mode than those of the other global DEMs. The (Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – ICESat-2 terrain with canopy) errors seems to follow the distribution of the other Copernicus DEM GLO-30 studies, but the tail of distribution is longer due to the introduction of the ICESat-2 estimated canopy height. Most of the (Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – GEDI highest return) errors are negative, showing that Copernicus DEM GLO-30 is closer to GEDI lowest mode (ground return) than to GEDI highest return (top of canopy return).

According to this study, **Copernicus DEM GLO-30** shows the best **accuracy** with the lowest arithmetic mean (0.033°m). The same applies for the best standard deviation (0.627°m) and RMSE (0.628°m) when compared to ICESat-1 reference data.

5.4 Spatial distribution of EEA-10, GLO-30 and GLO-90 errors

In section 4.5, methods and results of the spatial distribution analysis are given for each DEM vs. LiDAR quantitative study. The following figures are a summary of these studies, giving the spatial distribution and statistics for **Copernicus DEM EEA-10, GLO-30 and GLO-90** compared to **ICESat-1, ICESat-2 terrain only, ICESat-2 terrain with canopy, GEDI lowest mode and GEDI highest return** reference data. The statistics are given as linear error at 95% (**LE95**).

For each COP-DEM, a page includes three parts:

- the static array giving for each one of the 5 LiDAR measurements the
 - **Number of pixels** – the total number N of the whole image (3665 lines x 5545 columns for Europe and 12000 lines 36000 columns for the world),
 - **Computed pixel** – total number C of pixels having at least one valid LiDAR measurement within its aggregation disk (see section 4.5.1.2),
 - **Computed pixels (%)** – the proportion of pixels actually initialised $100 * C/N$,
 - **Arithmetic mean** – the sum of the errors (difference between the interpolated DEM value and the LiDAR measurement) found within the aggregation disk divided by the number of samples found within the disk,
 - **Standard deviation** – quadratic mean of the difference between each error and the arithmetic mean,
 - **Min** – minimum error found within the aggregation disk,
 - **Max** – maximum error found within the aggregation disk.
- the histograms computed from the spatial aggregation image showing the distributions of errors for each LiDAR
 - ICESat-1 in black
 - ICESat-2 terrain only in orange
 - ICESat-2 terrain with canopy in green
 - GEDI lowest mode in brown
 - GEDI highest return in blue
- the spatial aggregation images computed from each LiDAR datasets. A land use / land cover (LU/LC) images is displayed first to guess a possible relation between the error clusters and a particular LU/LC class. A more systematic analysis of the relation between the error distribution and the LU/LC class is performed above in section 4.6 and summarised here after in section 5.5.

5.4.1 Copernicus DEM EEA-10

	e _{LE95}				
	ICESat-1	ICESat-2 terrain only	ICESat-2 terrain with canopy	GEDI lowest mode	GEDI highest return
Number of pixels	20 322 425	20 322 425	20 322 425	20 322 425	20 322 425
Computed pixels	11 514 092	11 648 713	11 642 341	6 413 648	6 413 709
Computed pixels (%)	56.66	57.32	57.29	31.56	31.56
Arithmetic mean	0.256	1.016	-6.616	2.006	-7.064
Standard deviation	0.422	0.876	2.699	1.610	1.198
Min	-5.290	-5.772	-16.638	-18.145	-17.608
Max	5.488	8.394	7.501	18.025	13.001

ICESat-1, and to a lesser extent ICESat-2 terrain only show the best performances in terms of accuracy (bias measured by the arithmetic mean) and precision (dispersion of difference values around the arithmetic mean measured by the error standard deviation also called root mean square error or RMSE). We note however an error cluster on the Scandinavian Forest illustrated by a positive secondary mode in the histogram of ICESat-1 which illustrates values of EEA-10 above those of ICESat-1.

The almost uniform blue color for the "ICESat-2 terrain with canopy" and "GEDI highest return" LiDARs shows that EEA-10 is still far below the LiDAR measurements (mean at -6.616 m and -7.064 m).

Figure 147 - Copernicus DEM EEA-10 – spatial distribution of errors maps and statistics (LE95).

5.4.2 Copernicus DEM GLO-30

	e _{LE95}				
	ICESat-1	ICESat-2 terrain only	ICESat-2 terrain with canopy	GEDI lowest mode	GEDI highest return
Number of pixels	432 000 000	432 000 000	432 000 000	432 000 000	432 000 000
Computed pixels	149 494 779	151 673 311	151 759 064	122 022 742	122 008 589
Computed pixels (%)	34.61	35.11	35.13	28.25	28.24
Arithmetic mean	0.653	0.779	-3.826	1.822	-6.324
Standard deviation	1.772	0.855	2.856	2.540	1.838
Min	-723.918	-4.974	-11.005	-14.758	-15.769
Max	140.459	5.009	10.527	15.005	14.812

ICESat-1 shows the best accuracy (bias) and precision (RMSE) for GLO-30, even if the performance is degraded compared to that obtained for EEA-10. For "ICESat-2 terrain only" and for "GEDI lowest mode", we note red clusters above boreal and tropical forests showing that LiDAR has reached the ground but that many GLO-30 heights are above with a mode at about 1.50 m which could correspond to low vegetation.

Figure 148 - Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – spatial distribution of errors maps and statistics (LE95).

5.4.3 Copernicus DEM GLO-90

	e _{LE95}				
	ICESat-1	ICESat-2 terrain only	ICESat-2 terrain with canopy	GEDI lowest mode	GEDI highest return
Number of pixels	432 000 000	432 000 000	432 000 000	432 000 000	432 000 000
Computed pixels	150 108 645	152 652 690	152 854 677	122 047 694	122 019 276
Computed pixels (%)	34.75	35.34	35.38	28.25	28.25
Arithmetic mean	0.209	1.014	-3.728	1.762	-6.159
Standard deviation	0.383	1.101	2.856	2.510	1.787
Min	-3.014	-6.246	-11.307	-15.532	-17.185
Max	3.015	6.248	11.072	15.519	16.692

Although the appearance of the histograms of GLO-30 and GLO-90 are very similar, it is noted that the accuracy of GLO-90 compared to ICESat-1 is of all the best (arithmetic mean at 0.209 m only). This excellent performance is probably due to the fact that the sampling distance of GLO-90 (90 m) is close to the footprint diameter of ICESat-1 (70 m).

Figure 149 - Copernicus DEM GLO-90 – spatial distribution of errors maps and statistics (LE95).

5.5 Land use / land cover vs. DEM height errors – Quantitative assessment

5.5.1 Copernicus DEM heights analysis over canopy

Copernicus DEM (here EEA-10), clearly shows the presence of wooded areas.

In the Landes forest in France (fig.a), one can distinguish the forest plots (fig.c) by stretching the restitution of heights in pseudo-colour in the interval [50m; 100m].

Fig.d shows the elevation profiles of the two LiDAR measurements "GEDI lowest mode" (represented by a single black line) and "GEDI highest return" (represented by a transparent coloured profile). The colour chart varies from blue (+120 m) to red (+135 m) allowing to assess the difference ("GEDI highest return" - "GEDI lowest mode") at about 14 m.

This value can be compared to the 9 m of the EEA-10 profile shown in fig.e. The footprint of this profile is shown in fig.b.

Heights in EEA-10 (9 m) are therefore significantly less than those of LiDAR "GEDI highest return" (14 m).

Figure 150 - Copernicus DEM EEA-10 canopy heights over the Landes – France Comparison with GEDI lowest mode and highest return height profiles.

5.5.2 Comparison of distributions per class for the 3 ground sampling distances (GSD)

Figure 151 below compares the distributions for the different LU/LC classes for the 3 COP-DEMs: -EEA-10 at European level (copied from Figure 98), -GLO-30 at world level (copied from Figure 108), and -GLO-90 at world level (copied from Figure 118).

One may observe that GLO-30 and GLO-90 are very similar and differ from the EEA-10 distribution. In particular:

- “croplands” (10, 11) are much more populated at European level than at world level,
- “grassland” (130) has almost the same frequency in the 3 DEMs,
- “bare areas” (200) is much more represented at world level (certainly due to the extents of large deserts present at world level but almost absent at European level),
- “Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, closed to open (>15%)” is dominant at European level (certainly due to the extents of the Scandinavian forests).

Figure 151 - Comparison of distribution per class of EEA-10 (top), GLO-30 (bottom left) and GLO-90 (bottom right).

5.5.3 COP-DEM above terrain

The comparison of COP-DEM EEA-10 vs. ICESat-1 and “ICESat-2 terrain only” over forest areas demonstrates that a large majority of COP-DEM heights is above the terrain.

As shown in Figure 152, almost all the classes, and in particular the croplands and grasslands, have a zero-centred error mean with a low standard deviation. Class 70 “Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, closed to open (>15%)” that is one of the most populated in Europe shows a long rightward tail meaning that Copernicus DEM is above the ICESat-1 and “ICESat-2 terrain only” measurements. This difference is particularly noticeable for “ICESat-2 terrain only” (see the right part of the figure).

ICESat-1 is considered as a “surface” LiDAR measurement while “ICESat-2 terrain only” is by definition a “terrain” LiDAR. The fact that in both cases EEA-10 is above these two LiDARs demonstrates that EEA-1, and more generally all the COP-DEMs that derive from the same TanDEM-X data, cannot be considered as pure DTM (Digital Terrain Model).

Figure 152– Comparison of errors histograms (Copernicus DEM EEA-10 – ICESat-1 LE95) on the left and (Copernicus DEM EEA-10 – ICESat-2 terrain only LE95) on the right - classified with C3S-LC 2013.

5.5.4 COP-DEM below surface

The comparison of COP-DEM EEA-10 vs. “ICESat-2 terrain with canopy” over forest and cropland / grassland areas demonstrates that a majority of COP-DEM heights is below the surface.

As illustrated in Figure 153, the cropland classes (10, 11, 12 and 20) show a first mode close to zero, with a long tail of distribution of negative values meaning that EEA-10 is below the LiDAR measurements. One may observe class 70 “Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, closed to open (>15%)” shows a leftward mode centred around -9.542 m. This class, like almost all the other classes, has a very large standard deviation and RMSE that are probably due to the heterogeneity and disparity of tree heights inside a 300x300 m² cell.

Considering class 70, the fact that EEA-10 is above the “ICESat-2 terrain only” measurement (see preceding section 5.5.2) and below the “ICESat-2 terrain with canopy” shows that **Copernicus DEM cannot be considered as pure DTM (Digital Terrain Model) nor a pure DSM (Digital Surface Model) but stands between a DTM and a DSM.**

Figure 153 – Error histograms of (Copernicus DEM EEA-10 – ICESat-2 terrain with canopy LE95) classified with C3S-LC 2013.

5.5.5 Influence of canopy opening on height differences

In Figure 154, height differences between GLO-30 and GEDI lowest mode (top left) / highest return (top right) are analysed over **tree cover classes**. In this case study, broadleaved deciduous trees are considered, **only the canopy opening varies**. One may observe the following for each distribution:

- Open (15-40%) – Among the three canopy opening classes, the open canopy distribution gives the lowest overall differences between GLO-30 and GEDI for both lowest mode and highest return measurements. As the canopy is classified as open, the chances of comparing both EEA-10 and GEDI heights at terrain level is higher than in other classes. This fact may explain the better results obtained with open canopy than with the two other classes.
- Closed (15-40%) – The closed canopy class distribution show greater standard deviation and mean for both GEDI lowest mode and highest return than the open canopy class. One may also observe the presence of multiple modes in the GEDI lowest mode distribution. This fact could reflect the different levels of GLO-30 heights for this class, being retrieved close to terrain, low vegetation or high vegetation depending on the areas.
- Closed to open (<15%) – As one may expect, the closed to open canopy distribution shares common features with both open canopy and closed canopy cover classes. Considering GEDI lowest mode data, one may see that the closed to open canopy class has only one mode such as the open canopy class, but also has a long tail of distribution in positive values, such as the closed canopy class. Such similarities are also visible in the GEDI highest return distributions, for which both modes seem to match shapes of the open canopy and closed canopy classes.

Figure 154 – Comparison of errors histograms (Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – GEDI lowest mode) on the top left and (Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – highest return) on the top right - influence of canopy opening over forests.

5.5.6 Influence of leaf shape on height differences

In Figure 155, height differences between GLO-30 and GEDI lowest mode (top left) / highest return (top right) are analysed over **tree cover classes**. In this case study, deciduous trees and open to closed canopy are considered, **only the leaf shape varies**.

The (GLO-30 – GEDI lowest mode) and (GLO-30 – GEDI highest return) studies highlight two different behaviours:

- GLO-30 – GEDI lowest mode – Both broadleaved and needleleaved classes give similar distributions. As Copernicus DEM is not a DTM (Digital Terrain Model), comparing Copernicus DEM heights to the terrain heights of GEDI lowest mode result in positive errors.
- GLO-30 – GEDI highest return – As opposed to the (GLO-30 – GEDI lowest mode) study, different overall distributions are observed for broadleaved and needleleaved classes. One may note that the needleleaved and broadleaved class share the same overall shape, but have different main modes. The first mode (closest to zero) is higher for the needleleaved class than for the broadleaved class, whereas the second mode (furthest to zero) is higher for the broadleaved class than for the needleleaved class. Considering the highest return is always higher than the lowest mode (see bottom left histogram), the first mode (closest to zero) may occur when both Copernicus DEM and GEDI highest return heights are relative to the ground. Then, the second mode (furthest to zero) may be explained by the GEDI highest return measurement, which is the highest point acquired within a 25 metres footprint. In cases of varying canopy heights, Copernicus DEM heights are relative to the top of canopy, whereas the GEDI highest return heights are relative to the highest point in the canopy within its footprint.

Figure 155 – Comparison of errors histograms (Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – GEDI lowest mode) on the top left and (Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – highest return) on the top right - influence of leaf shape over forests.

5.5.7 Influence of leaf life span on height differences

In Figure 156, height differences between GLO-30 and GEDI lowest mode (top left) / highest return (top right) are analysed over **tree cover classes**. In this case study, broadleaved deciduous trees and open to closed canopy are considered, **only the leaf life span varies**.

The (GLO-30 – GEDI lowest mode) and (GLO-30 – GEDI highest return) studies highlight two different behaviours:

- GLO-30 – GEDI lowest mode – One can see a high proportion of Copernicus DEM heights being close to GEDI lowest mode for the deciduous class than for the evergreen class. As the leaves are deciduous, an important part of Copernicus DEM heights can be generated from the ground than from the top of canopy, which is not the case for evergreen trees.
- GLO-30 – GEDI highest return – One can see higher errors considering the evergreen class than considering the deciduous class. Considering the highest return is always higher than the lowest mode (see bottom left histogram), the first mode (closest to zero) may occur when both Copernicus DEM and GEDI highest return heights are relative to the ground. The proportion of these differences is higher in the deciduous class than in the evergreen class, because more Copernicus DEM heights can be retrieved from the ground. As a consequence, the evergreen class shows a higher proportion of Copernicus DEM surface heights compared to the GEDI highest return, which is the highest point within the canopy.

Figure 156 – Comparison of errors histograms (Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – GEDI lowest mode) on the top left and (Copernicus DEM GLO-30 – highest return) on the top right - influence of leaf life span over forests.